

PLAN'EAT

ON OUR WAY TO TRANSFORMING FOOD SYSTEMS

Policy document

For an innovative framework to develop food-based dietary guidelines

PLAN'EAT

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Participant responsible CREA

Main authors Federica Grant*(CREA),
Vittoria Aureli*(CREA),
Laura Rossi (CREA)

*These authors contributed equally to this work and share first authorship

Authors' contributions Eileen Gibney (UCD), Fanny Salesse (UCD),
Olivia Riemer (TMG), Gültaç Çınar (TMG),
Nathanael Picas (HOPSCOTCH), Philippine Bondil (HOPSCOTCH)

Website <https://planeat-project.eu/>

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		Cardiovascular, Endocrine-metabolic Diseases ; Nutrition and Health, MSc - Sustainable food expert at Netherlands Nutrition Centre; Andrea Zentai, Leonóra Zámbo, Eszter Sarkadi-Nagy - National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy, Hungary ; Anna Taraszewska, National Institute of Public Health NIH—National Research Institute Medical Center for Dietetics and Health Education ; Marta Jeruszka-Bielak, Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), Warsaw, Poland ; Åsa Brugård Konde, Nutritionist, Swedish Food Agency	
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Acronyms and abbreviations

Terms	Definition
AIDGI	Adherence to Italian Dietary Guidelines Index
ANSES	Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire
BMI	Body Mass Index
CE	Centrum voor Energiebesparing
COFIDS	Composition of Foods Integrated Dataset
COI	Cost of Illness
CVDs	Cardiovascular diseases
DALYs	Disability-Adjusted Life Years
DGE	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Ernährung/ German Society for Nutrition
DGI	Dietary Guidelines Index
DHD	Dutch Healthy Diet
DRV	Dietary Reference Values
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
F&V	Fruits and Vegetables
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FAO AQUASTAT	FAO's Global Information System on Water and Agriculture
FAOSTAT	Food and Agriculture Organization Statistical Database
FBDGs	Food-Based Dietary Guidelines
Food-EPI	Healthy Food Environment Policy Index
FPN	Food Prices for Nutrition
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GRADE	Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluations
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project
HBGV	Health-Based Guidance Value
HEI	Healthy Eating Index
HEPs	Healthy Eating Patterns

HFSS	High in Fat, Sugar and Salt
HICs	High-income countries
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
ICP	International Comparison Program's
IFASTAT	International Fertilizer Association Statistics
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LDL	Low-Density Lipoprotein
LMICs	Low-and-middle-income countries
NCDs	Non-Communicable Diseases
NDGI	Norwegian Dietary Guideline Index
NDNS	National Diet and Nutrition Survey
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NNR	Nordic Nutrition Recommendations
PDCAAS	Protein digestibility-corrected amino acid score
PHD	Planetary Health Diet
PHE	Public Health England
PNNS-GS	Programme National Nutrition Santé Guidelines Score
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment
RCTs	Randomized Controlled Trials
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SHDB	Social Hotspot Database
s-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
TCA	True Cost Accounting
UK	United Kingdom
UPFs	Ultra Processed Foods
USA	United States of America
USD	United States Dollar
WCRF	World Cancer Research Fund
WFR	Weighed Food Records
WHO	World Health Organization

Glossary

Capital	The various resources that represent stocks of value, each capable of generating future benefits that support and enhance human well-being.
Impacts	The effects (positive or negative) that a process, product, or activity has on the environment, society, and economy. In the context of food systems, impacts can include greenhouse gas emissions, labour conditions, and public health outcomes.
Human capital	The knowledge, skills, competencies, and attributes embodied in individuals that facilitate the creation of personal, social, and economic well-being.
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	A scientific method used to evaluate the environmental footprint of a product or process across its entire life cycle; from raw material extraction to production, distribution, consumption, and disposal. LCA helps identify areas for reducing environmental harm and improving sustainability.
Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)	The collection and quantification of inputs and outputs (such as energy, water, raw materials, and emissions) for a product, process, or system throughout its life cycle.
Monetization	The process of assigning a monetary value to impacts.
Natural capital	The limited stocks of earth's physical and biological resources and the limited capacity of ecosystems to provide ecosystem services.
Produced capital	All manufactured capital, such as buildings, factories, machinery, and physical infrastructure (roads, water systems), as well as all financial capital and intellectual capital (technology, software, patents, brands, etc.)
Social capital	Encompasses networks, including institutions, together with shared norms, values, and understandings that facilitate cooperation within or among groups.
True Cost Accounting (TCA)	A method of measuring the real costs and benefits of economic activities by incorporating environmental, social, and health externalities. TCA aims to reveal hidden costs and benefits associated with food systems, guiding decision-makers toward more sustainable practices.

Introduction

The current state of the human health and the European food environment reveals significant challenges and the need to quickly shift population eating behaviours towards healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns [1].

Even though life expectancy in Europe remains high, the prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as cancer, obesity, type 2 diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) has increased worldwide in recent decades, being today responsible for 90% of total premature deaths, 85% of years lived with disability and accounting for 80% of the health burden in European Union (EU) countries [2]. In addition to this, Healthy Life Years at birth in Europe in 2022 accounted for 62.8 years for women and 62.4 years for men [3], indicating that the amount of time spent to reach the expectancy of life (81.5 years in 2023) [4] may be affected by disabilities that reduce the quality of life, including NCDs. In particular CVDs are the leading cause of death in the EU, responsible for 37% of annual deaths (39% in men and 46% in women). In comparison, cancer accounts for 24% of deaths in men and 20% in women with the aggravating factor of being responsible of early death. Additionally, over 33 million people in the EU have diabetes, a number expected to rise to 38 million by 2030 [2]. At the same time, the so-called triple burden of malnutrition, meaning the combination of overnutrition, undernutrition and micronutrient deficiencies within some population groups has become increasingly common, highlighting the complex and multifaceted nature of nutritional challenges [5].

One of the main causes of these health conditions is attributable to unhealthy dietary patterns, characterized by a high intake of foods rich in free sugars, and added salt, saturated and/or trans fats, and low in fibre, which contribute to the rise of NCDs [6]. The Global Burden of Disease Study showed that the most important dietary risk factors for mortality are related to diets high in sodium and low in whole grains, fruits, nuts and oilseeds, vegetables and omega-3 fatty acids [7]. For these reasons, adherence to a healthy diet plays a key role in preventing and limiting the incidence and prevalence of NCDs. Evidence now supports the benefits of a dietary pattern rich in plant sources of fat and protein, fish, nuts, whole grains, fruits and vegetables, avoiding foods sources of partially hydrogenated fats and limiting red and processed meat, and food sources of refined carbohydrates, some Ultra-Processed Foods (UPFs) and discretionary foods [8,9].

Besides this, the European food system is an important contributor to puts significant pressure on climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource depletion, highlighting the need for sustainable food systems transformation [10]. In particular, meat and dairy production [11–13], due to their agronomic and zootechnical activities have one of the highest environmental impact and can be a significant target for change [14]. According to the Global Nutrition Report figures, animal-based products such as beef, lamb, pork and poultry contribute the most to the Green House Gas (GHG) emissions and land use, while it should be highlighted that fruit and vegetables and grains contribute more on freshwater use, nitrogen and phosphorus applications [15,16]. However, the adoption of a balanced plant-based diets, preferably based on agroecology [17], can reduce the impact of GHG emissions, land and water use, thus reducing the impact of food production on the environment [18]. Besides this, despite being one of the most advanced systems globally, the European food-system faces inefficiencies, including as food waste (in 2022, the European Union generated approximately 132kg of food waste per inhabitant, totalling over 59 million tonnes [19]) and unequal access to nutritious food, with rates of food insecurity in Europe around 9% [20]. Addressing these interconnected issues requires an integrated approach that prioritizes health, environmental sustainability, and equity, aligning food production and consumption with planetary boundaries and public health goals [21].

In this context, Food-Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDGs) are a powerful policy tool to address the current challenges in human health and environmental sustainability. Based on evidence-based recommendations, FBDGs translate complex nutritional evidence into actionable population advice aimed at informing consumers and adapted for different target groups (from children to elderly people) [22]. Although FBDGs were originally developed with a focus on human health, the context in which we live necessitates the inclusion of all dimensions of sustainability—health, environmental and social—which are deeply interconnected. FBDGs should promote dietary patterns that are not only healthier but also more sustainable, aligning with environmental objectives, while addressing social equity and ethical considerations in the food system [23,24].

One of the main activities of the Horizon Europe PLAN'EAT project is to propose an innovative framework for the development of dietary guidelines, based on project participating countries dietary pattern mapping (Deliverable 1.2) and True Cost Accounting (TCA) calculation and results (Deliverable 3.3). Although the importance of the FBDG as a public health policy document has been recognised, there are still limitations given the lack of adherence to the guidelines' advice. For this reason, this work aims to identify the main barriers that prevent consumers from following the dietary recommendations and to find a methodology to overcome them.

To this end, this document firstly reviews the main shortcomings and describes the challenges related to methodological aspects together with the communication strategy to share the FBDGs. Secondly, this review provides the basis to propose an innovative approach that would try to achieve the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) recommendations to develop the future dietary guidelines under a food system- based approach [25] together with proposing a solution to standardise the main barriers faced in relation to the recommended foods in terms of categorisation and quantification. The final output of this activity will be a proposal for an innovative framework for European standardization of FBDGs that would be used by EU member states by adopting it according to national cultural, dietary and environmental aspects.

The present work represents the policy document that includes the scientific background supporting the establishment of this innovative framework, which has been delivered in another separate specific document.

FBDGs shortcomings

Methodologies

The process of developing FBDGs involves a complex connection of scientific evidence, public health outcomes, traditions/cultural/geographical considerations, food production and sustainability criteria. This chapter examines the diverse methodological possibilities and approaches used in formulating FBDGs.

One of the most widely recognized method for developing evidence-based dietary guidelines is the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluations (GRADE) system. It aims to provide a transparent and systematic approach to grading the quality of evidence and the strength of recommendations. GRADE categorizes evidence into four levels: 1) High quality (confident that the true effect aligns closely with the estimated effect (typically from randomized controlled trials, RCTs); 2) Moderate quality (moderate confidence in the effect estimate; the true effect may differ); 3) Low quality (Limited confidence in the effect estimate (often observational studies)) and 4) Very Low quality (minimal confidence in the effect estimate [26]. However, one of the main challenges of the GRADE system is its undervaluation of observational studies, which, unlike clinical trials, are often relied upon in nutrition research to explore long-term dietary habits and health outcomes. Additionally, the GRADE system may not sufficiently account a range of contextual variables such as cultural preferences, regional/local dietary patterns, and socio-economic conditions [27,28]. These factors are essential when formulating practical guidelines that people will follow, yet GRADE does not sufficiently account for such issues.

In addition, a scoring system to assess and evaluate the meta-evidence of randomized controlled trials and cohort studies in nutrition research has been developed, namely the NutriGRADE [29]. Although the first assessment demonstrated more reliability of this methodology with respect to the GRADE system and perhaps greater potential in the nutrition-field, the application of this approach does not consider the contextual variables listed in the paragraph above.

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) guidelines [22] outline a stepwise and multi-disciplinary approach, based on the early involvement of stakeholders to promote the acceptance of the FBDGs. This framework is based on the collection of all recent international and national reviews on diet-health relationships and nutrients/foods of public health importance, while also considering country-specific health challenges and culturally relevant food patterns. According to the EFSA approach, the inclusion of all these different aspects is essential to increase acceptance and adherence of FBDGs by the national population. Alongside this, recommendations for FBDGs should be made taking into account specific needs of population groups. At the conclusion of the entire data collection process, two key points emerge as particularly significant: testing and optimizing FBDG and its graphical representation. testing and optimizing FBDG and

its graphical representation. Similarly, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines [30] underline a systematic and inclusive approach. The process begins with the formation of a multidisciplinary working group or a committee with different experts. The methodological framework is based on: the assessment of diet-related health patterns, diseases, and mortality rates to define key public health concerns, review food consumption patterns and their links to health outcomes, identify nutrient deficiencies and foods of public health importance and ensure consistency with existing national policies. It also requires defining the scope of the guidelines, identifying the target audience, and setting clear objectives. Once evidence-based recommendations are developed, the importance of transforming these guidelines into clear and feasible consumer focused messages is emphasized. Despite the differences between EFSA and FAO/WHO guidelines, both approaches underscore the need for inclusive processes and scientifically grounded strategies to develop impactful FBDGs.

Finally, the Nordic Nutrition Recommendations (NNR) framework [31] stresses the analysis of five key pillars for developing FBDGs: public health challenges, food consumption patterns, food availability, sociocultural and socioeconomic aspects, and environmental sustainability. Among these, the integration of environmental sustainability is particularly highlighted, reflecting the growing recognition of its importance. To support this, the NNR framework incorporates science-based advice addressing both the health and environmental impacts of food, providing a comprehensive foundation for sustainable and health-focused dietary recommendations.

METHODOLOGIES USED FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FBDGS

To better understand the methodologies underlying European FBDGs, a detailed analysis of the documents available in the FAO repository [32] was conducted, highlighting differences in approaches and levels of methodological details. The analysis covered 33 European countries. In order to effectively categorize the approaches used, three distinct methodological categories have been identified: 1) evidence-based; 2) basic quantitative calculations and 3) data modelling.

The majority of countries (30 out of 33), primarily rely on literature and evidence reviews supported by scientific consensus. This suggests a strong emphasis on grounding FBDGs in established research and multidisciplinary expert agreement. A smaller subset of countries (8 out of 33) combines this approach with basic calculations, indicating some integration of quantitative methods into their processes. Only few countries, such as Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, add data modelling techniques. This approach offers a sophisticated tool for integrating all sustainability aspects (health, environmental and social). For this reason, diet optimization models will be explored in greater detail in the following paragraphs.

DATA MODELING SYSTEM

In general terms, a diet optimization model is a method aiming to identify the optimal combination of foods for a population, a specific target group or an individual, that minimizes or maximizes an objective function (such as cost, calories, GHGs) while fulfilling a set of constraints (such as nutritional and dietary recommendations, environmental impact) [33]. A constrained optimization model has the potential to simultaneously apply constraints to different characteristics of a diet [34]. Different studies carried out in the European region [10,35–38] were conducted with the aim to optimise the current diet to achieve health and environmentally sustainable objectives considering the habitual food consumption patterns as a proxy of acceptability [39].

The theoretical application of the diet modelling approach to establish dietary recommendations and to set up FBDGs has been considered for many years by different studies applying various methodologies, even though sustainability aspects were not always included [27–29].

As previously reported France, Germany, the Netherlands, Denmark and the United Kingdom (UK) have already adopted a modelling system to develop their FBDGs. A related-detailed description of the method is reported in the following paragraph in which the countries were divided into those including sustainability aspects and those not including them.

EXAMPLE COUNTRIES INCLUDING SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS

Germany

The German Society for Nutrition (DGE) has developed a new methodology based on mathematical optimisation model MS Nutrition [43] to update FBDGs, released in 2024, using three dimensions [44,45]:

- 1) health aspects (food-health ratios and energy and nutrient intake);
- 2) environmental aspects (greenhouse gas emissions and land use);
- 3) the usual food consumption in Germany.

The target function consisted of three components:

1. minimisation (reduction) of the disease burden in Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs),
2. minimisation (reduction) of the environmental burden and
3. minimisation of deviations from current food consumption (proximity to the usual consumption).

The data used consists of the average food consumption in the adult population, the energy and nutrients intake, the food-health relationships and the environmental impact.

Using this approach deviation from normal food consumption was minimised, the relative risk of developing diet-related diseases was reduced, and the optimisation outcomes were within the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) target of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C [46].

The Netherlands

In 2016 the Optimeal® programme ([Sustainable diets | Mérieux NutriSciences | Blonk](#)) was used for the development of the Wheel of Five [47]. For this process, the Dutch dietary guidelines, Dietary Reference Values (DRV), and current Dutch consumption patterns were considered together with expert judgement. Several maximum restrictions were set for food groups due to environmental sustainability and feasibility while staying as close as possible to people's current consumption patterns, but no restrictions were set on environmental indicators (66). Subsequently, the environmental impact of the Dutch FBDGs was calculated together with the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment [24,48].

Currently, the Netherlands Nutrition Centre is working on an update of their FBDG, integrating both health, sustainability and food safety aspects in their optimisation model for various population subgroups and eating preferences (e.g. vegetarian).

Denmark

In 2021, the Danish FBDGs (2021) were updated through a diet modelling system considering health and environmental aspects, in order to develop a rich plant-based dietary recommendations [49]. Two approaches were developed and assessed. The first one, considered the EAT-Lancet Commission recommendations as the reference diet, but also taking into account food availability and the adjustment to a total energy intake reference (10 MJ). The results obtained from this model, were adjusted through a second model that considered Danish habitual dietary intake, together with the national FBDGs and food habits and preferences.

Finally, the modelled intake was adjusted to be in line with the latest scientific evidence on the relationship between food intake and disease risk, ensuring the agreement with nutritional recommendations,

EXAMPLE COUNTRIES NOT INCLUDING SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS

France

The Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire (ANSES) developed a method to establish Healthy Eating Patterns (HEPs) for the new French FBDGs, released in 2016, for adult men (18–65 y) and women (18–55 y), which consists of an in-depth food pattern modelling approach (linear programming of combined model -code language C++ with IBM® CPLEX software) using an enhanced optimization method gathering all the multiple aspects of HEPs [50,51].

A modelled diet consisting of the daily consumption of each of 32 food groups selected was identified. The established constraints are reported as follows:

1. Nutrient constraints were set so that the modelled diet complied with the DRVs;
2. Maximal limits were added as constraints to food groups whose consumption is associated with an increased risk of NCDs;
3. Dietary habit constraints were set so that the modelled diet remained within the range of observed food consumption;
4. Contaminant constraints were determined to ensure that output exposure remained at or below the Health-Based Guidance Value (HBGV), or, when the HBGV was a benchmark dose limit, below the median of the observed exposure of the population.

This function applied combined several criteria to minimize deviations from observed consumption, minimize (or maximize) the consumption of certain food groups to prevent NCDs, and possibly minimize exposure to contaminants.

The United Kingdom (UK)

The Eatwell Guide was developed by Public Health England (PHE) uses a data-driven approach to represent dietary recommendations in the UK, that were updated in 2016 [52] Linear programming was employed to calculate food group proportions, ensuring adherence to dietary reference values (DRVs) while minimizing deviations from current dietary habits [53,54].

This methodology was used to optimize food group proportions based on data from:

1. National Diet and Nutrition Survey (NDNS) providing nationally representative data on average food consumption and nutrient intake;
2. Composition of Foods Integrated Dataset (COFIDS) used to analyse the nutritional content of foods.

This approach incorporated specific constraints for nutrients (energy, free sugars, fats, fibre, protein, and salt) and foods/food group (fruit and vegetables, fish and red and processed meat) based on nutrient targets outlined by DRVs and minimizing deviations from current UK dietary habits. The final linear programming modelled scenario met all of the UK dietary recommendations for the average adult.

PHE commissioned the Carbon Trust to conduct a post hoc sustainability assessment of the modelled scenario. Whilst the outcome of this assessment did not inform decisions around the final model, it indicated that the modelled scenario had an appreciably lower environmental impact than the current UK diet.

From this analysis it can be pointed out how the application of a modelling system could be suggested as a viable approach to consider various aspects simultaneously, considering the aim of the FBDGs to encourage the adoption of healthy and sustainable diets. This can be completed as part of the initially modelling process, or post hoc as in the example of the UK. Since the concept of a sustainable diet includes different dimensions starting from its definition of being nutritionally adequate, economically affordable, culturally acceptable and environmentally friendly [55], the application of a diet optimization model that integrates different metrics to fulfil the objective to achieve a healthy and sustainable dietary pattern simultaneously, should be a strategy to adopt [33]. This suggestion can be strengthened by the demonstration of this approach, that considering the sustainable dimension, developed by countries as Germany and The Netherlands together with the lack of inclusion of the sustainable question within the FBDGs, as highlighted in the following section.

FBDGs methodologies' summary

The development of FBDGs is a complex process that requires the integration of scientific evidence with public health, food production, sustainability issues, and cultural considerations.

The NutriGRADE system (based on the GRADE system) classifies the quality of scientific evidence, although it has some limitations.

Various national and international organisations, as EFSA, FAO/WHO and the Nordic Council of Ministers, have established recommendations on how to develop dietary guidelines.

The majority of European countries develop dietary guidelines based on literature reviews and scientific consensus. Only a few countries have adopted dietary optimisation models:

- Germany, the Netherlands and Denmark consider health and environmental constraints;
- France and the United Kingdom only consider health constraints.

Other European countries could further explore the modelling approach as a possible innovative methodology considering different sustainable perspectives.

Incorporating sustainability into FBDGs

In recent years, there has been a growing global effort to integrate environmental sustainability criteria into FBDGs, which were traditionally focused solely on human health. Despite these attempts, a lack of a clear methodology on how to effectively incorporate sustainability impacts into dietary recommendations still remains. The most recent review by James-Martin et al. [56] assessed FBDGs of 83 countries worldwide and found that only 37 included environmental sustainability, often manifesting as general advice without actionable or quantified suggestions (such as specifying exact reductions in meat consumption or clear targets for increasing plant-based food intake). The principles most addressed were associated with environmental impact of foods, inclusion of less animal and more plant-based products in the diet, loss of biodiversity, and food waste impact. Besides this, another study analysing 90 FBDGs worldwide, found that only 13 of these FBDGs integrate both environmental sustainability and socio-cultural aspects, emphasizing that future dietary recommendations should consider not only health but all sustainability aspects with environmental (GHGs, water and land use, eutrophication potential, etc.) and social indicators (labor conditions, gender equality, fair trade and ethical sourcing, et.) [23]. Similarly, Martini et al. [57] underscored the need for revisions in future guidelines to address these gaps.

To overcome this situation, Van Dooren et al. (2024) [24] proposed six approaches listed in order of complexity for incorporating sustainability into FBDGs: 1) health first (which is the basis of all current national guidelines that does not consider the use of constraints or sustainability advice); 2) additional advice on environmental sustainability; 3) demonstrating synergies between health and environmental sustainability on integrated messages related to health and the environment; 4) modelling impact in which health and sustainability are taken equally into account by using constraints on these two aspects; 5) combining strategies can be a distinct approach or a series of steps within a policy process aimed at fully integrating environmental sustainability and public health nutrition, potentially reshaping the food system away from past norms and 6) systems first applies a systems thinking approach to developing FBDGs, shifting the focus from 'food-based' to 'food system-based' guidelines. The last two approaches are considered by Van Dooren et al. the most innovative and transformative, aiming to create more sustainable dietary patterns while ensuring that they remain health-promoting [24]. It is also worth noting that these strategies are not mutually exclusive and can be combined.

GLOBAL APPROACHES TO INTEGRATE SUSTAINABILITY INTO FBDGs

Reviewing the documents of countries that have analysed how to improve the presence of sustainability in their FBDGs, notable similarities and differences emerged in the strategies applied that are considered below. The Nordics countries - Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden - identified major challenges in their national food consumptions (high meat consumption and a lower consumption of fish, fruits and vegetables), and opportunities to better improve sustainability criteria aligning food production with regional capacities, with the use of new technologies [58]. Italy focuses on a multidisciplinary approach and in their FBDG translate sustainability into actionable recommendations for consumers even though claiming for the need of further studies on consumer acceptance and perception on sustainability [59]. The United Kingdom's approach has heavily focused on effective communication for consumers, aiming to enhance both the relevance and the impact of sustainable dietary recommendations [60] while Switzerland uses a multistakeholder approach, with different actors focusing on specific sustainability niches [61]. Based on the information contained in the Knowledge for Policy ([Food-Based Dietary Guidelines - Guidance on sustainability | Knowledge for policy](#)), other European countries have incorporated, to varying degrees, qualitative information regarding food sustainability within their FBDGs. Outside Europe, Australia emphasizes the importance of structured local guidelines for feasibility and alignment with national dietary habits, while highlighting the need for significant behavioural changes to improve health and environmental sustainability [62]. A similar approach has also been applied to China and Iran. In fact, regional disparities and

cultural preferences are central to China's strategy, focused on considering different food needs between rural and urban residents [63]. On the other hand, Iran emphasizes in its guidelines the need to adjust food policies and enhance economic and cultural aspects to improve access to sustainable diets [64].

The most recent revision of the United States of America (USA) FBDGs ([Dietary Guidelines for Americans, 2025–2030](#)) continues to represent a major challenge from a sustainability perspective. Although the updated guidelines place a greater emphasis on limiting ultra processed foods and increasing the consumption of fruits, vegetables and whole grains, remain a strong focus on animal food-products, requiring significant changes to address the sustainability issue. Adherence to the USA FBDG is linked to higher carbon emissions, primarily due to its emphasis on animal-based foods such as meat and dairy products, in contrast to dietary patterns like the Mediterranean Diet, which demonstrate a significantly lower carbon footprint due to its high content in plant-based foods [66]. Supporting this perspective, Springmann et al. (2020) found that national dietary guidelines could better promote both health and sustainability by limiting the intake of animal-based products, while advocating for a greater consumption of plant-based foods. These findings underscore the critical need to integrate sustainability criteria into the revision of the USA FBDGs.

These diverse approaches highlight the range of strategies that countries have adopted to incorporate sustainability into their FBDGs. Moreover, it should be considered the different ways in which sustainability can be defined and which individual or combined indicators can be used of, such as GHGs, land use, water consumption, and others, highlighting the complexity and context-dependent nature of incorporating sustainability into dietary guidelines. However, other countries prioritize communication or multistakeholder collaboration, others focus on structural changes and alignment with local dietary habits.

Key considerations for incorporating sustainability into FBDGs

Globally, only 45% of FBDGs include environmental sustainability and less than 15% integrate both environmental dimensions (such as GHGs, land use, water use, biodiversity) and socio-cultural aspects.

The integration of sustainability into FBDGs faces several key challenges: (i) the absence of a standard methodology for embedding sustainability criteria, (ii) the strong context-dependence whereby cultural, economic, and dietary baselines shape national priorities, and (iii) persistent uncertainty regarding which indicators should be included and how they ought to be carried out.

Way forward:

- Develop clear, measurable sustainability criteria in future FBDGs revisions.
- Combine health and sustainability modelling to set actionable targets (e.g., specific meat reduction, plant-based increase, etc.).
- Promote consumer-oriented communication and multi-stakeholder governance to enhance acceptance and feasibility.

Standardization of food groups and portion size

To provide a harmonised or suggested approach to incorporate sustainability into existing FBDGs, it is important to consider the differences in existing FBDGs. Two key aspects of FBDGs that differ across various EU policy documents are related to the standardisation of foods groups and the definition and quantification of portion sizes. The absence in the harmonisation of these aspects represents a challenge at EU level. In fact, these differences can create confusion when comparing dietary advice across regions or designing cross-border nutritional programs or developing a harmonised nutrition labelling system. The lack of alignment in food group standardization and portion size quantification complicates the development of a common framework for harmonized EU-wide dietary guidelines. Maintaining the fact that diverse guidelines need to reflect cultural and regional dietary patterns, the absence of a common basis of recommendation can hinder efforts to provide consistent public health messaging across the EU. Variations also make it harder to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of FBDGs in improving public health outcomes across EU member states. Understanding these differences and proposing harmonisation strategies is critical for policymakers and health professionals aiming to align dietary recommendations while respecting regional diversity.

CHALLENGES IN ACHIEVING STANDARDIZATION OF FOOD GROUPS

The methodological approach applied in the definition of food groups aimed to characterise the types of food within each group, focusing on their nutritional profiles and specific qualities important from a public health point of view [67]. The classification of foods into food groups requires that all the food items included in the group should share some common characteristics, such as their origin (animal or plant) and/or nutrient content and/or role in the diet [68]. The classification of food groups has evolved significantly over the years, influenced by changing nutritional science, health outcomes priorities, and global dietary patterns.

To establish scientifically grounded FBDGs that address diet-health relationships, existing evidence on how to organize foods in different food groups should be applied [69]. A key element of EFSA's proposed approach for drafting FBDGs is the analysis and the identification of food groups that are relevant from a public health perspective [22]. The central role of food groups in the development of FBDGs makes it necessary to establish a standardization at European level to enable comparisons and data sharing between countries.

This type of standardization is a significant challenge, given the diverse dietary patterns and public health priorities across Europe. The current lack of a unified approach to categorizing food groups complicates efforts to create consistent and evidence-based dietary recommendations to improve health and sustainable eating behaviours.

In fact, analysis of the different guidelines' food groups showed several common traits but also relevant differences across countries. While these discrepancies reflect different nutritional priorities and cultural habits as highlighted by Montagnese et al. [70], the main purpose of FBDGs is not to offer a theoretical classification or ranking of foods, but rather to provide practical recommendations that align with real-life eating patterns. Therefore, building on shared elements while addressing divergences could be a concrete step toward developing a common EU framework that remains relevant and actionable for consumers. Generally, a study [71] analysing 98 FBDGs worldwide pointed out that the most used terms to identify food groups were: fruits (58%), vegetables (53%), oils and fats (27.5%), vegetables and fruits (24.5%), and foods from animals (13%). Moreover, the study conducted by Camara and colleagues, identified consistencies within dietary guidelines in the recommended food groups for fruits, vegetables, starchy foods (cereals, preferably whole grains, bread, pasta, rice, potatoes), legumes, nuts, milk and dairy products (yogurt, cheese), meat and meat products, fish, eggs, water, and oil (vegetable oils, with an emphasis on virgin olive oil) [72,73].

For what concerns the discrepancies, these mainly regard protein sources and animal-based foods [74]. For instance, some countries classify legumes with vegetables or cereals, focusing on their fibre content, while others group them with proteins due to their relevant plant-based protein content, and to their role as substitute of animal-based foods [75]. As highlighted by Hughes et al. [76], in the European FBDGs, legumes are mostly included in the fruit and vegetables group in Austria, Finland, and Hungary; in the vegetables group in Estonia and Germany; and in the protein-rich foods group in Albania, Belgium, Bulgaria, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Malta, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey, and the UK. Similarly, foods like nuts and oilseeds are grouped separately in some guidelines or included with fats and oils or proteins in others, depending on their perceived health impacts and traditional culinary uses [70].

An additional element of heterogeneity emerges when recommendations broadly concern a large food group that include products with very different nutritional profiles. For example, in Europe, 85% of countries identify dairy products as a separate food group [75]; however, most countries provide a single recommendation for the entire category. In fact, more than half of European FBDGs recommend 2–4 servings of dairy products per day, and over 80% include specific guidance on cheese consumption, generally emphasizing low-fat or fat-free options, fermented dairy products, and a variety of fresh cheeses ([Food-Based Dietary Guidelines recommendations for milk and dairy products | Knowledge for policy](#)). Nevertheless, only a few countries, such as Cyprus, Hungary, Italy, and Poland, provide separate quantitative recommendations for milk or yoghurt consumption.

This approach groups together foods such as milk and yogurt, as well as cheese, including varieties that may be high in salt and fats, or added sugars in some fermented milk products, with different effects on human health [77,78]. This generalized approach fails to highlight the significant differences in nutritional profiles among these foods and can lead to confusion among consumers.

Just as a coding system has been developed by EFSA [79] to improve the comparability of food consumption datasets across EU countries, the development of a standardized system for the classification of food groups and specific recommendations for individual foods within a food group should be prioritized at the European level. Such a standardization would address the current inconsistencies in food group definitions and the lack of detailed guidance for specific foods, enabling more precise and comparable dietary recommendations. This would ultimately facilitate better public health strategies and improve the efficacy of FBDGs across different European countries, aligning them more closely with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) objectives [80].

DEFINITION AND QUANTITIES OF RECOMMENDED FOODS

Concerning the question with regard to the amount of food consumed, different studies highlighted issues related to increased portions and the consequent increased energy intake, both among adult and younger populations [81–84]. This phenomenon has been described as a potential factor for the increase in the prevalence of overweight and obesity.

Regarding the definition, available literature shows the lack of universal meaning of the terms “portion” and “serving” within dietary guidelines as well as in other sectors, such as in the industry or labelling. Examples of given definitions are given below:

- The term ‘portion’ is defined as the amount of food or drink that one would consume in one eating or drinking occasion - whether in a restaurant, from a package or in consumer’s own kitchen - also known as ‘portion size’ [85], and is usually expressed in units of weight [85–88]
- For food labelling purposes, portion size (or just portion) is defined as the amount of a particular food or drink that can be reasonably expected to be consumed by an individual on a single consumption occasion. In this context, the portion size is sometimes referred to as ‘a serving’ by food manufacturers, identified as the amount of food listed on a product's nutrition facts label [88,89] or by health professionals, especially for those foods that need to be divided or portioned by the consumer before consumption [90,91].

The collection of definitions of portions and servings demonstrate that there are various ways to identify and describe the amount of food to be consumed, depending on the context of use of the definition, such as use by food producers rather than healthcare professionals. These different stakeholders have different purposes in identifying recommended food quantities, either for labelling descriptions, and/or for nutritional recommendations [92–94].

These examples show that the term ‘portion’ does not always correspond to the standard reference amount that experts include in nutritional recommendations at a national level, highlighting the need for a strategy that clarifies which terminology should be used according to the context. Particularly, a harmonised terminology should be identified considering the different industry and dietary recommendations separately. As regard of recommended food quantities, since a high level of variability was found among the guidelines analysed in both studies carried out on this aspect [74,95], a harmonised reference should be established so that European countries can refer to the same standard.

On this issue, the findings of Salesse et al. [74] highlighted many differences among countries:

- The lack of a common terminology used to identify a reference consumption occasion;
- The lack of a standardised reference unit to identify the recommended quantities (e.g. grams, household measures, other references, sometimes used in combination);
- The lack of a homogeneous food classification together with the lack of the recommendations for a specific food category, both quantitatively and qualitatively as previously stated.

Similarly, Carruba et al. [95] found considerable variability in standard portion sizes across countries for several food groups, particularly staple foods such as bread, pasta, milk, and vegetables, highlighting heterogeneous national interpretations of the same food categories. Moreover, their study showed differences not only in the recommended number of daily portions, but also in the gram weights used to define a portion and in the level of detail provided to consumers. In line with these findings, recent evidence further confirms marked heterogeneity in the quantification of serving sizes in FBDGs worldwide, including

differences in units of expression (e.g., grams versus household measures), levels of numerical precision, and overall standardization across national guidelines [96].

Actions towards changing the methods applied to identify and characterize the adequate portion sizes to recommend within FBDGs should be considered, giving the important role of dietary guidelines as an instrument to encourage the population to follow a healthy and balanced diet reducing the development of non-communicable disease.

In addition, recommended portion size should be always included in the FBDGs as a part to which rely on for technical reasons. However, the messages that can reach the consumers could be qualitative, emphasizing the proportion of food that constitute a balanced diet.

Food groups and portion sizes

Differences in the classification of food groups and the recommended portion sizes could represent barriers to the harmonisation of public health programmes across Europe.

Food groups

Purpose of classification: Food groups should be defined according to common characteristics (origin, nutrient content, role in the diet) and their relevance from a public health perspective.

Current challenges: (i) Lack of a unified system across Europe complicates comparability and policy integration; (ii) Differences reflect both cultural traditions and nutritional priorities; (iii) Broad categories (e.g. “dairy products”) risk masking nutritional heterogeneity and confusing consumers.

Future perspective: Develop a standardised European system for food group classification, building on EFSA coding experience with EU Menu and provide specific recommendations within each food group to capture nutritional diversity.

Portion sizes

Terminology: there is still no clear definition of 'portion' or 'serving' in relation to a unit of consumption. According to the final objectives of the labelling system and marketing, as well as nutritional recommendations, a harmonised definition should be established for use in and outside the dietary guidelines.

Quantity: since the variety of measures used to quantify recommended food intake (e.g. grams, household measures) differs across European FBDGs, a standardised system should be developed to provide a reference that can then be adapted according to local contexts, energy requirements and cultural backgrounds.

Adherence to FBDGs

The level of adherence to FBDGs remains a significant concern. At a general level, analysis of European studies evaluating adherence to national dietary recommendations reveals that children, adolescents, and young adults are the groups with the lowest levels of compliance [97–101], with women generally having greater adherence to national recommendations compared to men [99,101–103].

A more detailed analysis of specific food groups or dietary patterns across Europe may offer further insights. In Greece, children and adolescents with overweight or obesity demonstrated significantly lower consumption of plant-based foods such as fruits, vegetables, and legumes, as well as dairy products and fish, compared to national dietary recommendations. On the other hand, meat consumption (both red and white meat) exceeded recommended levels by 131% [104]. In Ireland, poor compliance with FBDG among school-aged children was largely attributed to low consumption of whole grains, fruits, and vegetables, combined with high intakes of sugar-sweetened beverages and processed meats [98].

Young adults in Germany and Spain showed dietary patterns that do not adhere to national FBDGs [101,103]. In Germany, the majority of individuals (18–30 years) failed to meet recommendations for most of the food groups. Only the 4.2% of men and the 15.4% of women consumed the recommended daily portions of vegetables and 20.8% of men and 43.6% of women are compliant with fruit consumption recommendations. In contrast, the consumption of meat, eggs, oils and fats, and water generally adhere to the recommended

guidelines [101]. A similar situation was observed in Spain, where university students exhibited similarly low compliance with guidelines for foods as bread and other grain products, fruits, vegetables, and meat, while significantly exceeded the recommendations for cold cuts and sweets. Concerning the gender differences, in Spain as well as in Germany, women adhered more consistently to recommendations for fruits and vegetables [101,103]. A study conducted in Luxembourg has shown that older adults tend to adhere more closely to FBDGs compared to younger populations, in particular regarding the recommendations for salt intake and fruits, vegetables, and animal-based protein group consumption. Related to general population, women had a better compliance with national guidelines than men, due to their significant higher consumption of fruits, vegetables, and dairy products and lower intake of salt [99].

INDICATORS AND TOOLS FOR ASSESSING ADHERENCE TO FBDGS

The problem related to assess the adherence to FBDGs is often linked to a gap in the monitoring strategies implemented by countries following the publication of updated dietary guidelines. Monitoring if people follow the guidelines highlights dietary habits that may harm health and shows which recommendations are less followed. This information is essential for tailoring preventive measures effectively [102]. However, to efficiently assess adherence to FBDGs, it is necessary to have and to apply reliable indicators that provide information on whether the population is following the national food recommendations or not. By examining these indicators, it is possible to identify gaps in adherence, assess the quality of diets and food literacy rates, and understand the impact of dietary habits on health outcomes, such as NCDs, to inform policy makers to develop interventions and public health prevention strategies.

Food consumption data

Based on EFSA's EU MENU methodology [105], a constant and structured monitoring of the eating habits of the European population is possible through national and representative surveys. These surveys are designed to collect accurate and comparable data on food consumption across populations and specific population groups (e.g. children to elderly people), regions, and demographic characteristics [106]. By standardizing data collection methods, the EU MENU methodology ensures consistency and reliability of such data, facilitating the comparison of dietary patterns both within country and cross-countries. The analysis of food consumption data plays a crucial role in assessing how closely the population adheres to or deviates from national FBDGs. However, a significant challenge lies in the timing and coordination between the release of updated FBDGs and the subsequent monitoring of national food consumption. Dietary guidelines should be periodically revised to incorporate the latest scientific evidence, reflecting changes in nutritional requirements and public health priorities. If monitoring efforts are not carefully synchronized with these updates, the ability to measure the impact and effectiveness of the recommendations becomes compromised.

FBDGs adherence indices

FBDGs adherence indicators are tools used to assess the alignment of the population with recommendations, providing valuable data to guide national interventions.

An example of good indicator in Europe is the Norwegian Dietary Guideline Index (NDGI) designed to reflect adherence to the Norwegian FBDG [102], that is widely used nationally to monitor population adherence and inform public health policy. The evaluation of this index in 8,558 participants showed that the sample achieved an average score of 65 out of 100, with a greater adherence observed in women, elderly participants, those with higher education, and a better self-perceived household economy [102].

Italy developed the Adherence to Italian Dietary Guidelines Index (AIDGI) based on a food consumption frequency scale. AIDGI provided a synthetic evaluation of the adherence to a healthy diet as defined in the dietary guidelines and was applied at national scale permitting to differentiate adherence levels in different population group [107]. A study by Grant and Rossi [108] involving 2,869 participants representative of the Italian population found an equal distribution across the four levels of adherence: 28.9% low, 21.5% low-medium, 25.5% medium-high, and 24.1% high. Among those with the lowest AIDGI scores, there was a higher prevalence of men, younger individuals, and families with five or more members.

In France, an updated version of the original Programme National Nutrition Santé Guidelines Score (PNNS-GS) was developed to align with the revised 2017 French nutritional guidelines. This new version, the PNNS-

GS2, aims to measure adherence to the latest French dietary recommendations. A study involving 80,965 French adults found that higher PNNS-GS2 scores were positively associated with older age and higher educational attainment [109,110]. In the Netherlands, the Dutch Healthy Diet index (DHD15-index) consists of fifteen components representing the fifteen food-based Dutch dietary guidelines of 2015. Each component is scored on a scale from 0 to 10, resulting in a total score ranging from 0 (no adherence) to 150 (complete adherence). In the study by Looman et al. (2017), the validity of the index was tested on a sample of 885 adults aged between 20 and 70 years, and it was concluded that the index effectively assesses adherence to the 2015 Dutch dietary guidelines and serves as an indicator of overall diet quality [111].

Another example, outside Europe, is the Healthy Eating Index (HEI), that assesses how well a set of foods aligns with dietary recommendations and patterns outlined in the USA's FBDG [112]. The latest version of this index is the HEI-2020, which reflects alignment with the 2020-2025 DGA. The phase of evaluation used food consumption data representative of the American population and showed an average HEI-2020 score of 58 out of 100 for the population aged 2 and older. Among these, young children up to age 4 and adults aged over 60 had higher average total scores compared to other population groups [113]. The Dietary Guidelines Index (DGI), used in Australia, is another indicator designed to reflect adherence to national dietary recommendations. The DGI evaluates Australian dietary patterns based on their FBDG, providing a comprehensive measure of overall diet quality [114]. Based on a study by Ward et al. (2019), the DGI was applied to Weighed Food Records (WFR) collected from a sample of 141 adults. The median DGI score was low, at 50.87 (range 20.6–104.1), with higher diet quality observed in women compared to men [115]. By adapting these indicators to reflect the unique needs and recommendations of different countries, public health authorities can better monitor trends and implement effective dietary interventions.

Food literacy

Evaluating food literacy levels is increasingly recognized as a valuable indicator to enhance adherence to FBDGs. Food literacy plays a crucial role in assessing the effectiveness of public health nutrition policy interventions, while simultaneously serving as a key determinant for health improvement, environmental sustainability, and social equity [116]. Food literacy encompasses a set of interrelated knowledge, skills, and behaviours essential for planning, managing, selecting, preparing, and consuming food to meet nutritional needs [117]. [118]. Besides this, Cullen et al. (2015) [118] conceptualize food literacy as the intersection of community food security and individual food skills, providing a holistic understanding of food systems within specific societal and cultural contexts. This interconnected perspective enables individuals to make informed food choices that directly impact health. Monitoring the population's level of food literacy could provide insight into how well FBDGs are followed at the national level, or if they are indirectly difficult to understand due to the general population's level of nutritional knowledge. Various assessment tools have been developed to measure food literacy. A scoping review by Amouzandeh C et al. (2019) [119] identified 12 assessment tools that explicitly measure food literacy or a part of it among the adult population. However, the conclusions of the study highlighted that, to date no tools have been explicitly developed from Vidgen and Gallegos' conceptualization [117] of food literacy or crafted to capture all 11 components of food literacy.

Adherence to FBDGs

Adherence to FBDGs remains generally low, with children, adolescents, and young adults showing the weakest compliance, while women tend to follow recommendations more than men.

Across countries, common gaps include low consumption of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, coupled with excess intake of meat, sweets, and processed meat. Older adults show higher adherence, particularly for fruit and vegetable intake.

Monitoring

Monitoring the adherence is often limited by a lack of systematic follow-up after FBDG updates, making it difficult to evaluate their real impact.

Indicators and tools:

- **Food consumption data:** collected through national surveys using EFSA's EU MENU methodology. Enables monitoring trends and evaluating the impact of FBDGs. Challenges include timing of guideline updates vs. survey data collection.
- **Adherence indices:** evaluate alignment of population diets with national FBDGs to identify gaps, assess diet quality, and guide public health interventions. Differences in methodology across countries limit comparability.
- **Food literacy:** assesses knowledge, skills, and behaviours for planning, selecting, preparing, and consuming food. Current tools measure only parts of the 11 components of food literacy.

Communication, disseminations and barriers

Effective communication of FBDGs should be fundamental for promoting healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns, as well as improving food literacy rates and general public health. However, several challenges persist in the way these guidelines are disseminated effectively, leading to barriers in their adoption and implementation across different populations. Most of these negative factors are related to the adaptation of scientific messages for not-expert audience and for different target groups (from young population to elderly people), accessibility and general complexity of the guidelines.

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION GAPS

Successfully communicating FBDGs to diverse audiences is a challenging task, as it requires balancing simplicity and clarity with maintaining scientific accuracy. The WHO's strategic communications framework for effective communication emphasizing that this aspect should be accessible, actionable, credible, trustworthy, relevant, timely, and easily understood [120]. Issues identified in the UK recent research include the need to review the language and tone of messages, tailor communications to specific population groups, address the barriers and benefits of adopting recommendations, develop practical tools and resources for their implementation, and leverage social media and marketing strategies to increase public engagement [60]. Additionally, a report from the Federation of European Nutrition Societies [121] has identified several limitations related to the communication of European FBDGs including their frequent lack of translation into clear and actionable messages for consumers, insufficient dissemination strategies, limited tailoring of communication to different target groups, and the overall complexity of the information provided. According to a cross-sectional study by Yoong et al. [122], many FBDG dissemination strategies lack formal plans, and few provide detailed information, especially regarding the public as the primary end-user. Additionally, Brown et al. [123] criticized the limited research on the public's use of FBDGs and pointed out that despite years of existence, FBDGs have not been as successful in changing consumer behaviour or reducing NCDs. According to the study of Wijesinha-Bettoni et al. [124], this is related to the fact that FBDGs are not fully utilized and should involve sectors beyond nutrition and health fields to be more effective. For these reasons, training all professionals (not only dietitians and nutritionists) involved in the dissemination of FBDGs with

the public should be essential. Without adequately prepared professionals, the impact of the guidelines is likely to remain limited.

However, to create an effective communication strategy an appropriate budget allocation should be required to ensure efficiency. Without sufficient investment, dissemination efforts often encountered difficulties in its objectives and impact. Moreover, although FBDGs are generally designed for the healthy adult population, communication and dissemination strategies should be reinforced to effectively reach populations at higher risk (low-income groups, ethnic minorities, older adults, etc.). The duration of the campaign is also critical, as sustained communication is key to promoting and embedding new FBDGs within public behaviour.

BARRIERS TO FBDGs IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation refers to the comprehensive process of integrating FBDGs into national policies, programmes, and multisectoral actions in order to influence dietary behaviours and the broader food system (<https://www.fao.org/nutrition/education/dietary-guidelines/background/implementation/en/>). However, several barriers hinder their effective implementation, most of which are related to the lack of official plans. Based on the study of Wijesinha-Bettoni R. et al. [124], among 27 countries worldwide, most have an official body responsible for FBDG implementation. However, in Europe only a few countries, such as Denmark, Finland, Germany, Malta, and Norway, have a defined strategy or an operational plan. Even fewer countries have a dedicated budget, a gap also highlighted in the study by Keller and Lang [125]. In fact, the lack of resources - both financial and human - limit the ability of governments and organisations to develop and implement the FBDG recommendations.

Moreover, there is often a lack of collaboration across sectors, which can result in fragmented efforts and insufficient awareness of the importance of FBDGs, and the model followed to develop the guideline can become a barrier if there is not an appropriate involvement of different stakeholders. Besides this, conflict of interest, social attitudes (i.e., traditional food preferences) and the lack of availability, affordability issues and access to healthy foods were also mentioned [124].

Conflicting interests significantly hinder the effective implementation of FBDGs. Food and agricultural policies that prioritize market economies, combined with industry interests and the influence of mass media and marketing, may undermine the development and implementation of FBDGs [125–127].

Another key issue is the weakness of food policies at the European level, which often do not align with healthy dietary recommendations [128]. The study of Djojoseparto et al [128], identified that most food environment policy indicators are not adequate at EU level through the use of the Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI). This situation occurs because most EU countries prefer to address public health issues at the national level and do not adhere to European policies, which are often voluntary. For example, only few EU countries are using fiscal measures to make High in Fat, Sugar and Salt (HFSS) foods less accessible and affordable [129].

Moreover, there is a lack of practical "ready-to-use" recommendations or implementation tips [60] which further hinders adherence. The guidelines often fail to provide clear, actionable steps tailored to different socioeconomic and cultural contexts, leaving individuals unsure of how to apply them in daily life. A study by Leme et al. (2021) showed that adherence to FBDGs is generally low both in high-income countries (HICs) and low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs), with nearly 40% of the population not adhering to their national guidelines. However, HICs tend to have a higher consumption of discretionary foods, while the results for LMICs are mixed (low consumption of healthy foods and high consumption of unhealthy foods) [130]. This situation occurs because vulnerable groups (such as people with low socio-economic status) may lack the resources, food literacy or support to integrate healthy practices into their routines. Additionally, the lack of availability and accessibility to affordable healthy and sustainable foods, make it difficult for many individuals to adhere to FBDGs, especially in low-income groups and areas or regions with fewer public health intervention [131–133]. For individuals struggling with immediate economic or health challenges, long-term benefits such as disease prevention may seem abstract, reducing their motivation to engage with dietary recommendations.

To overcome these barriers, various strategies have been recommended [134]: integrating FBDGs into school curricula and nutrition education, improving food literacy rates, improving the availability of nutritious foods in low-income communities, implementing economic measures to improve affordability, and enacting policy

actions such as marketing restrictions and easy-to-understand front-of-pack nutrition labels, utilizing mass media campaigns, and involving various sectors (e.g., health, education, agriculture) in the process. Community-based approaches, i.e., including the use of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and local organizations for food education and cooking demonstrations, can also help to bridge the gap between knowledge and practical application by raising food literacy level among communities [135]. By overcoming these barriers, FBDGs can be better integrated into public health policies and everyday practices, ultimately contributing to healthier and more sustainable diets and improved well-being for different population groups across countries.

FOCUS: FOOD EDUCATION IN SCHOOL CURRICULA

Several shortcomings in school-based food education programs across countries could be identified. One major issue is the variability in curriculum space dedicated to food education, while most countries have some form of mandatory food curriculum, there is no consensus on its scope or implementation. The study of Smith, Wells & Hawkes (2022) [136] analysed food curricula in 11 countries worldwide (Australia, Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Iceland, Ireland, Japan, Norway, Scotland, Slovenia, and Sweden) and highlighted that many of these overly focus on nutrition knowledge, neglecting information regarding the sociocultural, equity, and sustainability aspects.

Another significant shortcoming is the mismatch between the food environment in schools and the national FBDGs. The widespread availability of highly sugary, processed foods in school cafeterias and vending machines directly undermines efforts to encourage balanced and nutritious diets. These foods, typically low in essential nutrients and high in unhealthy fats, sugars, and salts, contribute to poor dietary choices and increased risks of obesity and related health issues in latter age [137]. Studies have shown that the higher is the grade levels of schools, the less healthy is the school food environment [138]. However, research by Vereecken C.A. et al. (2004) found that school food environment can play a key role in shaping adolescents' eating habits, particularly in secondary schools [137]. Besides this, even the food environment surrounding schools is often characterized by the abundant presence of food establishment, particularly fast-foods, convenience stores, supermarkets, and grocery stores, which commonly provide a diverse range of unhealthy and ready-to-eat food options [139].

Another critical shortcoming is the lack of time, resources, and proper teacher training to effectively deliver food education. Teachers often appear to lack the necessary knowledge and pedagogical tools to incorporate food education into their lessons [140]. The study of Nanayakkara et al. (2022), suggest improving secondary school teachers' confidence in teaching food and nutrition by offering more professional development, ensuring adequate knowledge, providing more resources and time, keeping them updated on food trends, and elevating the status of food and nutrition subjects in schools [141]. In particular, there is a limited emphasis on early childhood education recognised a critical period for building lifelong healthy habits. Programs targeting younger children, especially those in the 0 to 6 age group, could be the key in shaping both individual and family-level behaviours [142,143]. Early education settings should integrate practical food and nutrition components that involve not only children but also their families and educators through a variety of approaches, such as creating supportive food environments, embedding nutritional lessons into daily activities, and ensuring that educators are equipped with adequate training [144].

Furthermore, there is a recognized gap in the involvement of parents in the educational process, with most strategies relying on indirect methods like newsletters rather than active, direct engagement with students and their families [145]. Research shows that parental involvement can significantly enhance the impact of school-based interventions, especially when parents actively participate in homework or other school activities related to food education [146].

As stated by FAO *“countries are increasingly integrating food and nutrition education as a core element of their national curricula and of their school food and health policies”* [147]. However, to reach the full potential of food and nutrition education in schools, a more comprehensive, practical, and inclusive approach is needed starting from the early stages of schooling., This should be accompanied by increased collaboration between schools and families to improve food literacy levels in children and their families. Furthermore, it is essential to integrate nutritional education into higher and vocational school pathways, while also

acknowledging the critical contribution of healthcare and nutrition professionals in delivering effective nutritional counselling.

Communication, dissemination and barriers

Effective communication of FBDGs is fundamental for promoting healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns, enhancing food literacy, and supporting public health.

Communication challenges:

- Messages are often too complex or technical for the general public.
- Many FBDGs lack formal dissemination plans or practical tools for implementation.
- Professionals involved in FBDG communication (not just nutritionists) often need training.
- Limited budget and campaign duration reduce effectiveness.
- Vulnerable populations (low-income, minorities, older adults) are often underserved.

Implementation is further hindered by policy gaps, limited intersectoral collaboration, cultural food preferences, and conflicting industry interests. In addition, the availability, affordability, and accessibility of healthy foods remain major barriers, while FBDGs often do not provide clear, context-specific instructions for daily life.

To address these challenges, multi-level strategies are needed, including integrating FBDGs into school curricula, improving food literacy and professional training, implementing supportive policies (e.g., marketing restrictions, front-of-pack labels), and engaging communities through practical education programs.

Schools play a critical role, particularly when curricula include practical, sustainable, and culturally relevant food education, and actively involve families. Early childhood education is key for shaping lifelong healthy habits.

Building the framework

This section outlines the steps taken to develop an innovative framework that addresses key shortcomings of current FBDGs. The framework combines a food systems approach with the True Cost Accounting (TCA) methodology developed in the PLAN'EAT project. While this is one possible approach, it should be seen as part of a broader set of strategies to improve FBDGs.

The proposed framework includes:

- A food-system-based approach, including use of a TCA methodology that is aligned with PLAN'EAT project aims and scope;
- A standardized procedure for defining food groups, terminology, and recommended quantities of food;
- A communication strategy.

TCA for FBDGs

Within the PLAN'EAT project, TCA is proposed as a key tool for developing more holistic FBDGs. TCA captures the environmental, health, and social impacts of diets and translates them into monetary values, making hidden costs visible. This provides a more complete evidence base for dietary recommendations.

In the development of FBDGs, TCA can be used to:

1. identify key factors contributing to the negative impacts and hidden costs of diets;
2. highlight the most effective levers for making diets healthier and more sustainable;
3. develop effective strategies that guide the transition to healthier populations and more sustainable food systems.

To test feasibility, TCA could be applied to a case comparing two different food groups or products such as red meat and legumes. Such a case study would help assess methodological strengths, limitations, and trade-offs—particularly in situations where data are incomplete—and provide insights into resource needs and practical implementation.

INTEGRATING TCA INTO THE DEVELOPMENT OF FBDGS

Food-Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDGs) are key policy tools that provide recommendations for healthy eating patterns based on nutritional needs. However, they often fail to adequately address the environmental and social impacts of food systems, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and social inequalities. TCA is an integrated, systems-based approach that monetizes the health, environmental, social, and economic impacts of food production and consumption.

Hidden costs of food systems

The Food and Agriculture Organization's (FAO's) 2023 and 2024 *State of Food and Agriculture (SOFA)* reports [148,149] estimate the hidden health, environmental, and social costs of global agrifood systems to be at least USD 10 trillion annually. In high- and upper-middle-income countries (including Europe), over 70% of these costs arise from the health impacts of diets low in whole grains and fruits but high in animal-based products, processed foods, and additives, which lead to non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and associated productivity losses. Meanwhile, environmental impacts account for around 20% of costs, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, nitrogen pollution, land-use changes, and water depletion. The SOFA reports emphasize the need for FBDGs that address these hidden costs by promoting healthy and sustainable diets. In this context, other reports—such as the *TEEBAgriFood Scientific and Economic Foundations Report* [150], the 2023 and 2024 *State of Food and Agriculture* reports [148,149] and the WWF's and TMG's *True Cost Accounting and Dietary Patterns* study [151]—highlight the need for FBDGs to adopt a systems-based approach that considers the interconnected relationships within food systems, accounting for environmental, social, and health impacts and economic effects along the entire value chain. Recognizing this need, FAO is developing a new methodology for food-systems-based dietary guidelines, which integrates health and nutritional priorities with socio-cultural, economic, and environmental sustainability to promote healthy diets.

The development of such FBDGs needs to involve different experts (dietitians, nutritionists, environmental scientists, economists, behavioural scientists, and communication experts) to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of food systems. FBDGs should:

- Consider the true costs of food (see chapter “Detailed Methodological Approach”), evaluating overall health, environmental, and social impacts (see chapter “Social Capital”);
- Promote healthy diets that reduce the risk of obesity and other NCDs;
- Incorporate recommendations that minimize negative environmental, social, health, and economic impacts;
- Embrace a holistic approach that addresses hidden costs throughout the entire agrifood system.

BENEFITS OF A TCA APPROACH FOR DEVELOPING FBDGS

The report *True Cost Accounting and Dietary Patterns* [151] introduces TCA as an innovative tool to assess diets and develop dietary policies that account for human health impacts, environmental sustainability, and social justice. The study shows the significant impact of dietary choices on natural resource management, producers' equity treatment, and population health. Despite the fact that at least 100 countries have FBDGs, only a few incorporate environmental sustainability or social welfare considerations. The related working paper [152] underlines the potential role of TCA-based dietary guidelines as a key policy tool for influencing positive changes not only in consumer behaviour but also in public procurement and social protection, driving the shift toward food systems that respect planetary boundaries and minimum social rights, as described by Raworth [153].

Moreover, the hidden costs or “externalities” of food systems—such as environmental and health damages caused by pollution, resource depletion, or malnutrition—are often overlooked. By identifying, quantifying, monetizing, and communicating these impacts, TCA simplifies the integration of sustainability aspects into decision-making processes for consumers, businesses, and policymakers.

The TEEBAgriFood report [150] (widely embraced as the leading reference point for TCA-based food systems analysis) underscores the importance of adopting a systems-based approach when assessing food and agriculture systems. The report suggests that FBDGs should evaluate a range of impacts and interactions beyond nutritional concerns. To capture the full range of impacts, The TEEBAgriFood report incorporates four types of capital¹: natural capital, human capital, social capital, and produced capital (see Figure 1 and Table 1). These capitals must be clearly represented at all stages of the supply chain. Formulating FBDGs using this approach not only considers food systems’ impact on human health but also on environmental degradation and social inequities, as well as their economic burden on society.

Figure 1: Capital stocks and value flows in eco-agri-food systems (Source: TEEB, 2018 [150]).

Table 1. Definition of the four types of capital, taken from the TEEBAgriFood framework [150].

Capital	Definition
Human capital	Individuals’ knowledge, skills, competencies, and attributes that facilitate the creation of personal, social, and economic well-being.
Social capital	Encompasses networks, including institutions, together with shared norms, values, and understandings that facilitate cooperation within or among groups.
Produced capital	All manufactured capital, such as buildings, factories, machinery, and physical infrastructure (roads, water systems), as well as all financial and intellectual capital (technology, software, patents, brands, etc.).

¹ *Capital*: The economic framing of the various stocks that embody future streams of benefits that contribute to human well-being.

Natural capital The limited stocks of earth's physical and biological resources and the limited capacity of ecosystems to provide ecosystem services.

TCA METHODOLOGY

This section presents a structured methodology for the development of FBDGs via the TCA approach for dietary recommendations.

TCA holistically evaluates impacts across four capitals; natural, human, social, and produced. In the proposed TCA methodology for the development of FBDGs, the assessment focuses on natural, human, and social capital only. Produced capital is not included as the most significant impacts of food and diets are encompassed by the other three capitals. Excluding produced capital also helps keep the analysis and modelling needs manageable and ensures resources are directed toward the areas with the greatest relevance to food systems.

Though there are other approaches to implementing TCA [154], we suggest that a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology [155] is most appropriate since it allows for quantification and monetization of several impacts. LCA is widely recognized by international bodies, including the EU, as effective for assessing the environmental impacts of the entire life cycle of products, processes, or systems—including raw materials, production, transportation, use, and disposal—thereby enabling the identification of areas where adverse environmental impacts can be reduced.

While LCA is an effective tool for quantifying impacts, it also has limitations, as with any modelling approach. LCA depends on comprehensive data for inputs, outputs, and emissions and any inaccuracies in this data can undermine the reliability of the results. Moreover, global datasets may not accurately reflect regional variations. Additionally, LCA models are not able to assess indicators like biodiversity loss and animal welfare. Quantifying social impacts presents additional challenges as factors like labour conditions and community well-being are less standardized and harder to model than environmental impacts. Current Social LCA (s-LCA) models and databases are primarily used for social risk assessment rather than quantifying actual impacts. Additionally, data availability for social impact assessment is often limited. However, databases such as the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) can be used to identify social risk hotspots within the supply chain (see chapter “Social Life Cycle Assessment”).

Implementing TCA can present several challenges for authorities. TCA is a relatively new and complex methodology that requires collaboration across multiple disciplines and the involvement of skilled experts including environmental scientists, health authorities, nutritionists, social experts, and economists, which demands high-level coordination. Additionally, TCA is a data-intensive approach relying on diverse sources, where data availability and quality can be limited, requiring expert interpretation. Authorities may also face institutional barriers, such as a lack of technical capacity and limited awareness of TCA among policymakers. Overall, successful application of TCA demands both technical expertise and strong interdisciplinary cooperation and allocated resources. Before starting the TCA process, it is useful to build a coalition of relevant expertise and policy domains to ensure technical accuracy and effective implementation. Additionally, allocating a sufficient dedicated budget for TCA implementation is crucial to support a successful TCA process.

TCA steps

The TCA approach presented here is based on the *Applying the TEEBAgriFood evaluation framework* report [156].

- **Environmental costs** are estimated using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) method combined with damage costs monetization factors.
- **Dietary-related health costs** are calculated using the cost-of-illness approach outlined by Seidel et al. [157] or the comparative risk assessment of diet-related health risks method by Springmann et al. (2021) [158] to estimate consumption-related health impacts.
- **Social risks** are evaluated based on social LCA (s-LCA).

The TCA approach thereby collates key indicators for natural, human, and social capital impacts and outlines the data needed to perform TCA assessment of FBDGs. The TEEBAgriFood TCA methodology comprises four key steps, which are explained in relation to FBDGs below.

Step 1: Framing the analysis to clarify its purpose.

The first step in a TCA is to define its purpose. In the context of FBDGs, the objective is to make dietary recommendations not only healthier but also more sustainable. TCA provides a framework for developing FBDGs that integrate nutrition and health objectives with environmental considerations, while also recognizing economic and social dimensions. This requires assessing the full range of costs and benefits of current and proposed dietary patterns, before using these insights to guide the development of FBDGs that balance affordability, cultural acceptability, and long-term sustainability. This step can also be used to ensure the analysis takes into account broader national priorities, including commitments on climate action, biodiversity conservation, and public health.

Step 2: Defining the scope, boundaries, and assumptions of the analysis.

This step includes defining: 1) the subject of analysis; 2) the functional unit of the assessment; 3) the geographical boundary; and 4) the agri-food value chain scope.

1. *Subject of analysis:* To develop FBDGs using a TCA approach, a comprehensive diet-level assessment (i.e. considering both individual food items and the combined effects of food items within dietary patterns) is necessary. This requires food consumption data. Given the limited data on the relationships between food items and their production and consumption processes, dietary impact can be approximated by summing impacts of individual food products (for an example of food products in a diet see Appendix A; for an example of impacts of diets see Appendix B).
2. *Functional unit:* In the LCA method (quantifying environmental impacts such as GHG emissions, acidification, or eutrophication), functional units allow for comparison of LCA results across different products or systems that serve the same function [159]. So far, no appropriate functional unit for food and diets is available, as it is challenging to capture the nutritional function of food in a comparative way. For this reason, functional units are commonly based on mass or energy (e.g. kg, serving size, kcal) for food products.
3. *Geographical boundary:* Since many products consumed in European countries are imported, it is essential to consider impacts across the entire value chain, including at production stages that may take place in other countries. The geographical boundary for TCA assessment and data search should therefore include not only the country for which the FBDGs are developed but also the countries where the consumed food is produced, in order to take into account the environmental and social impacts of primary production. LCA methodology considers the country of production, as environmental impacts can vary by location. However, information on country of production may not always be available. To address this, a trade mapping exercise is recommended to identify where food products are likely produced. National import statistics can also be used to estimate the most probable country of origin. For EU countries, using EU averages is also an option, though this only allows for a high-level assessment and does not consider country-specific differences in production impacts.
4. *Agri-food value chain scope:* Since TCA takes a systems-based approach, the TCA methodology analyses the entire food system—from production to consumption—capturing environmental, social, and health impacts (Figure 2). The scope of TCA should account for all three of these impacts, depending on data availability and the specific aims of the study.

Environmental assessment of diets is predominantly focused on impacts of food production such as land-use change, GHG emissions, and biodiversity loss. Nutritional assessment is focused on impacts of consumption, while health assessment includes both impacts of production and consumption. Production-related health impacts of food are estimated using the LCA method, where human toxicity impacts from exposure to harmful substances during production are calculated. Consumption-related health impacts are assessed based on the health risks associated with specific diets, such as diets low in fruits and vegetables or high in processed meat. These consumption patterns are linked to risks of chronic diseases (e.g. cardiovascular diseases). Social impacts related to production activities with unsafe working conditions, unjust wages, and child labour have detrimental effects on human and social capitals. Globally, 152 million children (aged

between 5–17) are in child labour, a staggering 70% of whom work in agriculture [160]. Furthermore, child labour in agriculture is not limited to developing nations; it also poses a significant issue in industrialized countries [154]. Additionally, agriculture is among the most dangerous sectors to work in, with high rates of injuries and illnesses. Workers face risks from machinery, heavy lifting, animals, extreme weather, and long working hours that pose serious occupational hazards [161].

The analysis is based on input and output data from food production, processing, distribution, retail, and consumption stages and impact data on natural, social, and human capitals. However, as mentioned above, TCA assessment highlights that significant negative environmental and social impacts within the food system often occur at the production stage.

Figure 2. Life Cycle Assessment boundaries. Source: TEEB (2018), p. 274 [150].

Step 3: Measure and value

This step involves: 1) selecting the methods for impact assessment and valuation; 2) collecting and validating the data and addressing data gaps and uncertainties; 3) estimating the impacts; and 4) assigning a monetary value to the impacts to facilitate valuation.

For the impact assessment of diets, we recommend combining three approaches (there are also other approaches that can be implemented with primary data to assess impacts and hidden costs under human and social capital, which are briefly explained in the related sections):

1. LCA to estimate environmental impacts and production-related health impacts (e.g., by using the ReCiPe 2016 or the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) LCA method);
2. Cost of Illness (COI) approach by Seidel et al. [157] or the comparative risk assessment of diet-related health risks method by Springmann et al. (2021) [158] to estimate consumption-related health impacts;
3. Social risk assessment using a Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) approach to evaluate social risks and define hotspots that require intervention across the food supply chain (see chapter "Social Life Cycle Assessment").

For valuation, we recommend using the monetization factors developed by True Price (rights-based approach) or CE Delft (damage costs approach) [162] (for further details, see "PHASE 5: Estimate the hidden costs").

It should be noted that, while the diet optimization modelling systems used to develop FBDGs apply specific health-based restrictions to determine dietary recommendations, the TCA approach serves a different purpose. TCA does not replicate the diet optimization modelling system used to develop FBDGs, instead it provides a method to integrate environmental, social, and health dimensions into a sustainability assessment of dietary recommendations.

Step 4: Take action

The final step of the TCA process is to communicate and translate the findings into concrete action. For FBDGs, this means ensuring that the results of the assessment are reflected in the design and revision of the guidelines so that they address not only health and nutrition, but also environmental, social, and economic impacts. Beyond shaping the guidelines themselves, further actions are needed to ensure that FBDGs are implemented by food companies, food providers, and other actors, creating food environments that support healthy and sustainable dietary patterns. The outcomes of the TCA analysis can also inform awareness-raising campaigns, educational initiatives, and communication strategies that help consumers and stakeholders understand the true costs and benefits of dietary choices.

DETAILED METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

In this section, the steps for assessing the impacts and hidden costs of diets as part of “Step 3: Measure and value” of TCA are listed and explained in detail as follows:

- Phase 1. Collect data on actual and recommended food consumption
- Phase 2. Define the diets to be modelled
- Phase 3. Collect data on food production
- Phase 4. Calculate environmental and social impacts of food products and health impacts of diets
- Phase 5. Estimate the hidden costs
- Phase 6. Taking the results into account for the design of FBDGs

PHASE 1 – Collect data on actual and recommended food consumption

The first phase involves gathering data on both current dietary patterns and recommended food intake for the population group. This requires two main steps:

1. Collecting detailed information on the types and amounts of foods and beverages currently consumed by the population group. This includes identifying typical dietary patterns and quantifying the intake of different food groups.
2. Quantifying recommended food and non-alcoholic drinks consumption according to existing FBDGs, and the population’s nutrient requirements. Each country should identify the nutritional recommendations included in their FBDGs.

To benchmark current dietary patterns and FBDGs and compare their environmental, health, and social impacts, a reference diet must be selected. A reference diet is a benchmark dietary pattern used to compare environmental, health, and social impacts of current diets and FBDGs. It is assumed to be nutritionally adequate, environmentally sustainable, and healthy. The Planetary Health Diet (PHD), designed for sustainability by balancing health and environmental trade-offs, can be used as the reference diet for the TCA assessment. We recommend to not include alcoholic beverages in the model since the PHD and World Health Organization suggest minimal or no alcohol intake.

PHASE 2 – Define the diets to be modelled

In this phase, the goal is to identify representative food products that can be used to model the environmental, health, and social impacts of current and recommended diets, while keeping modelling efforts manageable. A representative product is a specific food item chosen to represent a broader food category or subcategory in dietary modelling. Using representative foods is recommended because it allows for efficient modelling while maintaining meaningful differentiation between food groups. Modelling every individual food item consumed by a population would be very resource-intensive but have minimal added value for understanding broader dietary impacts. Representative products therefore enable assessing impacts at the food-category level. We recommend modelling all three diets (current diets, FBDGs, and the

PHD) to compare how proposed FBDGs perform relative to actual consumption and sustainable dietary targets.

The first step in this phase is defining the food categories in the diets. National-level food consumption data should be used to define food categories within the current diets and FBDGs. A standardized approach to defining food categories needs to be established in order to effectively and efficiently compare food consumption across current diets, FBDGs, and the PHD. When testing the TCA approach in the scope of the PLAN'EAT project (Appendices A and B), a standardized categorization system with 24 food categories was developed, translating broader European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) categories into manageable groups for comparison. The food group information provided in the national dietary guidelines and in the PHD were, whenever possible, translated to EFSA's level L1 food category definitions. While level L1 data improves efficiency, it should be noted that it does not consider the degree of processing and therefore cannot account for the varying impacts of UPFs, despite the substantial role they play in shaping the environmental, social, and health outcomes of food products. As a result, it may underestimate the hidden costs of highly processed or discretionary food items. Higher-level EFSA categories (e.g. "legumes, nuts, oilseeds, and spices") were divided into more specific groups (e.g. legumes, nuts, and oilseeds), while certain products, such as spices, were excluded from dietary recommendations and categorized under "other." A three-digit numbering system was introduced to ensure consistency across food types and subcategories, with representative products assigned to each food category. Table 1A in Appendix A provides an example of selected food groups for diets. With reference to this framework, the food groups proposed in Table 1A can be considered as macro groups. Within these macro groups, smaller groups can be created according to each country's choice of grouping. For example, "fruit and vegetables" is one of the proposed food groups to be considered as a starting point; within this group, sub-categories (e.g. pomaceous fruit) could be created; and, in each of the sub-categories, representative items can be selected. Meanwhile, meat can be categorized into beef, pork, and poultry, as these represent distinct animal production systems with differing impacts.

Representative products are then selected within each food category. For comparison of findings, we recommend using the same representative products for current diets, FBDGs, and the PHD, adjusting only the quantities to align with the consumed and recommended amounts. Research on TCA highlights that the main differences in environmental, health, and social impacts comes from differences in broader categories such as plant-based versus animal-based products [157] (Michalke et al., 2023, Michalke et al., 2022, Pieper et al., 2020). We propose selecting representative products that represent the characteristics of each sub-category within broader categories. For instance, in the "Fruit and fruit products" category, pome fruits could be represented by "apple," exotic fruits by "banana," and berries by "strawberries" (Appendix A). Appendix A, Table 1A outlines how each food category can be grouped. When selecting representative products for each category, it is important to consider which product is most consumed in the country of assessment and whether data for that product is available in impact assessment databases. If data is available, the most consumed product can be selected; if not, the next most representative product should be considered. The consumption amounts for each food group are then calculated by multiplying the representative food by the total amount of the corresponding food group according to current diets or recommended amounts respectively.

Data sources

Data sources for food consumption data and diet modelling presented in Table 2 can be used to model diets and food production trade profiles. Various sources of nationally representative food consumption data are available. In the PLAN'EAT project, the EFSA Food Consumption Database was used, although alternative data sources could also be considered.

Table 2. Food consumption and diet modelling data sources.

Data Source	About the data	What the data is used for
The EFSA Food Consumption Database [106]	The database provides detailed food consumption data for individuals living in Europe. The data is	Mapping dietary patterns

	collected using a variety of methods, including food diaries, food records and 24-hour recalls.	
National dietary recommendations	National food-based dietary recommendations can be used to determine the recommended food intake per person per day.	Mapping dietary patterns
FAO Food Balance Sheets (FAO, 2010–2022)	The FAO Food Balance Sheets present a comprehensive overview of food supply at national level. They include primary and processed commodities potentially available for human consumption, supply sources, and utilization.	Constructing domestic food production and trade profiles

PHASE 3 – Collect data on food production

The purpose of this phase is to collect data on food production and trade in order to identify the countries of origin of the consumed foods. This information is essential for modelling the entire value chain and estimating the respective impacts of consumed foods. Trade data is used to determine the countries where foods are produced, while national statistics provide details on domestic production activities and local conditions [157]. Since many products consumed in a country are not domestically produced, it is important to account for impacts across the entire value chain by identifying countries of production. To simplify this, we propose a 90% cut-off approach, focusing on the top five (or more) countries of origin that account for at least 90% of imports into a given country. Import values from these countries are normalized to 100%, and the adjusted shares are used to represent the composition of the product mix consumed in the country.

PHASE 4 – Calculate environmental and social impacts of food products and health impacts of diets

The purpose of this phase is to estimate the environmental, social, and health impacts associated with food products and dietary patterns. Details on the environmental, health, and social impact assessments are provided below under natural, social, and human capital.

NATURAL CAPITAL

Environmental impact assessment

Environmental impacts of food and diets are assessed using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methods (which guide the calculation of impacts) and supporting data. An environmental impact assessment based on LCA requires:

- a life cycle inventory (LCI) database providing information on food and agricultural production inputs, outputs, and processes;
- appropriate LCA software; and
- a suitable life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) method.

Details on each of these assessment components (method and data) are explained in the following sections.

The environmental domain is the most extensively researched and standardized area in the TCA literature. Widely accepted environmental impact indicators are presented in Table 3. In the PLAN'EAT Deliverable D3.3 "True Costs and Benefits of 3 EU Diets," the environmental assessment of diets revealed that GHG emissions and land-use change are the dominant impact drivers. However, when selecting impact indicators, it is possible to include and monetize a broader set of environmental impacts. By following the LCA approach using the ReCiPe 2016 method, it is possible to account for all the indicators suggested by Huijbregts et al. (2016). Additionally, all these impacts can be monetized using appropriate monetization factors (e.g. from CE Delft's *Environmental Prices Handbook*). When selecting indicators, it is important to pay attention to

whether monetization is feasible. Incorporating a set of indicators provides a more comprehensive environmental assessment.

Table 3. Overview of globally material (meaning relevant) impacts under natural capital.

Impact category**	Impact Indicator	Unit	Source
Contribution to climate change	Greenhouse gas emissions*	kg CO ₂ -eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016)[163]
Pollution of the living environment	Particulate matter formation*	kg PM _{2.5} -eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Photochemical oxidant formation*	kg NO _x -eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Acidification*	kg SO ₂ -eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Ozone layer depleting emissions*	kg CFC11-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Depletion of scarce abiotic resources	Fossil fuel depletion*	kg oil-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Depletion of scarce abiotic resources	(Other) non-renewable material depletion*	kg Cu-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Depletion of scarce abiotic resources	Scarce water use (blue water)*	m ³	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Terrestrial ecotoxicity (air pollution)*	kg 1,4-DB-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Terrestrial ecotoxicity (water pollution)*	kg 1,4-DB-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Freshwater eutrophication*	kg P-eq to freshwater	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Marine eutrophication*	kg N-eq to marine water	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Terrestrial ecotoxicity (soil pollution)*	kg 1,4-DB-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Freshwater ecotoxicity (soil pollution)*	kg 1,4-DB-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Pollution of the living environment	Marine ecotoxicity (soil pollution)*	kg 1,4-DB-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Degradation of biodiversity and ecosystems	Land use/transformation*	m ² × yr annual cropland-eq	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Animal welfare	Animal years suffered	ALYs (Animal life years suffered)	Scherer et al. (2018) [164]

Degradation of biodiversity and ecosystems	Land occupation*	MSA ha yr	True Price (2023)[157]
Degradation of biodiversity and ecosystems	Soil organic carbon (SOC) loss*	kg SOC	True Price (2023) [157]
Degradation of biodiversity and ecosystems	Soil loss from wind erosion*	kg soil lost	True Price (2023) [157]
Degradation of biodiversity and ecosystems	Soil loss from water erosion*	kg soil lost	True Price (2023) [157]

*Impacts that can be assessed with TCA approach.

**Based on TEEB (2018).

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The environmental assessment is based on LCI data, which can be obtained from secondary LCI databases such as ecoinvent [165] or Agribalyse [166]. These databases provide product inventories that can be matched to the diets modelled in Phase 2 (see Table 4 for data sources). A critical step in this process is the selection of appropriate LCI data. Ideally, product-specific inventories that reflect the actual characteristics of the consumed food items (e.g. their precise origin and production system) would be used. However, such detailed data are rarely available. Therefore, modelling requires well-grounded assumptions, such as:

- using representative data from the country of origin
- considering import shares and transport distances
- accounting for production inputs (e.g. fertilizers, pesticides, irrigation)
- reflecting country-specific electricity mixes, the use of greenhouses, or differentiating between animal husbandry systems

In cases where direct information is not available, inventories can be constructed or approximated based on representative averages, for example by weighting data according to the energy contribution of different products within a country of origin.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

LCIA translates the inventory results into their respective environmental impacts. In this step, the inventory results are classified according to their effect and quantified with a characterization factor to calculate their contribution to specific environmental impacts. Several environmental impact assessment methods can be applied at this stage, with ReCiPe 2016 [163] and PEF being a widely accepted and implemented approach [167].

Data sources

A life cycle inventory (LCI) database should be selected based on the scope of the assessment. For agriculture and food products, we recommend using the Agribalyse database, as it is one of the most comprehensive and widely accepted LCA databases. Although its products and processes are primarily focused on France, they are also largely representative of other European countries. That said, while Agribalyse offers valuable data on the French context and European food systems, it may not always accurately reflect practices in other regions with differing agricultural methods. Country-specific adjustments for production-related data—such as yield, pesticide use, fertilizer application, and irrigation levels—can be made using data from FAO statistics². It should be noted that while Agribalyse is a comprehensive database, there may be gaps in

² National authorities should allocate funds to develop LCI databases tailored to their country, as this would enhance results and facilitate easier implementation.

data for specific products, production methods, or regions. The LCI databases and agriculture statistics data sources are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Environmental impact assessment data sources.

Data Source	About the data
FAOSTAT [168]	Provides comprehensive data on food and agriculture, including production, trade, and consumption data at the country level.
IFASTAT [169]	Provides statistical data on fertilizers and agricultural inputs, including use, trade, and production.
FAO AQUASTAT [170]	Provides data on global water information that includes data on water resources, irrigation, and agricultural water use.
Agribalyse database [166]	Contains detailed LCI data for agricultural and food products, covering environmental impacts across the entire supply chain.
Agri-Footprint database [171]	Provides LCI data for agricultural products, focusing on environmental impacts at production level.
Ecoinvent [165]	A comprehensive LCA database with global data on environmental impacts for a wide range of products and processes, including agriculture and food production.
World Food LCA [172]	Offers LCI data specifically for food products, covering environmental impacts.

SOCIAL CAPITAL

Social impacts can be assessed using primary data, but where primary data is hard to obtain, a social risk assessment can be conducted using secondary databases and appropriate LCA software. Other social impacts need to be assessed through other methods. For example, food affordability can be assessed by applying the Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet methodology outlined by Herforth et al. [173]. Details of available assessment methods for social impacts of diets are provided below.

The social domain has the least coverage in the scientific literature when it comes to validated metrics for dietary impact assessment. Table 5 presents the relevant social impacts of diets. The social risk assessment of diets in the PLAN'EAT Deliverable D3.3 "True Costs and Benefits of Three EU Diets" shows that the highest risks within the supply chain are linked to labour-related issues. At a minimum, initial attention and efforts should focus on assessing labour-related impacts, as they represent the most significant area of concern in the social dimension.

Table 5. Overview of globally relevant impacts under social capital.

Impact category**	Impact indicator	Unit	Source
Food security	Food security index measuring ratio of change in price of a basic food basket per change in price of a product	-	Capitals Coalition (2023) [174]
Benefits sharing	Index measuring the change in number of people reached through community engagement	-	Capitals Coalition (2023)[174]

Lack of union rights	Instances of denied freedom of association*	Number of violations	True Price (2023) [175]
Gender equity	Gender gap in hours worked*	Minutes per day	OECD (2024) [176]
Gender equity	Gender pay gap*	€	True Cost Initiative (2022) [177]
Human rights violation	Underage workers below minimum age*	Child Full-Time Equivalent (FTE)	True Price (2023) [157]
Human rights violation	Forced labour*	FTE DALY	True Price (2023) [157] True Cost Initiative (2022) [177]
Laws and regulations	V-Dem Accountability Index	-	FSCI (2023) based on Varieties of Democracies [178]
Laws and regulations	Corruption Perceptions Index (0-100 Index)	-	Transparency International (2023) [179]
Laws and regulations	Prior Informed Consent (PIC) procedures for trade of pesticides and chemicals	Number of export notifications and responses	European Chemical Agency (2015)[180]
Food affordability	Food affordability index measuring food price in relation to standard income	-	Harrison et al. (2022) [181]
Social risk	Social risk on the production side (Index)	-	Frehner et al. (2021) [182]
Food availability	Net imports relative to production	%	Turner et al. (2018) [183]
Acceptability	Mean departure from observed diet	%	Perignon et al. (2016) [36]
Income	Wage gap from unequal opportunities (e.g. gender, racial, or religious discrimination)*	€	True Price (2023) [157]
Integration of workforce into communities	Index measuring the change in number of migrant workers with feeling of exclusion	-	Capitals Coalition (2023)[174]

*Impacts that can be assessed with TCA approach.

** Based on TEEB (2018).

Social impact assessment

Impact indicators defined under social capital—such as forced labour, child labour, or wage gap—cannot be estimated using the LCA approach due to the lack of secondary data and appropriate models. However, these impacts can be assessed through other methods such as the Eco-Cost Methodology (Ecocost Value, n.d.) and

the Anker Methodology [184]. Both methods rely on primary data within the product supply chain, such as workers' ages, working hours, and monthly net wages. When primary data for this information is available, these methods can be effectively applied using existing monetization factors for the respective impact indicators, as outlined in the *TCA Handbook* by the True Cost Initiative [177].

When primary data is unavailable, alternative approaches like Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) with secondary data can be used to evaluate social risks. Through s-LCA-based social risk assessment, social sustainability can be evaluated. This approach helps identify hotspots in the supply chain that may require intervention to reduce negative social impacts and improve sustainability. It should be noted that the availability of secondary data remains limited and, since impact assessment through s-LCA is a relatively new approach, suitable monetization methods are still under development. As a result, it is currently not possible to fully quantify these impacts with existing monetization factors.

Social Life Cycle Assessment

S-LCA is conceptually defined in *Guidelines for the Social Life Cycle Assessment* [185], which covers the five stakeholder categories and related impact categories described below:

- **Worker/human rights:** freedom of association and collective bargaining, child labour, fair salary, working hours, forced labour, equal opportunities/discrimination, health and safety, social benefits/social security.
- **Consumer/cultural heritage:** health and safety, feedback mechanism, consumer privacy, transparency, end of life responsibility.
- **Local community/working conditions:** access to material resources, access to immaterial resources, delocalization and migration, cultural heritage, safe and healthy living conditions, respect of Indigenous rights, community engagement, local employment, secure living conditions.
- **Society/health and safety:** public commitments to sustainability issues, contribution to economic development, prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts, technology development, corruption.
- **Value chain actors/governance:** fair competition, promoting social responsibility, supplier relationships, respect of intellectual property rights.

For a full picture of the true costs of diets, the values of all these social impacts need to be considered. However, many of them are currently not quantifiable due to a lack of quantitative methods or the inability to monetize qualitative information. Further, the complexity and multidimensionality of certain social factors make them challenging to quantify in monetary terms. Therefore, we recommend implementing a social risk assessment using a secondary social impact database. Social risk assessment can be conducted using the Social Hotspot Database (SHDB) [186] as a data source, along with LCA software.

The SHDB is designed to identify and evaluate social risks within global supply chains, covering labour conditions, human rights issues, community impacts, and other social dimensions influenced by production and consumption activities. It includes a set of 160 social indicators to assess various aspects of social sustainability. Users can select indicators based on their relevance to specific social risks and their ability to reflect the hotspots at different stages of the supply chain. With the SHDB's own LCIA method, the Social Hotspots Index, social risks are expressed for each impact indicator in medium risk hours equivalent (mrheq) per kg of product. This unit reflects both the likelihood and severity of social risks based on labour intensity and risk levels in the country and sector of production. A value of 1 mrheq represents a medium level of risk; the higher the mrheq, the greater the potential social risk. This helps identify areas in the supply chain that may require attention or intervention.

Social risk assessment can help to improve dietary recommendations by identifying products or product categories that contribute significantly to social risks within diets. By comparing social risks across different foods, such as beef, poultry, vegetables, or legumes, it is possible to highlight specific hotspots where interventions are most needed. These may include products (e.g. beans or exotic fruits sourced from high-risk countries) or supply chain stages (e.g. that are tied to poor labour practices). The results can guide targeted actions, such as recommending the reduction of reliance on high-risk imports and promoting socially-certified alternatives from countries with stronger labour standards (e.g. Fairtrade products). This can help reduce social impacts by promoting locally grown or certified options to mitigate risks.

To conduct the social risk assessment of diets, the following data points regarding the food product's supply chain need to be collected:

1. Each product in the constructed diet must be mapped to one of the 57 Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) sectors included in the SHDB.
2. Producer price (costs) of each food product. In the SHDB, producer prices are necessary because they are used to calculate social risks and serve as the main factor differentiating risks for products within the same sector.

When interpreting social risk results from the s-LCA approach with SHDB data, several uncertainties should be considered. This is largely due to the way the SHDB constructs the data. The SHDB models serve to interpret underlying statistical and sectoral information to estimate risk levels, often by aggregating both qualitative and quantitative information. However, the nature of these models introduces substantial uncertainty. The SHDB applies general risk classifications (e.g. low, medium, high, very high) based on expert judgment, data distribution across sectors and countries, and existing literature. The accuracy of these classifications can vary depending on the availability and quality of the underlying data. Additionally, since the SHDB relies on generic sector-level data, it may overlook specific details relevant to products or local conditions. The aggregation of information across broad categories can oversimplify complex socio-economic realities. This is particularly important when interpreting results for individual products or sectors, where the assessed risk may appear disproportionately high due to the generalized nature of the data or the hotspot-focused approach. Another source of uncertainty in the risk assessment is the way certain products are grouped into broad sectors within the SHDB. For example, legumes are categorized under the "vegetables and fruits" sector, along with all other vegetable and fruit products. This means that the social risks associated with legumes such as beans or chickpeas are not product-specific, but rather reflect the general risks assigned to the entire sector. As a result, the assessment does not account for differences in production conditions or specific social risks that may apply to individual types of legumes.

Diet affordability assessment

A diet affordability assessment can be implemented by applying the Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet methodology outlined by Herforth et al. [173], which involves:

1. matching the **food categories** used in the diet modelling to align with the International Comparison Program's (ICP) Food Prices for Nutrition (FPN) categories (the FPN database categorizes food costs under groups such as fruits, vegetables, starchy staples, animal-sourced foods, legumes, nuts and seeds, and oils and fats; therefore, this step is necessary to be able to assess the costs of the food items defined in the diets);
2. calculating diet costs based on these aligned food categories using food price data from the ICP; and evaluating diet affordability based on household income data [187]. The threshold for affordability can be set at 20–30% of daily income spent on food, which aligns with the literature [188].

Previous studies on the affordability of the EAT-Lancet [189] and other healthy diets [190] have shown that sustainable, healthy diets remain within the affordability range for high-income countries.

Data sources

Two secondary input/output databases are currently available for social impact assessment (Table 6). We recommend using the SHDB to conduct social risk assessments and identify hotspots in the food supply chain, as it covers a broader range of sectors and countries compared to the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment (PSILCA) database [191]. This allows for the assessment of a wider variety of products. For affordability assessment of diets, useful data sources are presented in Table 7.

Table 6. Data sources for social impact assessment.

Data source	Description
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SHDB [186]	Provides data on social risks and impacts across global supply chains, including 160 indicators for 57 sectors, covering categories such as labour conditions, human rights, and community well-being. The LCI (Life Cycle Inventory) database describes performed work hours within different sectors and countries for the production of commodities.
PSILCA Database [191]	Provides data on social impacts across supply chains, including 69 indicators, covering categories such as labour rights, working conditions, wages, and other social dimensions.
FAOSTAT Producer prices database	Provides food prices in USD/kg to implement in social risk assessment by SHDB.

Table 7: Diet affordability data.

Data source	Description
International Comparison Program's Food Prices for Nutrition (ICP FPN)	Provides standardized, cross-country food cost and diet affordability data.
Eurostat's European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SLIC) [187]	Provides comprehensive information on income, poverty, social exclusion, and living conditions across European countries.

HUMAN CAPITAL

We recommend using one of the two methods explained below to quantify consumption-related dietary health impacts and costs, such as those associated with noncommunicable diseases. Health impacts resulting from environmental pollution during food production (such as human toxicity) can be assessed using the environmental LCA method outlined in the Natural Capital section. This section provides details on estimating dietary-intake-related health impacts and the relevant data sources required. Other human-capital-related impacts (such as occupational incidents and wage gap below living wage) can be assessed using primary data, but where primary data is unavailable, a social risk assessment covering these impacts can be conducted using secondary databases and appropriate LCA software. Details of these assessment components are provided in the following section. Table 8 provides an overview of health- and other human-capital-related impacts.

Table 8. Overview of globally relevant impacts under human capital.

Impact category**	Impact Indicator	Unit	Source
Occupational health and safety risks	Workers who experienced non-physical, non-sexual harassment*	Number of workers	True Price (2023) [157]
Occupational health and safety risks	Non-fatal occupational incidents*	Incidents	True Price (2023) [157]
Occupational health and safety risks	Fatal occupational incidents*	Incidents	True Price (2023) [157]
Occupational health and safety risks	Health conditions due to excessive working hours*	Disability-adjusted life years (DALYs)	True Cost Initiative (2022) [177]

Mental health	Contribution to increased suicide rates in agriculture (indirect)	n/a	n/a
Production-related human health impacts	Human toxicity (air pollution)*	DALYs	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Production-related human health impacts	Human toxicity (water pollution)*	DALYs	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Production-related human health impacts	Human toxicity (soil pollution)*	DALYs	Huijbregts et al. (2016) [163]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of undernutrition*	DALYs	Fitzpatrick et al. (2019) [192]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of malnutrition*	DALYs	WBCSD (2018) [193]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of hypertension*	DALYs	WBCSD (2018) [193]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of noncommunicable diseases*	DALYs	WBCSD (2018) [193]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of dementia*	DALYs	Fitzpatrick et al. (2019) [192]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of food poisoning*	DALYs	WBCSD (2018) [193]
Consumption-related human health impacts	Health impact of pesticide exposure*	DALYs	WBCSD (2018) [193]
Public health threats from livestock production	Health impact of antibiotic use*	DALYs	Fitzpatrick et al. (2019) [192]
Public health threats from livestock production	Contribution to the exposure to zoonotic diseases (indirect)*	DALYs	n/a
Income	Wage gap below minimum wage*	€	True Price (2023) [157]
Income	Wage gap below living wage*	€	True Cost Initiative (2022) [177]
Income security	Workers without legal social security*	FTE	True Price (2023) [157]

*Impacts that can be assessed with TCA approach.

** Based on TEEB (2018).

Assessment of health costs of diets

Health costs assessment of diets can be conducted by following one of two methodologies: (1) the Cost of Illness (COI) approach by Seidel et al. [142], or (2) the comparative risk assessment of diet-related health risks method by Springmann et al., (2021) [158]. The COI approach by Seidel et al. [142] tends to overestimate health costs because it assumes a linear dose-response relationship between food intake and dietary risks, which may not accurately reflect real-world risk patterns. In contrast, the comparative risk assessment

method may underestimate costs, as it only focuses on mortality outcomes and does not capture the reduction in quality of life from chronic diseases such as type 2 diabetes. These conditions often require long-term treatment and reduce productivity, thereby generating significant additional societal costs that this method omits. As a result, the comparative approach potentially underrepresents the economic burden of diet-related diseases. Despite these issues, both methods are peer-reviewed and accepted in the scientific community. It is likely that the true health costs of dietary patterns lie somewhere between the estimates provided by these two approaches. Therefore, applying both methods in parallel can provide a more balanced assessment and help capture the full range of potential health costs.

The Cost of Illness (COI) Approach

The COI approach by Seidel et al. [142] enables the assessment of the costs of malnutrition or the potential cost savings due to healthier diets. The analysis focuses on three major malnutrition-related diseases (cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and neoplasms) and calculating Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) for each of the three diseases to quantify the total burden, representing the combined number of years lost due to poor health, disability, or early death. DALYs are then monetized using national COI estimates, which capture both direct healthcare costs (e.g. medical treatments, hospitalizations) and indirect costs (e.g. productivity loss due to morbidity and premature death).

Health costs are attributed to dietary patterns by linking foods to recognized dietary risk factors according to their contribution to DALYs. Each representative product in the modelled diet is matched with a dietary risk factor, which falls into one of two main categories: excessive intake (of e.g. red meat, sugar-sweetened beverages, and sodium) or insufficient intake (of e.g. fruits, vegetables, legumes, and nuts). To measure the extent of dietary risks, a baseline of healthy consumption is established. A country's healthy consumption baseline is defined using the recommended intake levels set by, for example, its national health authorities. This means that the health costs associated with consumption at the national recommendation level are set to zero. Any deviation, whether of actual intake or other recommendation levels, is therefore considered either beneficial or detrimental to health and correspondingly increases or decreases health costs (see Appendix B for an example result). A linear dose-response relationship is assumed for all products, meaning that each additional unit of intake has the same positive or negative effect on external health costs. Once dietary intake is mapped to risk factors and compared against the healthy baseline, the deviation from that baseline is calculated for each factor. DALYs attributable to specific diseases are then proportionally allocated to these deviations. Multiplying these values by the COI per DALY yields the per capita annual health costs.

The comparative risk assessment of diet-related health risks method

The second method that can be used to estimate the health costs of different diets is the comparative risk assessment method developed by Springmann et al. (2021) [158]. We provide a summary of the method below; detailed implementation steps, including formulas and related data, can be found in Supplementary Appendix I of Springmann et al. (2021) [158].

This approach starts with estimating how many deaths and cases of disease are linked to certain dietary factors by using a proportion called population impact fractions (PIFs). These fractions show how much disease could be prevented if diets changed from current patterns to healthier alternatives. PIF is calculated based on relative risk of diseases and the population size. The relative risk estimates linking diet-related risk factors to specific disease outcomes (e.g. heart disease, stroke, cancer, type 2 diabetes) include non-linear dose-response relationships for fruits and vegetables, nuts and seeds, and fish, meaning that the effect on disease risk changes at different levels of intake (e.g. the first few servings might have a bigger impact than later ones). For all other risk factors, a linear dose-response relationship is assumed, where the risk changes at a constant rate with changes in intake. Since the analysis mainly looks at deaths from chronic diseases, it focuses on adults aged 20 and older. These relative risk parameters are provided in Supplementary Appendix I of Springmann et al. (2021).

The method then estimates the number of deaths that could be avoided by reducing a specific risk factor, which is calculated by multiplying the PIF by the disease-specific death rate, and the total number of people in the population. It estimates how many lives could be saved if a diet-related risk was reduced. In this calculation, mortality data can be adapted from the Global Burden of Disease project [194,195].

To finally value the diet-related health outcomes, the method links the number of attributable deaths in each dietary scenario to cost-of-illness estimates. These estimates account for both direct costs, such as medical and healthcare expenses, and indirect costs, including informal care and productivity losses from missed workdays. Springmann et al. (2021) provide a set of cost-of-illness estimates (in USD per death) for cardiovascular diseases, cancer, stroke, and type 2 diabetes across different regions.

Assessment of other human capital related impacts

Other impacts on human capital, such as occupational health and safety, excessive working hours, and income conditions, cannot be accurately estimated using LCA with secondary data due to insufficient data and models. These impacts can instead be assessed using primary data through methodologies like the Eco-Cost Methodology (Ecocost Value, n.d.) and the Anker Methodology [184]. These methods utilize data from the supply chain, including accident rates, illnesses, fatalities, worker demographics, working hours, and wages. Alternatively, social life cycle assessment (s-LCA) with the SHDB can be used to evaluate these risks through secondary data, as covered in the Social Capital section above.

Data sources

Table 9 presents available data for the health impacts assessment of diets, based on the COI approach by Seidel et al. [157].

Table 9. Data for the COI method.

Data source	About the data
Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation from the University of Washington [196]	DALY rates of individual countries and DALY rates for dietary risk factors.
EUROSTAT—Populations and social conditions [197]	Population data on a national level for calculations of dietary risk factors.
European Cardiovascular Disease Statistics [198]	Calculates cardiovascular disease costs; it documents mortality, morbidity, costs, risk factors, and other key statistics from all over Europe.
Systematic review of economic studies on costs for diabetes mellitus [199] Estimating the current and future costs of Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes in the UK, including direct health costs and indirect societal and productivity costs [200] Direct Medical Costs of Type 2 Diabetes in France: An Insurance Claims Database Analysis [201] Impact of type 2 diabetes on health expenditure: estimation based on individual administrative data [202] Cost burden of type 2 diabetes in Germany: results from the population-based KORA studies [203]	These studies are examples that can be used to calculate the costs of type 2 diabetes. They represent France, Germany, and the UK. Similar studies can be found for other European countries.

The cost of cancer in Europe [204]	Total cost of cancer differentiated for countries all across Europe; can be used to estimate neoplasm costs.
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PHASE 5 – Estimate the hidden costs

In this phase, the quantified environmental, social, and health impacts of diets are translated into monetary terms. This is done by applying monetization factors that assign a financial value to each type of impact, such as greenhouse gas emissions, land use, or health outcomes. The result is an estimate of the hidden costs embedded in food items and dietary patterns.

Monetization provides a way to express diverse impacts in a common unit, allowing a comprehensive comparison of impacts. This supports more informed decision-making. In the context of designing FBDGs, monetizing dietary impacts offers a clear advantage. It makes it easier to compare the health, environmental, and social impacts of diets, and to highlight trade-offs and synergies.

Monetization factors

Monetization factors convert quantitative estimates of environmental, human health, and social impacts into monetary values, reflecting either costs (e.g. due to ill health) or benefits (e.g. due to better health). These factors are developed by various organizations and differ in their methodologies and applicability; i.e. they may represent either costs of restoring environmental quality to its original state (the abatement costs approach) or the burden borne by society due to the impacts of an activity (the damage costs approach).

Various sources provide monetization factors that are suitable for different types of impact assessments and their respective environmental, health, or social impacts [162,175]. For valuing the results of environmental impact assessments conducted using the ReCiPe 2016 LCIA method, two primary sources are recommended:

- **The True Price Foundation** adopts a rights-based approach, where a product is considered sustainable if the basic rights of all, including future generations, are respected in production and consumption. Here, monetization factors represent the remediation costs associated with a negative environmental or social impact [175].
- **CE Delft’s Environmental Prices Handbook** implements a damage cost approach, which reflects restoration and compensation costs resulting from environmental damage. Restoration costs are incurred to return a system to its original or target state; e.g. through afforestation after land-use changes, while compensation costs represent the economic or non-economic burden borne by society due to the environmental impacts of food production or consumption [162].

In addition to environmental impacts, both sources provide monetization factors for human health impacts related to production activities. The two methods should not be used in combination as they calculate different costs; it is recommended to choose one. Apart from these two sources, other references listed in Table 10 provide monetization factors for various indicators that align with other impact estimation methods.

Table 10. Data sources and their provided monetization factors for various indicators.

Data source	Provides
True Price Foundation, <i>Monetisation factors for true pricing</i> [175]	Monetization factors for a wide range of environmental, social, and human health impacts, based on a rights-based approach.
CE Delft, <i>Environmental Prices Handbook</i> [162]	Monetization factors for environmental and human health impacts, primarily following a damage cost approach.
Ecocosts Value, <i>Sustainability Impact Metrics</i> [205]	Monetization factors for environmental impacts based on prevention costs. Focuses on emissions, energy use, resource depletion, and waste.

<i>TCA Handbook</i> [177]	Guidance on impact assessment with primary data and applying monetization factors for TCA. Covers environmental, health, and social impact categories.
German Environmental Agency, <i>Value Factors 2020</i> [206]	Monetization factors for the assessment of environmental costs. Focuses on impacts categories such as climate change, air pollution, and water pollution.

The source of this data is reported in the References section.

PHASE 6 – Taking the result into account for the design of FBDGs

Use TCA results to guide the refinement of dietary guidelines by highlighting food groups with the highest impacts, ensuring FBDGs promote both human health and sustainability. In this phase, the results from the TCA assessment are integrated into the design of FBDGs. This involves using the TCA findings to identify the key food groups contributing to the negative environmental, social, and health impacts of diets, as well as the associated hidden costs. FBDGs can then incorporate specific recommendations that address these negative impacts, prioritizing actions that deliver the benefits for both human health and environmental sustainability.

An example result of the implementation of TCA on FBDGs applied for two countries (Germany and Ireland) is presented in Appendix B. The example compares the environmental, health, and social impacts of three dietary patterns: the actual diet, the national dietary recommendations, and the Planetary Health Diet (PHD). Importantly, the purpose of this comparison is not to directly transfer dietary pattern results into FBDGs. Instead, the findings should be used to strengthen specific recommendations. For example; if the consumption of a specific product has a high negative impact, this reinforces the recommendation to limit its consumption; on the contrary, if a specific food item has a low negative impact or a positive impact, its consumption could be encouraged.

The TCA assessment provides authorities with a comprehensive evidence base to refine dietary guidelines. In particular, the results can be used to:

- Gain a comprehensive view of how different diets perform in terms of environmental, health, and social sustainability.
- Identify key cost and impact drivers in the FBDGs compared to the PHD. This helps to highlight the food groups that contribute most to negative impacts and to target dietary adjustments accordingly.
- Understand how variations in food consumption within dietary patterns influence environmental and health outcomes.
- Refine dietary guidelines to minimize both health and environmental costs, promoting more sustainable eating habits.
- Address social risks by assessing how shifting from current diets to more sustainable options can reduce overall social risks linked to food production.
- Promote dietary patterns that balance minimizing negative health, environmental, and social impacts in order to create more sustainable food and nutrition policies.

Where the TCA assessment results of FBDGs show that national recommendations already perform better than the PHD (as referenced in the example of Germany in Appendix B), these findings can reinforce the specific dietary guidelines as a strong model to follow. The focus on improving the dietary guidelines should then be directed towards other aspects rather than adapting national recommendations based on sustainability impacts. The FBDGs should give more consideration to the real diet of the population group, increasing alignment between guidelines and actual consumption patterns, and enhancing strategies to improve compliance with existing recommendations.

In conclusion, the application of the TCA method can be a useful tool for decision-makers to identify the major impacts resulting from the adoption of various dietary patterns. However, the results should be seen as a starting point for discussion for the authorities responsible for developing FBDGs. National authorities can interpret the findings and ensure that FBDGs balance health, environmental, and social goals while remaining practical and relevant to the population.

NECESSARY RESOURCES AND TOOLS

The application of TCA to the development of FBDGs requires a combination of specialized expertise, sufficient time, and access to appropriate tools and data. This section outlines the essential knowledge areas and technical skills needed, the estimated time frame for conducting the analysis, and an overview of associated costs for software, databases, and expert consultancy. Together, these elements provide the foundation for ensuring that TCA-based assessments are both rigorous and feasible.

Required expertise

Experts should have expertise in the areas of food systems and nutrition, economics, environmental science, and impact assessment. Those applying TCA to the development of FBDGs should have expertise in impact assessment and monetization approaches, as well as good knowledge of:

- **Food production and consumption** (food production conditions, consumption patterns, and composition databases)
- **Nutrition science** (and the ability to assess and compare dietary recommendations)
- **Impacts (environmental, health, and social) of food production and consumption**
- **Environmental life cycle assessment (LCA) principles and use of LCA software**
- **Social LCA** (social impact assessment and familiarity with e.g. the Social Hotspot Database (SHDB))
- **Human health impact assessment** (and the ability to analyse these impacts using the Cost of Illness (COI) approach [157] or the comparative risk assessment of diet-related health risks (Springmann et al., 2021) [158] method)
- **TCA** (including monetization approaches)

Time frame

The time frame presented is estimated for implementation by a single skilled expert (Table 11). However, if the necessary skills or access to data and methods are lacking, the required time could be longer.

Table 11. Time frame of TCA implementation for FBDGs development.

Steps	Minimum required time for a skilled expert
Selection of impact categories; selection of monetization method; screening available databases and datasets; data collection	1–2 months
Constructing dietary intakes; conducting environmental LCA; human health impact analysis and social LCA; monetization of assessed impacts	4 months

Costs

The costs of resources, tools, and expert consultancy are presented in Table 12. These costs may vary depending on the software and data used and the experience level of the expert.

Table 12. Costs of required resources and tools.

Resources and tools	Cost
LCA software (e.g. OpenLCA, SimaPro)	€0–€6,000/year
Environmental life cycle inventory database (e.g. Agribalyse, ecoinvent)	€0–€4,500/year
Social database (e.g. SHDB)	€3,000–€6,000/year
Health impact datasets	Mostly free of charge
Expert consultancy	6–12 person months*

* Person months depend on the amount of food products to be modelled.

True Cost Accounting

Implications for FBDGs

TCA is an integrated, systems-based approach that monetizes the health, environmental, and social impacts of food production and consumption. TCA could be used to develop FBDGs through i) identifying key factors contributing to the negative impacts and true costs of diets; ii) prioritizing high-impact improvement actions; iii) developing effective strategies for a transition toward sustainable food systems that promote healthier populations and a more sustainable planet.

Approach

Step 1: Framing the analysis to clarify its purpose.

Step 2: Defining the scope, boundaries, and assumptions of the analysis.

Step 3: Measure and value by i) defining the amount of current food intake, the dietary pattern of the population group, and the amount of recommended food and non-alcoholic drinks consumption in the FBDGs, together with identifying a reference diet; ii) identifying representative food items for current diets and dietary recommendations to model impacts at the level of food product; iii) using trade data to identify the countries of production and national statistics to provide details on production activities and local conditions; iv) using Life Cycle Assessment method to estimate environmental impacts and social risks, and Cost of Illness or the comparative risk of diet-related health risks method to estimate diet-related health impacts; v) applying monetization factors where possible to translate these impacts into the hidden costs of food items and diets.

Step 4: Take action.

Resources

Developing the analysis requires at least six months. Experts applying this methodology should have a good knowledge of the following areas: food production and consumption; nutrition science; environmental, social, health impacts of food production and consumption; environmental LCA principles and use of LCA software; social LCA; human health impact assessment; TCA.

Food groups

To achieve a common methodology at the European level, the following standardizations are proposed based on the commonalities and differences in the analysed European FBDGs available in the FAO repository [32]. Starting from the study of Salesse et al. [74], with the supporting studies of Klapp et al. [207] and James-Martin et al. [56], in which global FBDGs were investigated from different perspectives, and the issue of food group standardization was highlighted and analyzed, the food groups present in the FBDGs of individual European countries were examined. Building on their work, standardized approach grounded on the most similarities were proposed, and evidence-based solutions in cases of gaps were provided. This standardized grouping aims to establish clearer guidelines that can be consistently applied across EU countries, ensuring that dietary advice will be coherent and scientifically grounded. The first step of food group merging consisted in the creation of two large categories: the recommended food groups and the food groups to limit. This grouping aims to provide a clearer structure for future FBDGs, differentiating between foods that should be the basic components of a healthy and sustainable diet and those that should be limited, considering them discretionary in the sense of food items not necessary to fulfil the nutritional needs (such as fruit juices, savoury snacks, etc.). A third section has been added to highlight the role of alcoholic beverages, which should be avoided because it is difficult to define a quantity of consumption exempt to health risks.

Specifically, for the recommended food groups, both quantitative and qualitative recommendations have been provided to guide consumption in terms of frequency and variety, considering both health and environmental impacts. At the same time, EU countries retain the flexibility to adapt these general quantitative and qualitative recommendations at the national and/or regional level, in order to reflect local food cultures and traditional preferences.

RECOMMENDED FOOD GROUPS

In the “Recommended Foods Group” foods which are essential to achieve a healthy and sustainable dietary pattern are included. The consumption of these foods is recommended across all the FBDGs analysed because, when consumed daily or weekly in appropriate portions sizes, they provide the essential nutrients required and contribute to the prevention of non-communicable diseases (NCDs – cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, obesity, cancer, etc.) [208–210].

Fruits and Vegetables group (F&V group): Combining "Fruits" and "Vegetables" into a single food group was observed in 15 available European countries. These foods are often grouped together due to their low energy density and their role as sources rich in essential nutrients such as vitamins, minerals, trace elements and dietary fibre. Additionally, they serve as the primary source of dietary bioactive compounds (phytochemicals), naturally occurring potential protective substances that frequently contribute to their colours [211–213]. For these reasons, the combination of F&V in a single food group simplifies categorization while maintaining nutritional coherence. To maintain a balanced diet, it is essential to consume both fruits and vegetables (fresh or raw) daily and to eat a variety of these products to ensure a diverse array of vitamins, minerals, and fibre. Even though the specification of the minimum recommendation for each is advisable, as WHO guideline indicated to consumer at least 400 grams of fruits and vegetables per day [214], highlighting the importance of variety is a key aspect, as different fruits and vegetables offer various health benefits. Other elements of variability related to F&V group are related to the possible inclusion of fruit juice in “Fruits” group and potatoes in the “Vegetables” group. Considering the nutritional profile of fruit juice and potatoes and to standardize their positioning in the food groups at the EU level, these two items should be included in other food groups than in the F&V groups. Specifically, fruit juices, due to their high content of free sugars, and considering the position of WHO that consider fruit juices not comparable with fruit [215] are placed within the discretionary foods group. Potatoes, on the other hand, are included in the grain products, roots, and tubers group, because of their high starch content [216].

In the absence of fresh products, frozen fruits and vegetables can serve as valid alternatives, as they are typically frozen shortly after harvest and retain most of their nutritional properties. However, the consumption of fresh fruits and vegetables should be prioritised whenever possible to maximise the intake of certain heat-sensitive nutrients and preserve texture and taste.

Quantitative recommendations	<p>Consume at least 400 grams of fruits and vegetables per day, as recommended by WHO.</p> <p>This amount should ideally be divided into at least 5 portions (e.g., 2 portions of fruit and 3 of vegetables) throughout the day.</p>
Qualitative recommendations	<p>Include a wide variety of fruits and vegetables in the daily diet.</p> <p>Prefer fresh products whenever possible, otherwise frozen fruits and vegetables can be used as a convenient and nutritionally valid alternative.</p>

Fish and seafood, Meat (red and white), Eggs, and Legumes group and other plant-based alternatives (treated to extend shelf life maintaining the nutritional profile) group: This grouping of protein rich foods shows the most variability in the inclusion of legumes, as they are sometimes included and sometimes excluded, depending on the specific FBDGs analysed. In fact, in 13 European countries legumes can be found aggregated with other foods, as in vegetables group, fruit-vegetable group, grains group, or in protein group with or without the inclusion of nuts and oilseeds. This variability is justified considering their unique nutritional profile (rich sources of plant-based protein, carbohydrates, dietary fibres, and bioactive compounds) that allows them to fit into different food groups [217]. At the same time, the analysis of European FBDGs revealed consistency in merging fish, meat, and eggs, an approach that was followed by 19 European countries. To standardize at the EU level, it is suggested to create a single group including all protein-rich foods. This standardization could contribute positively to promote human health and environmental sustainability.

Within this unified group, however, it remains essential to distinguish between animal-based (fish and seafood, red and white meat, and eggs) and plant-based protein-rich foods (such as legumes and other plant-based alternatives that are processed to extend shelf life while preserving nutritional quality). This distinction is particularly important from both a health and sustainability perspective.

Integrating legumes into the same group of other protein-rich foods can help consumer awareness of their nutritional and health benefits, particularly as a valuable source of plant-based protein [218,219]. This could gradually lead to a reduction in the consumption of animal-based products, promoting a healthier and more sustainable eating pattern. Several studies have analysed the health impact of replacing animal-based proteins with legumes, highlighting reductions in Body Mass Index (BMI), waist circumference, Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, CVD and all causes of mortality [143,220–223].

Moreover, including legumes in weekly dietary recommendations could help to prevent protein deficiencies, a common concern when transitioning away from diets high in meat consumption [224]. Most legumes have a protein digestibility-corrected amino acid score (Protein digestibility-corrected amino acid score, PDCAAS) between 0.5 to 0.7, but pea and soy protein concentrates have a score of 0.89 and 1.0, respectively, similar to high-quality proteins such as eggs and milk [225]. One concern often raised is that most legumes are relatively limited in essential sulphur content, which, however, are present in other foods. For example, grains products are rich in sulphur-containing amino acids, while lysine is often a limiting component. Legumes, on the other hand, are high in lysine but low in sulphur amino acids. Consuming both food groups (legumes and grains) throughout the day helps meet the needs for both essential amino acids [226]. As highlighted by Young and Pellet, it is not required to consume complementary protein sources, such legumes and grains, in the same meal if the gap between meals is around 3h. In this case, the complementary amino acids will be metabolically available for protein synthesis [227].

Therefore, recommending the consumption of different proteins sources during the week -prioritizing plant-based over animal-based options - can provide a well-balanced diet with sufficient essential amino acids.

This classification could also simplify the message for consumers, making it clearer that legumes are a key component of a balanced dietary pattern. Emphasising their protein content would help consumers recognize their role in achieving adequate protein intake while moving towards more plant-based dietary patterns. As reviewed by Onwezen M.C et al (2021), consumers are already more inclined to replace animal-based proteins with legumes (followed by plant-based alternatives) compared to less familiar protein sources such as insects, algae, etc., which are still far from the general population's imagination [228]. Furthermore, Faber et al. (2021) suggest that legumes could be well-received by a wide range of consumers in different countries, potentially facilitating the transition to more plant-based diets [229].

The inclusion of other plant-based alternatives such as tofu, tempeh, soy-based products in this group, which offer significant protein content, reinforces the growing recognition of these products as nutritional and environmental options, based on their growing industrial market in Europe and the increasing consumption [230]. Nevertheless, emphasis should be placed on minimally processed plant-based alternatives defined as products derived from plants that undergo limited processing techniques to maintain their natural characteristics while providing convenience to consumers. These products are typically fresh or lightly treated to extend shelf life and improve quality without altering significantly their original form or nutritional content [134,231].

From an environmental perspective, incorporating legumes into this group and promoting their consumption as substitutes to animal-based products can contribute significantly to reducing the ecological footprint of diet [232]. Including legumes in the protein-rich food group, along with specifying a weekly recommendation for the subgroup of plant-based foods in relation to animal-based products, can be helpful to underscore their role as a valid alternatives, rather than being perceived merely as part of the fruits and vegetables food group, where their environmental contributions might be overlooked [233].

Quantitative recommendations	<p>Provide specific weekly intake recommendation for protein-rich foods.</p> <p>Provide weekly benchmarks for plant-based protein-rich foods in relation to animal-based sources.</p>
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Qualitative recommendations	<p>Clearly differentiate plant-based and animal-based protein subgroups within dietary guidelines to help consumers make informed choices and better understand the benefits of plant-based options.</p> <p>Prioritise plant-based protein sources, such as legumes, tofu, tempeh, and other minimally processed plant-based alternatives, for both health and environmental benefits.</p> <p>Include a variety of protein rich sources to ensure a complete amino acid profile, coming from both plant and animal-based products.</p> <p>Limit red meat consumption and prioritize white meat for health and environmental concerns.</p> <p>Adapt recommendations for specific population groups (such as vegetarians and vegans).</p>
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Nuts & oilseeds food group: In 6 of the reviewed FBDGs, nuts and oil seeds (such as rapeseed, flaxseed, mustard seed, etc.) were added to broader food groups (proteins, proteins and legumes or fats/oil group), while in 19 countries no recommendations were provided for these foods. Maintaining nuts and oil seeds as a separate food group, from oils and fats and proteins, is recommended for several reasons related to their nutritional composition and health benefits. Their content of plant-based proteins, dietary fibre, vitamins, minerals, phytochemicals, and unsaturated fatty acids makes nuts a nutritionally important food [234]. The group “Oils and fats”, on the other hand, are primarily composed of free fatty acids and therefore do not provide the same variety of nutrients found in nuts (tree nuts) and oilseeds. At the same time, it is important for this food group to have a specific weekly recommendation due to its high energy density. A clear guideline helps encourage balanced consumption and allows consumers to obtain the nutritional benefits of nuts and oil seeds.

Quantitative recommendations	Provide specific weekly intake recommendation for nuts and oilseeds.
Qualitative recommendations	<p>Choose unsalted and unsweetened varieties to avoid added sodium and sugars.</p> <p>Include a variety of nuts and oilseeds to benefit from a broader spectrum of nutrients and bioactive compounds.</p>

Dairy product group: Most of the analysed FBDGs in this group comprise very different food items namely milk and plant-based alternative, yoghurt and other fermented milk products without added sugars, and cheese. Including these foods within the same food group is consistent considering them an excellent source of calcium and being derivative of milk. However, while the combination of milk, yogurt, and other fermented dairy products forms a food group with largely interchangeable items, this is not the case for plant-based alternatives and cheese, which have different nutritional profiles often characterized by high levels of added sugars and saturated fats/sodium, respectively. Regarding plant-based alternatives, in addition to recommending the consumption of products with no added sugars, it is important to emphasize that only soy-based alternatives or fortified alternatives (with calcium, B12 vitamin, vitamin D) have a nutrient content comparable to that of cow's milk [235]. Regarding the consumption of cheese, different recent studies had suggested that moderate cheese consumption is not associated with increased health risks and may even offer some protective effects against certain diseases [236–238] probably due to the "matrix effect," where other components in cheese interact with its structure, potentially leading to health benefits [239]. However, further research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms behind these associations and to establish optimal consumption levels for different populations. In addition, considering the different types of cheeses, specific recommendations could be established by each country depending on the most consumed typology according to the current eating habits. Therefore, for now it is crucial to provide specific weekly recommendations for plant-based alternatives and to guide a moderate consumption of cheese, ensuring

that individuals achieve the health benefits without exceeding the intake undesirable components. Additionally, promoting appropriate dairy product recommendations can contribute to reducing the environmental impact of dairy production. It is well known that the livestock sector contributes significantly to global GHG emissions. Balancing dairy product recommendations while considering both human health and environmental impacts could be a strategy to mitigate these effects [240].

<p>Quantitative recommendations</p>	<p>Provide specific daily recommendations for milk, yoghurt and other fermented milk products without added sugars.</p> <p>Provide specific daily or weekly recommendations for plant-based alternatives, particularly encouraging the consumption of soy-based or fortified options with a nutrient profile comparable to cow's milk.</p> <p>Recommend a moderate consumption of cheese, aligning with current evidence suggesting that moderate intake may not be associated with adverse health outcomes and could offer protective effects.</p> <p>Ensure adequate calcium intake and B12 vitamin through a balanced inclusion of milk, yogurt, and/or fortified plant-based alternatives without added sugars, tailored to the needs of different population groups.</p>
<p>Qualitative recommendations</p>	<p>Encourage environmentally conscious choices by balancing dairy consumption with alternatives that have a lower environmental impact, without compromising nutritional adequacy.</p> <p>Prioritize plant-based alternatives with no added sugars to reduce the intake of sugars often found in these substitutes.</p> <p>Adapt recommendations for specific population groups (such as vegetarians and vegans).</p>

Grain products, starchy roots and tubers group: In the FBDGs of the European countries analysed, there is a consensus on creating a single food group that includes grain products, roots and tubers. To achieve a better standardization at the EU level, within this food group, the following subcategories can be identified: grains and grain-based products (pasta, bread, rice, oats, barley, and other cereals), roots and tubers (potatoes, sweet potatoes, cassava, and other similar starchy vegetables), bread alternatives (crackers and other grain-based alternatives) and non-sugar sweetened or low sugar breakfast cereals (<5g of sugar/100g of solid product [241]). The composition of this food group should be adapted at the national level to reflect the culinary traditions and dietary habits of different countries due to their importance in European daily diets. Grain and grain-based products (pasta, bread, rice, etc.), are rich in complex carbohydrates (mainly starch) but also contain protein and dietary fibre, micronutrients and phytochemicals.

The levels of these nutrients vary significantly depending on whether whole grains or refined grains are considered. Whole grains consistently provide significantly higher amount of fibre, minerals, vitamins and phytochemicals. Therefore, prioritising whole grains is strongly recommended, as their daily consumption plays a crucial role in promoting a balanced and healthy diet [242,243]. Starchy roots and tubers, that contain a high level of starch, have different contents of dietary fibre, vitamins, minerals and phytochemicals [244]. Finally, bread substitutes and non-sugar-sweetened or low-sugar breakfast cereals could be products that have undergone industrial processing and are then classified as ultra-processed foods (UPFs) in the NOVA system [245], with characteristics that may differ from their original ingredients in terms of fibre and salt content and/or added sugars and fats, especially in many ready-to-eat breakfast cereals. Although these are processed products, they can be included in a balanced diet as an occasional alternative to the original product because they are ready to use and have a longer shelf life than fresh products. For this reason, providing specific recommendations for each food category in the food group helps to balance daily and

weekly consumption, avoids over-consumption of substitutes that may lack the nutritional quality of the original foods, and promotes both nutritional adequacy and dietary diversity.

Quantitative recommendations	Encourage the daily consumption of grains and grain-based products.
Qualitative recommendations	<p>Prioritise whole grains (e.g., wholemeal bread, brown rice, oats, barley) over refined grains, due to their higher content of dietary fibre, vitamins, minerals, and phytochemicals.</p> <p>Limit the intake of low-sugar breakfast cereals and bread alternatives to an occasional and convenience use.</p> <p>Promote dietary diversity within this food group by incorporating a variety of grains, roots, and tubers regularly, reflecting national and cultural dietary patterns.</p>

Oil and fats group: in 23 FBDGs analyzed no detailed classification was observed, and very few recommendations on the amounts that should be consumed were provided. Indeed, only 7 countries provided a number of portions per day for this food group, while other 3 countries included a recommendation range, as this group was combined with nuts & oilseeds. To standardize at the EU level, it is suggested to include in this food group: vegetable oils (olive oil, sunflower oil, canola oil, rapeseed oil, corn oil, soya oil, coconut oil, etc.), vegetable fats (margarine and other fats derived from plants) and animal fats (butter, lard, and other fats derived from animal sources). Besides this, the importance of having specific recommendations for each category within this food group lies in their different fatty acid composition which are closely linked to the prevention or increase of NCDs [246]. To help consumers maintain a more balanced diet, in addition to a quantitative recommendation, there should also be a qualitative recommendation regarding the daily preference for not refined vegetable oils over animal and vegetables fats within this food group.

Quantitative recommendations	Provide specific daily intake recommendation for oils and fats.
Qualitative recommendations	<p>Prioritize the consumption of unrefined vegetable oils (such as extra virgin olive oil, rapeseed oil, or sunflower oil) over animal fats (such as butter or lard) and industrial vegetable fats (such as margarine).</p> <p>The use of excessive amounts of oil, even if extra virgin olive oil, during food preparation and consumption should be minimized.</p>

Water: In all guidelines analyzed, recommendations were provided for the exclusive consumption of water. Ensuring adequate water intake is essential for maintaining optimal physiological function and metabolism, including thermoregulation, digestion, nutrient transport, and waste substances elimination [247]. While individual needs for water can vary based on factors such as age, body weight, activity level, and environmental conditions [248,249], a general qualitative guideline is to consume water consistently throughout the day to prevent dehydration. Additionally, consuming water-rich foods, such as fruits and vegetables, can complement daily hydration needs. Non-sweetened beverages such as herbal tea without stimulating (or nervine) ingredients, can also contribute to maintaining adequate hydration throughout the day. In fact, it is strongly recommended to prioritize the consumption of plain water over other types of drinks, such as sweetened beverages, energy drinks, and sodas, which can contribute to increase the risk of developing chronic conditions like obesity, type 2 diabetes, and cardiovascular disease [250]. From the environmental perspective, prioritizing the consumption of plain water from sustainable sources (tap water or filtered water), has a minimal environmental footprint compared to bottled drinks, which often require extensive packaging, transportation, and production processes.

Quantitative recommendations	Provide daily intake references for water.
Qualitative recommendations	<p>Prioritize plain water over other beverages.</p> <p>Consume water consistently throughout the day to avoid dehydration.</p> <p>Include water-rich foods (such as fruits and vegetables) to support hydration.</p> <p>Non-sweetened beverages (e.g., herbal tea without stimulating (or nervine) ingredients) can contribute to hydration.</p> <p>Avoid or limit sugar-sweetened beverages, energy drinks, and sodas, due to their link with chronic diseases (e.g., obesity, type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease).</p> <p>From an environmental standpoint, prefer tap or filtered water over bottled beverages due to lower ecological impact.</p> <p>Emphasize that water needs vary by age, body weight, activity level, and environmental conditions.</p>

FOOD GROUPS TO LIMIT

“Food groups to limit” include foods that should be consumed occasionally due to their poor nutritional values and considering them not necessary to fulfil the nutritional needs [251]. This macro-group contains: 1) Discretionary products or Extra foods and 2) Processed meat.

Discretionary Products or Extra foods in the analysed European FBDGs generally included foods and beverages that are High in Fat, Sugar and Salt (HFSS) and some of which could be classified as Ultra Processed Foods (UPFs) (this category is mainly included in this group, however UPFs could be found also in the recommended food group considering their nutritional profile, tradition of use and for convenience of consumption) [71,252]. Several studies have highlighted the link between the overconsumption of HFSS and UPFs and the onset of NCDs with an increased risk of obesity, cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, certain types of cancer, early mortality, due to their high caloric density and low nutritional values [253–255]. UPFs include a wide variety of industrially processed products, often energy-dense, and also high in added fats, sugar, and salts. Moreover, different studies have recognized UPFs as a significant contributing factor to poor health outcomes [256,257]. Additionally, in terms of nutritional impact, it is relevant to consider food formulations often assembled into ready-to-eat hyper-palatable foods, that could encourage consumers overconsumption, leading to unhealthy eating patterns [256,258]. For all these reasons, UPFs or HFSS foods have a long-term impact on health, highlighting the importance of moderating their consumption and preferring fresh or minimally processed foods in dietary guidelines. To better standardize this group at the EU level, the following sub-categories based on the EFSA classification [106] are included: confectionery (including chocolate), sugar and other sweetening ingredients (including dairy plant-base alternatives with added sugars), water-based sweet desserts, fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates and home-made), marmalade and jams, fine bakery wares, sugar-sweetened beverages, artificial-sweetened beverages, energy drinks and beverages concentrates, water based beverages and spoonable desserts and ice creams, savoury snacks (potato crisps, chips, salted nuts, savoury-flavoured crackers...) and other UPFs or HFSS foods. These food categories should be considered non-essential for a healthy and sustainable diet and should only be consumed occasionally³ and in small quantities.

³ *Occasional consumption*: refers to the infrequent or limited intake of certain foods and/or beverages, typically on special occasions and in moderation. This implies that the item should not be consumed weekly or frequently, but rather at irregular intervals (more or less every two weeks), ensuring a balanced and healthy diet [214,259].

Processed meat is defined by World Cancer Research Fund (WCRF) as “*meat that has been modified through methods such as salting, curing, fermentation, smoking, or other processes to enhance flavor or preservation*” [260]. In the analyzed FBDGs, there is no consensus on the inclusion or exclusion from other food groups of processed meat, due to the lack of a specific recommendation or its categorization together with red meat. Given its relation to the increase of NCDs [261,262] and its classification in Group 1 of cancerogenic substances for humans by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) [263], distinguishing these foods from unprocessed meat products is deemed necessary. According to the EFSA classification, this group should include both chicken, turkey, pork, lamb, beef cooked (e.g., pastrami, cooked pork ham, sausages, etc.) and raw (e.g., bacon, pancetta, ham, speck, etc.) cured or seasoned meats [106]. These products should be limited in consumption, eaten occasionally and in small quantities to prevent potential health risks associated with their intake.

Additionally, it is strongly recommended to limit the consumption of added sugars and salt, as excessive intake of these nutrients is associated with an increased risk of NCDs such as obesity, hypertension, and cardiovascular diseases [214]. On the one hand, high sugar intake contributes to metabolic disorders, including insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes [264], on the other hand, excessive salt consumption is highly linked to elevated risk of hypertension, which is a major contributor for cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases [265]. Reducing these ingredients in the diet can help promote overall health and well-being by decreasing the risk of these preventable conditions.

FOOD GROUP TO AVOID

Regular and/or excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages is strongly associated with an increased risk of NCDs, including liver disease, cardiovascular diseases, different types of cancers, and mental health disorders, with 2.6 million deaths that were attributable to alcohol consumption in 2019 (2 million were among men and 0.6 million among women) [266]. Similarly to processed meat, the IARC has classified alcohol as a Group 1 carcinogen, providing sufficient evidence of its capacity of increasing the risk of developing cancer in humans [267]. Its classification in the group “To avoid”, highlights the importance of avoiding alcoholic beverages to mitigate the negative health effect related to alcohol consumption. Based on the EFSA classification, the alcoholic beverages group should include wine and wine-like drinks, beer and beer-like beverages, unsweetened spirits and liqueurs, and general mixed alcoholic drinks. However alcoholic beverages should be avoided as part of a balanced dietary pattern. In fact, according to the latest statement from WHO [268], the protective effects previously attributed to some alcoholic beverages – such as red wine - have been found to be largely influenced by the type of sample used in trial studies and the presence of process biases. These factors lead to significant limitations in the evidence and call into question such protective claims. The approach taken in this framework is consistent with public health strategies aimed at reducing NCDs and promoting sustainable and healthy dietary guidelines.

Standardisation of Food Groups in European FBDGs

To harmonise dietary guidelines across Europe, a common structure for food groups is required.

Based on the analysis of national FBDGs available in the FAO repository, a standardised grouping has been proposed to ensure consistency, clarity, and scientific robustness.

The proposed classification divides food into three main categories:

- **Recommended food groups:** foods that form the basis of a healthy and sustainable diet (fruits and vegetables; fish, seafood, eggs, white and red meat, legumes and minimally processed plant-based alternatives; nuts and oilseeds; dairy and plant-based alternatives; grains, roots, and tubers; oils and fats; water)
- **Food groups to limit:** foods with poor nutritional quality that should be consumed only occasionally and in small quantities (discretionary foods; processed meat and added sugars and salt to reduce in cooking and seasoning)
- **Food groups to avoid:** alcoholic beverages, due to the absence of a safe level of consumption.

This standardisation aims to provide a clear and coherent framework that can be applied across EU countries, while still allowing national adaptations (e.g. culinary traditions and gastronomy; nutritional needs of specific population groups, etc.)

Definition and quantities of recommended foods

DEFINITION AND SCOPE

Once the scope to identify a terminology for dietary recommendations has been defined, the expression "**harmonised standard reference portion**" should be used as a common and shared definition, as suggested by Carruba et al. [95]

Regarding the definition of the harmonised standard reference portion, considering the work of Almiron-Roig and colleagues, the reference unit of consumption for health considerations has been identified as follows: the amount of food or drink recommended to be consumed as part of a healthy diet or as part of a therapeutic diet, that should be issued by government health professionals (e.g. nutrition/dietetic associations) or non-governmental health-promoting organisations [269]. Focusing on the concept that the reference unit of consumption provides a sufficient and appropriate amount of nutrient to achieve a healthy and balanced diet, a complete and clear definition has been identified.

QUANTITIES OF RECOMMENDED FOOD: HARMONISED STANDARD REFERENCE PORTION

To apply a methodology for standardizing **the reference portion**, the study of Salesse and colleagues was considered as a reference, being very recent and focusing on the European FBDGs. The research team identified different food groups (Fruits, Vegetables, Cooked Grains/Cereals, Bread, Ready-to-Eat Breakfast Cereals, Potatoes/Starchy Vegetables, Milk/Plant-Based Alternatives, Yogurt and Fermented Dairy, Cheese, Meat, Fish/Shellfish, Eggs, Legumes, Nuts and Seeds, Fats and Oils) for which the quantities of food recommended were collected and converted – when necessary- as described in the cited publication [74].

To provide a **harmonised standard reference portion** for each food category of the European countries, the median was applied to consider the central position of the portion size distribution, since this value, unlike the mean, is less influenced by extreme values. The median values were then rounded and are reported in Table 13.

The methodology of considering the median values was chosen according to the study of Eldrige et al [270], that had used the average of serving and portion sizes to find a Global Portion Value, identified as further good, standardized approach.

In addition to the median values, a margin of +/- 10% around the median was applied to provide a more comprehensive and adaptable overview on how the amount of food may vary across different countries (Table 14).

For Water to drink, the standardization was applied using the number of glasses per day more represented in the FBDGs that include it as a category, generally corresponding to 6-8 glasses (not shown in the table). Moreover, the study of Salesse et al. allowed to identify the number of countries which include the recommended amounts of foods within the dietary guidelines [74]. The findings emphasized that quantitative recommendations were less frequently reported for 'Breakfast cereals', 'Nuts and seeds' (that in this framework was specified as 'Nuts and oilseeds' to avoid confusion with other type of seeds) and 'Oils and fats'.

The portion standardization proposed here can be one of the methodologies that may be used at European level to try to develop harmonized dietary guidelines, that have at the same time the potential to be adapted to different national contexts. In addition, these results could be a relevant point to pan European public health policies to base on future updates.

For this reason, considering the importance of a varied and balanced diet, it is suggested that all food groups included in this framework as recommended, should also have the harmonised standard reference portion. Therefore, the adaptation of the standard reference portion should consider:

- local consumption patterns;
- food traditions, recipes and gastronomy;
- different cultural situations (e.g. when there is not a standard portion for a specific food, the most similar food in term of nutrient composition should be considered);
- availability of products on the market (e.g. ready meals, UPFs);
- the nutritional requirements of subgroups (e.g. pregnant women, lactating women, elderly groups).

This adaptation should be achieved by using the frequency of consumption and considering 2000 Kcal as the standard daily energy intake, according to the Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers that identifies this energy reference as that belonging to the median request of an adult [271]. This adaptation methodology will allow each country to identify the quantities to add into the dietary guidelines with the possibility of identifying reference as 'half of the standard portion' or 'one standard portion and three quarters'. The adaptation process may include the option on adding specific example of equivalence (e.g. Eggs 50g, corresponding to 1 egg) according to what could be easier to understand depending on different contexts.

As previously stated, recommended portion size should be always included in the FBDGs as a part to which rely on for technical reasons.

Table 13. Quantities (grams) of harmonised standard reference portion and the range (+/- 10%) found for each food category analysed. In the first column, the corresponding food group to each food category for which a standard reference was identified, is reported.

Food group	Food category	Number of countries indicating the portion	Harmonised standard reference portion Median (g)	Min 10% (g)	Max 10% (g)
Fruit and vegetables	Fresh fruits	29	120	108	132
	Fresh vegetables (raw)	27	100	90	110
Grain products, roots and tubers	Cereals and (rice, pasta raw)	21	90	81	99
	Bread	20	50	45	55
	Ready-to-eat breakfast cereals	11	30	27	33
	Potatoes, starchy vegetables	17	140	126	154
Nuts and oilseeds	Nuts and oilseeds	14	25	23	28
Oils and fats	Oils and fats	13	10	9	11
Dairy products	Milk / plant-based alternatives	25	220	198	242

	Yogurts and other fermented dairy	21	170	153	187
	Cheese	25	50	45	55
Fish and seafood, meat (white and red), eggs, pulses and other plant- based alternatives	Meat	20	100	90	110
	Fish / shellfish	24	120	108	132
	Eggs	18	50	45	55
	Pulses (cooked) Pulses (dried)*	21 -	125 50	113 -	140 -

*the dried quantities are provided through the application of the conversion ratio/factor of 2.5 [272].

Definition and quantities of recommended foods

The 'harmonised standard reference portion' should be used as a common and shared definition regarding dietary recommendations.

A 'harmonised standard reference portion' was proposed for each food category in European countries, calculated by taking the median of the portion size distribution.

The proposed standardisation of portions could be one of the methodologies used at a European level to develop harmonised dietary guidelines that can be adapted to different national contexts.

Considering the importance of a varied and balanced diet, it is recommended that all food groups included in this framework as recommended, should also have the harmonised standard reference portion that, adapted as follows:

- local consumption patterns;
- food traditions, recipes and gastronomy;
- different cultural situations (e.g. when there is not a standard portion for a specific food, the most similar food in term of nutrient composition should be considered);
- availability of products on the market (e.g. ready meals, UPFs);
- the nutritional requirements of subgroups (e.g. pregnant women, lactating women, elderly groups).

this adaptation should be achieved by using the frequency of consumption and considering 2000 kcal as the standard daily energy intake, according to Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers.

Communication strategy

Based on the analysis of gaps of the present work and on a shared recognition that an effective communication and dissemination of FBDGs is still lacking [124], a strategic communication plan has been developed and directly incorporated into the framework. This plan aims to address the identified weaknesses by providing clear and easy-to-understand recommendations and utilizing diverse communication channels to ensure broader reach and impact. It also considers the need for tailoring messages to different target audiences (from young population to elderly people), enhancing accessibility, and promoting better understanding and engagement with the guidelines.

References

1. Amorim, A.; Barbosa, A.D.H.; Sobral, P.J.D.A. Hunger, Obesity, Public Policies, and Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: A Reflection Considering the Socio-Environmental World Context. *Front. Nutr.* **2022**, *8*, 805569, doi:10.3389/fnut.2021.805569.
2. European Commission https://health.ec.europa.eu/non-communicable-diseases/overview_en.
3. European Commission Healthy Life Years Statistics. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Healthy_life_years_statistics.
4. European Commission EU Life Expectancy. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/Ddn-20240503-2>.
5. Prentice, A.M. The Triple Burden of Malnutrition in the Era of Globalization. In *Nestlé Nutrition Institute Workshop Series*; Rogacion, J.M., Ed.; S. Karger AG, 2023; Vol. 97, pp. 51–61 ISBN 978-3-318-07169-6.
6. Clemente-Suárez, V.J.; Beltrán-Velasco, A.I.; Redondo-Flórez, L.; Martín-Rodríguez, A.; Tornero-Aguilera, J.F. Global Impacts of Western Diet and Its Effects on Metabolism and Health: A Narrative Review. *Nutrients* **2023**, *15*, 2749, doi:10.3390/nu15122749.
7. Afshin, A.; Sur, P.J.; Fay, K.A.; Cornaby, L.; Ferrara, G.; Salama, J.S.; Mullany, E.C.; Abate, K.H.; Abbafati, C.; Abebe, Z.; et al. Health Effects of Dietary Risks in 195 Countries, 1990–2017: A Systematic Analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *The Lancet* **2019**, *393*, 1958–1972, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30041-8.
8. Willett, W.C.; Stampfer, M.J. Current Evidence on Healthy Eating. *Annu. Rev. Public Health* **2013**, *34*, 77–95, doi:10.1146/annurev-publhealth-031811-124646.
9. Cordova, R.; Viallon, V.; Fontvieille, E.; Peruchet-Noray, L.; Jansana, A.; Wagner, K.-H.; Kyrø, C.; Tjønneland, A.; Katzke, V.; Bajracharya, R.; et al. Consumption of Ultra-Processed Foods and Risk of Multimorbidity of Cancer and Cardiometabolic Diseases: A Multinational Cohort Study. *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* **2023**, *35*, 100771, doi:10.1016/j.lanep.2023.100771.
10. Derqui, B.; Fernandez, V.; Fayos, T. Towards More Sustainable Food Systems. Addressing Food Waste at School Canteens. *Appetite* **2018**, *129*, 1–11, doi:10.1016/j.appet.2018.06.022.
11. Tukker, A.; Jansen, B. Environmental Impacts of Products: A Detailed Review of Studies. *J of Industrial Ecology* **2006**, *10*, 159–182, doi:10.1162/jiec.2006.10.3.159.
12. Tukker, A.; Goldbohm, R.A.; De Koning, A.; Verheijden, M.; Kleijn, R.; Wolf, O.; Pérez-Domínguez, I.; Rueda-Cantucho, J.M. Environmental Impacts of Changes to Healthier Diets in Europe. *Ecological Economics* **2011**, *70*, 1776–1788, doi:10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.05.001.
13. The ESTO network Environmental Impact of Products (EIPRO) Analysis of the Life Cycle Environmental Impacts Related to the Final Consumption of the EU-25. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3b4b06b7-4bc0-4350-a20b-accdc70d1d94/language-en> 2006.
14. Notarnicola, B.; Tassielli, G.; Renzulli, P.A.; Castellani, V.; Sala, S. Environmental Impacts of Food Consumption in Europe. *Journal of Cleaner Production* **2017**, *140*, 753–765, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.080.
15. Global Nutrition Report. Country Profile. <https://globalnutritionreport.org/resources/nutrition-profiles/>.
16. Global Nutrition Report 2021 Global Nutrition Report: The State of Global Nutrition. Bristol, UK: Development Initiatives. ISBN: 978-1-8381530-4-5.
17. Billen, G.; Aguilera, E.; Einarsson, R.; Garnier, J.; Gingrich, S.; Grizzetti, B.; Lassaletta, L.; Le Noë, J.; Sanz-Cobena, A. Reshaping the European Agro-Food System and Closing Its Nitrogen Cycle: The Potential of Combining Dietary Change, Agroecology, and Circularity. *One Earth* **2021**, *4*, 839–850, doi:10.1016/j.oneear.2021.05.008.
18. Viroli, G.; Kallmpourtzidou, A.; Cena, H. Exploring Benefits and Barriers of Plant-Based Diets: Health, Environmental Impact, Food Accessibility and Acceptability. *Nutrients* **2023**, *15*, 4723, doi:10.3390/nu15224723.
19. Eurostat Food Waste and Food Waste Prevention - Estimates. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Food_waste_and_food_waste_prevention_-_estimates 2022.

20. Carrillo-Álvarez, E.; Salinas-Roca, B.; Costa-Tutusaus, L.; Milà-Villaruel, R.; Shankar Krishnan, N. The Measurement of Food Insecurity in High-Income Countries: A Scoping Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* **2021**, *18*, 9829, doi:10.3390/ijerph18189829.
21. Leydon, C.L.; Leonard, U.M.; McCarthy, S.N.; Harrington, J.M. Aligning Environmental Sustainability, Health Outcomes, and Affordability in Diet Quality: A Systematic Review. *Advances in Nutrition* **2023**, *14*, 1270–1296, doi:10.1016/j.advnut.2023.07.007.
22. EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products, Nutrition, and Allergies (NDA) Scientific Opinion on Establishing Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *EFSA* **2010**, *8*, doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1460.
23. Fabri, R.K.; Martinelli, S.S.; Perito, M.A.; Fantini, A.; Cavalli, S.B. Absence of Symbolic and Sustainable Aspects in Recommendations for Healthy Eating: A Qualitative Analysis of Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Rev. Nutr.* **2021**, *34*, e200120, doi:10.1590/1678-9865202134e200120.
24. Dooren, C.V.; Loken, B.; Lang, T.; Meltzer, H.M.; Halevy, S.; Neven, L.; Rubens, K.; Seves-Santman, M.; Trolle, E. The Planet on Our Plates: Approaches to Incorporate Environmental Sustainability within Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Front. Nutr.* **2024**, *11*, 1223814, doi:10.3389/fnut.2024.1223814.
25. FAO Food System-Based Dietary Guidelines. An Overview. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/48b09e6f-bfee-4b80-a2d5-c24440c6d4a8> 2024.
26. Guyatt, G.H.; Oxman, A.D.; Vist, G.E.; Kunz, R.; Falck-Ytter, Y.; Alonso-Coello, P.; Schünemann, H.J. GRADE: An Emerging Consensus on Rating Quality of Evidence and Strength of Recommendations. *BMJ* **2008**, *336*, 924–926, doi:10.1136/bmj.39489.470347.AD.
27. Harbour, R.; Miller, J. A New System for Grading Recommendations in Evidence Based Guidelines. *BMJ* **2001**, *323*, 334–336, doi:10.1136/bmj.323.7308.334.
28. Tobias, D.K.; Wittenbecher, C.; Hu, F.B. Grading Nutrition Evidence: Where to Go from Here? *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **2021**, *113*, 1385–1387, doi:10.1093/ajcn/nqab124.
29. Erratum for Schwingshackl et al. Perspective: NutriGrade: A Scoring System to Assess and Judge the Meta-Evidence of Randomized Controlled Trials and Cohort Studies in Nutrition Research. *Adv Nutr* 2016;7:994–1004. *Advances in Nutrition* **2017**, *8*, 399, doi:10.3945/an.117.015206.
30. World Health Organization *Preparation and Use of Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: Report of a Joint FAO/WHO Consultation*; WHO Technical Report Series; WHO: Geneva, 1998; ISBN 978-92-4-120880-2.
31. Nordic Council of Ministers Nordic Nutrition Recommendations. <https://www.norden.org/en/publication/nordic-nutrition-recommendations-2023> 2023.
32. FAO Dietary Guidelines. <https://www.fao.org/nutrition/education/food-dietary-guidelines/en/>.
33. Gazan, R.; Brouzes, C.M.C.; Vieux, F.; Maillot, M.; Lluch, A.; Darmon, N. Mathematical Optimization to Explore Tomorrow's Sustainable Diets: A Narrative Review. *Advances in Nutrition* **2018**, *9*, 602–616, doi:10.1093/advances/nmy049.
34. Perignon, M.; Darmon, N. Advantages and Limitations of the Methodological Approaches Used to Study Dietary Shifts towards Improved Nutrition and Sustainability. *Nutrition Reviews* **2022**, *80*, 579–597, doi:10.1093/nutrit/nuab091.
35. Ferrari, M.; Benvenuti, L.; Rossi, L.; De Santis, A.; Sette, S.; Martone, D.; Piccinelli, R.; Le Donne, C.; Leclercq, C.; Turrini, A. Could Dietary Goals and Climate Change Mitigation Be Achieved Through Optimized Diet? The Experience of Modeling the National Food Consumption Data in Italy. *Front. Nutr.* **2020**, *7*, 48, doi:10.3389/fnut.2020.00048.
36. Perignon, M.; Masset, G.; Ferrari, G.; Barré, T.; Vieux, F.; Maillot, M.; Amiot, M.-J.; Darmon, N. How Low Can Dietary Greenhouse Gas Emissions Be Reduced without Impairing Nutritional Adequacy, Affordability and Acceptability of the Diet? A Modelling Study to Guide Sustainable Food Choices. *Public Health Nutr.* **2016**, *19*, 2662–2674, doi:10.1017/S1368980016000653.
37. Macdiarmid, J.I.; Kyle, J.; Horgan, G.W.; Loe, J.; Fyfe, C.; Johnstone, A.; McNeill, G. Sustainable Diets for the Future: Can We Contribute to Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions by Eating a Healthy Diet? *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **2012**, *96*, 632–639, doi:10.3945/ajcn.112.038729.
38. Vieux, F.; Perignon, M.; Gazan, R.; Darmon, N. Dietary Changes Needed to Improve Diet Sustainability: Are They Similar across Europe? *Eur J Clin Nutr* **2018**, *72*, 951–960, doi:10.1038/s41430-017-0080-z.

39. Mertens, E.; Van'T Veer, P.; Hiddink, G.J.; Steijns, J.M.; Kuijsten, A. Operationalising the Health Aspects of Sustainable Diets: A Review. *Public Health Nutr.* **2017**, *20*, 739–757, doi:10.1017/S1368980016002664.
40. Ferguson, E.L.; Darmon, N.; Briend, A.; Premachandra, I.M. Food-Based Dietary Guidelines Can Be Developed and Tested Using Linear Programming Analysis. *The Journal of Nutrition* **2004**, *134*, 951–957, doi:10.1093/jn/134.4.951.
41. Maillot, M.; Vieux, F.; Amiot, M.J.; Darmon, N. Individual Diet Modeling Translates Nutrient Recommendations into Realistic and Individual-Specific Food Choices. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **2010**, *91*, 421–430, doi:10.3945/ajcn.2009.28426.
42. Horgan, G.W.; Perrin, A.; Whybrow, S.; Macdiarmid, J.I. Achieving Dietary Recommendations and Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions: Modelling Diets to Minimise the Change from Current Intakes. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act* **2016**, *13*, 46, doi:10.1186/s12966-016-0370-1.
43. MS Nutrition MS Nutrition. Available Online at: <https://Ms-Nutrition.Com/En/Presentation/>.
44. Schäfer, A.C.; Boeing, H.; Conrad, J.; Watzl, B. Wissenschaftliche Grundlagen der lebensmittelbezogenen Ernährungsempfehlungen für Deutschland. *Ernährungs Umschau* **2024**, *71*, 158–166, doi:10.4455/eu.2024.009.
45. Schäfer, A.C.; Boeing, H.; Gazan, R.; Conrad, J.; Gedrich, K.; Breidenassel, C.; Hauner, H.; Kroke, A.; Linseisen, J.; Lorkowski, S.; et al. A Methodological Framework for Deriving the German Food-Based Dietary Guidelines 2024: Food Groups, Nutrient Goals, and Objective Functions. Publisher: medRxiv. 2024.
46. Ippc Special Report. Global Warming of 1.5 °C. <https://www.ipcc.ch/Sr15/>.
47. Hwalla, N.; Deeb, N.; Naja, F.; Nasreddine, L. Developing Sustainable Food-Based Dietary Guidelines for Lebanon: Integrating Health, Economic Resilience, and Sustainability. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2025**, *9*, 1531273, doi:10.3389/fsufs.2025.1531273.
48. Brink, E.; Van Rossum, C.; Postma-Smeets, A.; Stafleu, A.; Wolvers, D.; Van Dooren, C.; Toxopeus, I.; Buurma-Rethans, E.; Geurts, M.; Ocké, M. Development of Healthy and Sustainable Food-Based Dietary Guidelines for the Netherlands. *Public Health Nutr.* **2019**, *22*, 2419–2435, doi:10.1017/S1368980019001435.
49. Lassen, A.D.; Christensen, L.M.; Trolle, E. Development of a Danish Adapted Healthy Plant-Based Diet Based on the EAT-Lancet Reference Diet. *Nutrients* **2020**, *12*, 738, doi:10.3390/nu12030738.
50. Mariotti, F.; Havard, S.; Morise, A.; Nadaud, P.; Sirot, V.; Wetzler, S.; Margaritis, I. Perspective: Modeling Healthy Eating Patterns for Food-Based Dietary Guidelines—Scientific Concepts, Methodological Processes, Limitations, and Lessons. *Advances in Nutrition* **2021**, *12*, 590–599, doi:10.1093/advances/nmaa176.
51. ANSES opinion Updating of the PNNS Guidelines: Revision of the Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. Available Online at: <https://www.anses.fr/en/system/files/NUT2012SA0103Ra-1EN.pdf> 2016.
52. Public Health England in association with the Welsh Government, Food Standards Scotland and the Food Standards Agency in Northern Ireland The Eatwell Guide. From Plate to Guide: What, Why and How for the Eatwell Model. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-eatwell-guide>.
53. Cobiac, L.J.; Scarborough, P.; Kaur, A.; Rayner, M. The Eatwell Guide: Modelling the Health Implications of Incorporating New Sugar and Fibre Guidelines. *PLoS ONE* **2016**, *11*, e0167859, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0167859.
54. Scarborough, P.; Kaur, A.; Cobiac, L.; Owens, P.; Parlesak, A.; Sweeney, K.; Rayner, M. Eatwell Guide: Modelling the Dietary and Cost Implications of Incorporating New Sugar and Fibre Guidelines. *BMJ Open* **2016**, *6*, e013182, doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013182.
55. FAO and WHO *Sustainable Healthy Diets*; FAO and WHO, 2019; ISBN 978-92-5-131875-1.
56. James-Martin, G.; Baird, D.L.; Hendrie, G.A.; Bogard, J.; Anastasiou, K.; Brooker, P.G.; Wiggins, B.; Williams, G.; Herrero, M.; Lawrence, M.; et al. Environmental Sustainability in National Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: A Global Review. *The Lancet Planetary Health* **2022**, *6*, e977–e986, doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00246-7.
57. Martini, D.; Tucci, M.; Bradfield, J.; Di Giorgio, A.; Marino, M.; Del Bo', C.; Porrini, M.; Riso, P. Principles of Sustainable Healthy Diets in Worldwide Dietary Guidelines: Efforts So Far and Future Perspectives. *Nutrients* **2021**, *13*, 1827, doi:10.3390/nu13061827.

58. Meltzer, H.M.; Eneroth, H.; Erkkola, M.; Trolle, E.; Fantke, P.; Helenius, J.; Olesen, J.E.; Saarinen, M.; Maage, A.; Ydersbond, T.A. Challenges and Opportunities When Moving Food Production and Consumption toward Sustainable Diets in the Nordics: A Scoping Review for Nordic Nutrition Recommendations 2023. *Food & Nutrition Research* **2024**, *68*, doi:10.29219/fnr.v68.10489.
59. Rossi, L.; Ferrari, M.; Ghiselli, A. The Alignment of Recommendations of Dietary Guidelines with Sustainability Aspects: Lessons Learned from Italy's Example and Proposals for Future Development. *Nutrients* **2023**, *15*, 542, doi:10.3390/nu15030542.
60. Culliford, A.E.; Bradbury, J.; Medici, E.B. Improving Communication of the UK Sustainable Healthy Dietary Guidelines the Eatwell Guide: A Rapid Review. *Sustainability* **2023**, *15*, 6149, doi:10.3390/su15076149.
61. Teschner, R.; Ruppen, J.; Bornemann, B.; Emmenegger, R.; Sánchez, L.A. Mapping Sustainable Diets: A Comparison of Sustainability References in Dietary Guidelines of Swiss Food Governance Actors. *Sustainability* **2021**, *13*, 12076, doi:10.3390/su132112076.
62. Hendrie, G.A.; Rebuli, M.A.; James-Martin, G.; Baird, D.L.; Bogard, J.R.; Lawrence, A.S.; Ridoutt, B. Towards Healthier and More Sustainable Diets in the Australian Context: Comparison of Current Diets with the Australian Dietary Guidelines and the EAT-Lancet Planetary Health Diet. *BMC Public Health* **2022**, *22*, 1939, doi:10.1186/s12889-022-14252-z.
63. Wu, H.; MacDonald, G.K.; Galloway, J.N.; Geng, Y.; Liu, X.; Zhang, L.; Jiang, S. A New Dietary Guideline Balancing Sustainability and Nutrition for China's Rural and Urban Residents. *iScience* **2022**, *25*, 105048, doi:10.1016/j.isci.2022.105048.
64. Sobhani, S.R.; Edalati, S.; Eini-Zinab, H.; Kennedy, G.; Omidvar, N. A Comparative Analysis of Sustainability of the Usual Food Intakes of the Iranian Population, Iranian Food-Based Dietary Guidelines, and Optimized Dietary Models. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2022**, *6*, 838741, doi:10.3389/fsufs.2022.838741.
65. Willett, W.C.; Hu, F.B.; Rimm, E.B.; Stampfer, M.J. Building Better Guidelines for Healthy and Sustainable Diets. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **2021**, *114*, 401–404, doi:10.1093/ajcn/nqab079.
66. Cambeses-Franco, C.; González-García, S.; Feijoo, G.; Moreira, M.T. Driving Commitment to Sustainable Food Policies within the Framework of American and European Dietary Guidelines. *Science of The Total Environment* **2022**, *807*, 150894, doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150894.
67. Durazzo, A.; Camilli, E.; D'Addezio, L.; Le Donne, C.; Ferrari, M.; Marconi, S.; Marletta, L.; Mistura, L.; Piccinelli, R.; Scalvedi, M.L.; et al. Food Groups and Individual Foods: Nutritional Attributes and Dietary Importance. In *Reference Module in Food Science*; Elsevier, 2018; p. B9780081005965213371 ISBN 978-0-08-100596-5.
68. Emmett, P.M.; Jones, L.R.; Northstone, K.; Pounis, G.; Taylor, C.M. Collection and Management of Dietary Data. In *Analysis in Nutrition Research*; Elsevier, 2019; pp. 43–73 ISBN 978-0-12-814556-2.
69. Bechthold, A.; Boeing, H.; Tetens, I.; Schwingshackl, L.; Nöthlings, U. Perspective: Food-Based Dietary Guidelines in Europe—Scientific Concepts, Current Status, and Perspectives. *Advances in Nutrition* **2018**, *9*, 544–560, doi:10.1093/advances/nmy033.
70. Montagnese, C.; Santarpia, L.; Buonifacio, M.; Nardelli, A.; Caldara, A.R.; Silvestri, E.; Contaldo, F.; Pasanisi, F. European Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: A Comparison and Update. *Nutrition* **2015**, *31*, 908–915, doi:10.1016/j.nut.2015.01.002.
71. Monteiro, J.S.; Botelho, R.B.A.; Zandonadi, R.P.; Araujo, W.M.C. Is There a Convergence between the Food Classification Adopted by Food-Based Dietary Guidelines and Food Science and Technology? *Foods* **2023**, *12*, 3824, doi:10.3390/foods12203824.
72. T, E.; M, T.; Laar, J.; Van, A.; R, M.; R, S.; D, W.; Van, R.; H, V. Overview of Elements within National Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *EJNFS* **2017**, *6*, 172–227, doi:10.9734/EJNFS/2016/32645.
73. Cámara, M.; Giner, R.M.; González-Fandos, E.; López-García, E.; Mañes, J.; Portillo, M.P.; Rafecas, M.; Domínguez, L.; Martínez, J.A. Food-Based Dietary Guidelines around the World: A Comparative Analysis to Update AESAN Scientific Committee Dietary Recommendations. *Nutrients* **2021**, *13*, 3131, doi:10.3390/nu13093131.
74. Salesse, F.; Eldridge, A.L.; Mak, T.N.; Gibney, E.R. A Global Analysis of Portion Size Recommendations in Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Front. Nutr.* **2024**, *11*, 1476771, doi:10.3389/fnut.2024.1476771.

75. Herforth, A.; Arimond, M.; Álvarez-Sánchez, C.; Coates, J.; Christianson, K.; Muehlhoff, E. A Global Review of Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Advances in Nutrition* **2019**, *10*, 590–605, doi:10.1093/advances/nmy130.
76. Hughes, J.; Pearson, E.; Grafenauer, S. Legumes—A Comprehensive Exploration of Global Food-Based Dietary Guidelines and Consumption. *Nutrients* **2022**, *14*, 3080, doi:10.3390/nu14153080.
77. Kvist, K.; Laursen, A.S.D.; Overvad, K.; Jakobsen, M.U. Substitution of Milk with Whole-Fat Yogurt Products or Cheese Is Associated with a Lower Risk of Myocardial Infarction: The Danish Diet, Cancer and Health Cohort. *The Journal of Nutrition* **2020**, *150*, 1252–1258, doi:10.1093/jn/nxz337.
78. Sonestedt, E.; Wirfält, E.; Wallström, P.; Gullberg, B.; Orho-Melander, M.; Hedblad, B. Dairy Products and Its Association with Incidence of Cardiovascular Disease: The Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort. *Eur J Epidemiol* **2011**, *26*, 609–618, doi:10.1007/s10654-011-9589-y.
79. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA); Niforou, K.; Livaniou, A.; Ioannidou, S. FoodEx2 Maintenance 2023. *EFS3* **2024**, *21*, doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2024.EN-8813.
80. United Nations The 17 Goals Available online: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>.
81. Zlatevska, N.; Dubelaar, C.; Holden, S.S. Sizing up the Effect of Portion Size on Consumption: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Marketing* **2014**, *78*, 140–154, doi:10.1509/jm.12.0303.
82. Livingstone, M.B.E.; Pourshahidi, L.K. Portion Size and Obesity. *Advances in Nutrition* **2014**, *5*, 829–834, doi:10.3945/an.114.007104.
83. Fileh, S.; González Gil, E.; Miguel-berges, M.L.; Moreno Aznar, L.A. Food Portion Sizes, Obesity, and Related Metabolic Complications in Children and Adolescents. *Nutr Hosp* **2020**, doi:10.20960/nh.03118.
84. Steenhuis, I.H.; Vermeer, W.M. Portion Size: Review and Framework for Interventions. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act* **2009**, *6*, 58, doi:10.1186/1479-5868-6-58.
85. Meijer, G.W.; Grunert, K.G.; Lähteenmäki, L. Supporting Consumers' Informed Food Choices: Sources, Channels, and Use of Information. In *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research*; Elsevier, 2023; Vol. 104, pp. 229–257 ISBN 978-0-443-19302-6.
86. Hackett, R.M. The IGD Industry Nutrition Strategy Group Report – Portion Size: A Review of Existing Approaches. *Nutrition Bulletin* **2009**, *34*, 210–213, doi:10.1111/j.1467-3010.2009.01748.x.
87. BDA. The Association of UK Dietitians Portion Size. <https://www.bda.uk.com/resource/food-facts-portion-sizes.html>.
88. USDA Dietary Guidelines for Americans. 2020–2025. https://www.dietaryguidelines.gov/sites/default/files/2020-12/Dietary_Guidelines_for_Americans_2020-2025.pdf.
89. American Heart Association Portion Size Versus Serving Size. <https://www.heart.org/en/healthy-living/healthy-eating/eat-smart/nutrition-basics/portion-size-versus-serving-size>.
90. CIAA Portion Sizes For Purposes of Nutrition Labelling. <https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Brochure-on-Portion-Sizes-for-the-Purposes-of-Nutrition-Labeling.pdf>.
91. FoodDrinkEurope Portion Guidance. https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/07157_2-Portion-Guidance.pdf.
92. Kliemann, N.; Kraemer, M.; Scapin, T.; Rodrigues, V.; Fernandes, A.; Bernardo, G.; Uggioni, P.; Proença, R. Serving Size and Nutrition Labelling: Implications for Nutrition Information and Nutrition Claims on Packaged Foods. *Nutrients* **2018**, *10*, 891, doi:10.3390/nu10070891.
93. Faulkner, G.P.; Pourshahidi, L.K.; Wallace, J.M.W.; Kerr, M.A.; McCrorie, T.A.; Livingstone, M.B.E. Serving Size Guidance for Consumers: Is It Effective? *Proc. Nutr. Soc.* **2012**, *71*, 610–621, doi:10.1017/S0029665112000766.
94. Lewis, H.B.; Ahern, A.L.; Jebb, S.A. How Much Should I Eat? A Comparison of Suggested Portion Sizes in the UK. *Public Health Nutr.* **2012**, *15*, 2110–2117, doi:10.1017/S1368980012001097.
95. Carruba, M.O.; Ragni, M.; Ruocco, C.; Aliverti, S.; Silano, M.; Amico, A.; Vaccaro, C.M.; Marangoni, F.; Valerio, A.; Poli, A.; et al. Role of Portion Size in the Context of a Healthy, Balanced Diet: A Case Study of European Countries. *IJERPH* **2023**, *20*, 5230, doi:10.3390/ijerph20065230.
96. Pellegrini, B.; Grant, F.; Chehade, L.; Del Bo', C.; Riso, P.; Martini, D.; Rossi, L. Serving Size and Consumption Frequencies in Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: A Global Scoping Review. *Food Research International* **2026**, *236*, 119225, doi:10.1016/j.foodres.2026.119225.

97. Strid, A.; Hallström, E.; Lindroos, A.K.; Lindahl, B.; Johansson, I.; Winkvist, A. Adherence to the Swedish Dietary Guidelines and the Impact on Mortality and Climate in a Population-Based Cohort Study. *Public Health Nutr.* **2023**, *26*, 2333–2342, doi:10.1017/S1368980023001295.
98. Kehoe, L.; Buffini, M.; McNulty, B.A.; Kearney, J.M.; Flynn, A.; Walton, J. Food and Nutrient Intakes and Compliance with Recommendations in School-Aged Children in Ireland: Findings from the National Children's Food Survey II (2017–2018) and Changes since 2003–2004. *Br J Nutr* **2023**, *129*, 2011–2024, doi:10.1017/S0007114522002781.
99. Alkerwi, A.; Sauvageot, N.; Nau, A.; Lair, M.-L.; Donneau, A.-F.; Albert, A.; Guillaume, M. Population Compliance with National Dietary Recommendations and Its Determinants: Findings from the ORISCAV-LUX Study. *Br J Nutr* **2012**, *108*, 2083–2092, doi:10.1017/S0007114512000232.
100. Scalvedi, M.L.; Gennaro, L.; Saba, A.; Rossi, L. Relationship Between Nutrition Knowledge and Dietary Intake: An Assessment Among a Sample of Italian Adults. *Front. Nutr.* **2021**, *8*, 714493, doi:10.3389/fnut.2021.714493.
101. Stroebele-Benschop, N.; Dieze, A.; Hilzendegen, C. Students' Adherence to Dietary Recommendations and Their Food Consumption Habits. *Nutr Health* **2018**, *24*, 75–81, doi:10.1177/0260106018772946.
102. Totland, T.H.; Øvrethø, B.; Brantsæter, A.L.; Holvik, K.; Bere, E.T.; Torheim, L.E.; Abel, M.H. Development and Evaluation of an Index Assessing Adherence to the Norwegian Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: The Norwegian Dietary Guideline Index (NDGI). *BMC Nutr* **2024**, *10*, 94, doi:10.1186/s40795-024-00900-7.
103. Ramón-Arбуés, E.; Granada-López, J.-M.; Martínez-Abadía, B.; Echániz-Serrano, E.; Antón-Solanas, I.; Jerue, B.A. Factors Related to Diet Quality: A Cross-Sectional Study of 1055 University Students. *Nutrients* **2021**, *13*, 3512, doi:10.3390/nu13103512.
104. Georgiou, A.; Androutsos, O.; Chouliaras, G.; Charmandari, E. Do Children and Adolescents with Overweight or Obesity Adhere to the National Food-Based Dietary Guidelines in Greece? *Children* **2022**, *9*, 256, doi:10.3390/children9020256.
105. European Food Safety Authority Guidance on the EU Menu Methodology. *EFS2* **2014**, *12*, doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3944.
106. EFSA - European Food Safety Authority The EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption-data> 2024.
107. Grant, F.; Rossi, L. The Italian Observatory on Food Surplus, Recovery, and Waste: The Development Process and Future Achievements. *Front. Nutr.* **2022**, *8*, 787982, doi:10.3389/fnut.2021.787982.
108. Grant, F.; Rossi, L. Sustainable Choices: The Relationship between Adherence to the Dietary Guidelines and Food Waste Behaviors in Italian Families. *Front. Nutr.* **2022**, *9*, 1026829, doi:10.3389/fnut.2022.1026829.
109. Chaltiel, D.; Adjibade, M.; Deschamps, V.; Touvier, M.; Hercberg, S.; Julia, C.; Kesse-Guyot, E. Programme National Nutrition Santé – Guidelines Score 2 (PNNS-GS2): Development and Validation of a Diet Quality Score Reflecting the 2017 French Dietary Guidelines. *Br J Nutr* **2019**, *122*, 331–342, doi:10.1017/S0007114519001181.
110. Estaquio, C.; Kesse-Guyot, E.; Deschamps, V.; Bertrais, S.; Dauchet, L.; Galan, P.; Hercberg, S.; Castetbon, K. Adherence to the French Programme National Nutrition Santé Guideline Score Is Associated with Better Nutrient Intake and Nutritional Status. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association* **2009**, *109*, 1031–1041, doi:10.1016/j.jada.2009.03.012.
111. Looman, M.; Feskens, E.J.; De Rijk, M.; Meijboom, S.; Biesbroek, S.; Temme, E.H.; De Vries, J.; Geelen, A. Development and Evaluation of the Dutch Healthy Diet Index 2015. *Public Health Nutr.* **2017**, *20*, 2289–2299, doi:10.1017/S136898001700091X.
112. USDA Healthy Eating Index. <https://www.fns.usda.gov/cnpp/healthy-eating-index-hei>.
113. Shams-White, M.M.; Pannucci, T.E.; Lerman, J.L.; Herrick, K.A.; Zimmer, M.; Meyers Mathieu, K.; Stoody, E.E.; Reedy, J. Healthy Eating Index-2020: Review and Update Process to Reflect the Dietary Guidelines for Americans, 2020-2025. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics* **2023**, *123*, 1280–1288, doi:10.1016/j.jand.2023.05.015.

114. McNaughton, S.A.; Ball, K.; Crawford, D.; Mishra, G.D. An Index of Diet and Eating Patterns Is a Valid Measure of Diet Quality in an Australian Population¹. *The Journal of Nutrition* **2008**, *138*, 86–93, doi:10.1093/jn/138.1.86.
115. Ward, S.J.; Coates, A.M.; Hill, A.M. Application of an Australian Dietary Guideline Index to Weighed Food Records. *Nutrients* **2019**, *11*, 1286, doi:10.3390/nu11061286.
116. Macdiarmid, J.I.; Loe, J.; Douglas, F.; Ludbrook, A.; Comerford, C.; McNeill, G. Developing a Timeline for Evaluating Public Health Nutrition Policy Interventions. What Are the Outcomes and When Should We Expect to See Them? *Public Health Nutr.* **2011**, *14*, 729–739, doi:10.1017/S1368980010002168.
117. Vidgen, H.A.; Gallegos, D. Defining Food Literacy and Its Components. *Appetite* **2014**, *76*, 50–59, doi:10.1016/j.appet.2014.01.010.
118. Cullen, T.; Hatch, J.; Martin, W.; Higgins, J.W.; Sheppard, R. Food Literacy: Definition and Framework for Action. *Canadian Journal of Dietetic Practice and Research* **2015**, *76*, 140–145, doi:10.3148/cjdpr-2015-010.
119. Amouzandeh, C.; Fingland, D.; Vidgen, H.A. A Scoping Review of the Validity, Reliability and Conceptual Alignment of Food Literacy Measures for Adults. *Nutrients* **2019**, *11*, 801, doi:10.3390/nu11040801.
120. WHO WHO Strategic Framework for Communication for Effective Communications. <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/documents/communicating-for-health/communication-framework.pdf>.
121. Tetens, I.; Birt, C.A.; Brink, E.; Bodenbach, S.; Bugel, S.; De Henauw, S.; Grønlund, T.; Julia, C.; Konde, Å.B.; Kromhout, D.; et al. Food-Based Dietary Guidelines – Development of a Conceptual Framework for Future Food-Based Dietary Guidelines in Europe: Report of a Federation of European Nutrition Societies Task-Force Workshop in Copenhagen, 12–13 March 2018. *Br J Nutr* **2020**, *124*, 1338–1344, doi:10.1017/S0007114520002469.
122. Yoong, S.L.; Turon, H.; Wong, C.K.; Bayles, L.; Finch, M.; Barnes, C.; Doherty, E.; Wolfenden, L. An Audit of the Dissemination Strategies and Plan Included in International Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Public Health Nutr.* **2023**, *26*, 2586–2594, doi:10.1017/S1368980023001714.
123. Brown, K.A.; Timotijevic, L.; Barnett, J.; Shepherd, R.; Lähteenmäki, L.; Raats, M.M. A Review of Consumer Awareness, Understanding and Use of Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Br J Nutr* **2011**, *106*, 15–26, doi:10.1017/S0007114511000250.
124. Wijesinha-Bettoni, R.; Khosravi, A.; Ramos, A.I.; Sherman, J.; Hernandez-Garbanzo, Y.; Molina, V.; Vargas, M.; Hachem, F. A Snapshot of Food-Based Dietary Guidelines Implementation in Selected Countries. *Global Food Security* **2021**, *29*, 100533, doi:10.1016/j.gfs.2021.100533.
125. Keller, I.; Lang, T. Food-Based Dietary Guidelines and Implementation: Lessons from Four Countries – Chile, Germany, New Zealand and South Africa. *Public Health Nutr.* **2008**, *11*, 867–874, doi:10.1017/S1368980007001115.
126. Miller, D.; Harkins, C. Corporate Strategy, Corporate Capture: Food and Alcohol Industry Lobbying and Public Health. *Critical Social Policy* **2010**, *30*, 564–589, doi:10.1177/0261018310376805.
127. Tselengidis, A.; Östergren, P.-O. Lobbying against Sugar Taxation in the European Union: Analysing the Lobbying Arguments and Tactics of Stakeholders in the Food and Drink Industries. *Scand J Public Health* **2019**, *47*, 565–575, doi:10.1177/1403494818787102.
128. Djojosoeparto, S.K.; Kamphuis, C.B.M.; Vandevijvere, S.; Murrin, C.; Stanley, I.; Romaniuk, P.; Harrington, J.M.; Poelman, M.P.; the PEN Consortium Strength of EU-Level Food Environment Policies and Priority Recommendations to Create Healthy Food Environments. *European Journal of Public Health* **2022**, *32*, 504–511, doi:10.1093/eurpub/ckac010.
129. Obesity Evidence Hub Countries That Have Taxes on Sugar-Sweetened Beverages (SSBs). <https://www.obesityevidencehub.org.au/collections/prevention/countries-that-have-implemented-taxes-on-sugar-sweetened-beverages-ssbs>.
130. Leme, A.C.B.; Hou, S.; Fisberg, R.M.; Fisberg, M.; Haines, J. Adherence to Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: A Systemic Review of High-Income and Low- and Middle-Income Countries. *Nutrients* **2021**, *13*, 1038, doi:10.3390/nu13031038.

131. Bublitz, M.G.; Peracchio, L.A.; Dadzie, C.A.; Escalas, J.E.; Hansen, J.; Hutton, M.; Nardini, G.; Absher, C.; Tangari, A.H. Food Access for All: Empowering Innovative Local Infrastructure. *Journal of Business Research* **2019**, *100*, 354–365, doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.12.027.
132. Penne, T.; Goedemé, T. Can Low-Income Households Afford a Healthy Diet? Insufficient Income as a Driver of Food Insecurity in Europe. *Food Policy* **2021**, *99*, 101978, doi:10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101978.
133. Vilar-Compte, M.; Burrola-Méndez, S.; Lozano-Marrufo, A.; Ferré-Eguiluz, I.; Flores, D.; Gaitán-Rossi, P.; Teruel, G.; Pérez-Escamilla, R. Urban Poverty and Nutrition Challenges Associated with Accessibility to a Healthy Diet: A Global Systematic Literature Review. *Int J Equity Health* **2021**, *20*, 40, doi:10.1186/s12939-020-01330-0.
134. Drewnowski, A.; Monterrosa, E.C.; De Pee, S.; Frongillo, E.A.; Vandevijvere, S. Shaping Physical, Economic, and Policy Components of the Food Environment to Create Sustainable Healthy Diets. *Food Nutr Bull* **2020**, *41*, 74S–86S, doi:10.1177/0379572120945904.
135. Metcalfe, J.J.; McCaffrey, J.; Schumacher, M.; Kownacki, C.; Prescott, M.P. Community-Based Nutrition Education and Hands-on Cooking Intervention Increases Farmers’ Market Use and Vegetable Servings. *Public Health Nutr.* **2022**, *25*, 2601–2613, doi:10.1017/S1368980022000660.
136. Smith, K.; Wells, R.; Hawkes, C. How Primary School Curriculums in 11 Countries around the World Deliver Food Education and Address Food Literacy: A Policy Analysis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* **2022**, *19*, 2019, doi:10.3390/ijerph19042019.
137. Vereecken, C.A.; Bobelijn, K.; Maes, L. School Food Policy at Primary and Secondary Schools in Belgium-Flanders: Does It Influence Young People’s Food Habits? *Eur J Clin Nutr* **2005**, *59*, 271–277, doi:10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602068.
138. Finkelstein, D.M.; Hill, E.L.; Whitaker, R.C. School Food Environments and Policies in US Public Schools. *Pediatrics* **2008**, *122*, e251–e259, doi:10.1542/peds.2007-2814.
139. França, F.C.O.D.; Andrade, I.D.S.; Zandonadi, R.P.; Sávio, K.E.; Akutsu, R.D.C.C.D.A. Food Environment around Schools: A Systematic Scope Review. *Nutrients* **2022**, *14*, 5090, doi:10.3390/nu14235090.
140. Hall, E.; Chai, W.; Albrecht, J.A. A Qualitative Phenomenological Exploration of Teachers’ Experience With Nutrition Education. *American Journal of Health Education* **2016**, *47*, 136–148, doi:10.1080/19325037.2016.1157532.
141. Nanayakkara, J.; Margerison, C.; Worsley, A. Ways to Improve Secondary School Teachers’ Confidence in Teaching Food and Nutrition Subjects. *Education Inquiry* **2024**, *15*, 407–422, doi:10.1080/20004508.2022.2116865.
142. Lafave, L.M.Z.; Hayek, J.; Webster, A.D.; McConnell, C. Creating Healthy Eating and Active Environments in Early Learning Settings: Protocol of the CHEERS eHealth Intervention Study. *Front. Nutr.* **2024**, *11*, 1337873, doi:10.3389/fnut.2024.1337873.
143. Lee, H.; Schafer, M. Are Positive Childhood Experiences Linked to Better Cognitive Functioning in Later Life?: Examining the Role of Life Course Pathways. *J Aging Health* **2021**, *33*, 217–226, doi:10.1177/0898264320972547.
144. Yoong, S.L.; Lum, M.; Wolfenden, L.; Jackson, J.; Barnes, C.; Hall, A.E.; McCrabb, S.; Pearson, N.; Lane, C.; Jones, J.Z.; et al. Healthy Eating Interventions Delivered in Early Childhood Education and Care Settings for Improving the Diet of Children Aged Six Months to Six Years. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* **2023**, 2023, doi:10.1002/14651858.CD013862.pub2.
145. Hingle, M.D.; O’Connor, T.M.; Dave, J.M.; Baranowski, T. Parental Involvement in Interventions to Improve Child Dietary Intake: A Systematic Review. *Preventive Medicine* **2010**, *51*, 103–111, doi:10.1016/j.ypmed.2010.04.014.
146. Kristjansdottir, A.G.; Johannsson, E.; Thorsdottir, I. Effects of a School-Based Intervention on Adherence of 7–9-Year-Olds to Food-Based Dietary Guidelines and Intake of Nutrients. *Public Health Nutr.* **2010**, *13*, 1151–1161, doi:10.1017/S1368980010000716.
147. FAO School-Based Food and Nutrition Education. <https://www.fao.org/school-food/areas-work/based-food-nutrition-education/en/>.
148. *The State of Food and Agriculture 2023*; FAO, 2023; ISBN 978-92-5-138167-0.
149. *The State of Food and Agriculture 2024*; FAO, 2024; ISBN 978-92-5-139140-2.

150. TEEB TEEB for Agriculture & Food: Scientific and Economic Foundations. Geneva: UN Environment. ISBN: 978-92-807-3702-8. 2018.
151. Hamm, M.W.; Riemer, O.; Ploetz, T. True Cost Accounting and Dietary Patterns: A Strategy for Transformative Food Systems. Available Online: <https://www.tmg-thinktank.com/publications/true-cost-accounting-and-dietary-patterns-a-strategy-for-transformative-food> 2021.
152. Hamm, M.W.; Mueller, A.; Riemer, O.; Merrigan, K. True Cost Accounting and Dietary Patterns: A Strategy for Transformative Food Systems. Working Paper. Available Online: https://assets.ctfassets.net/rirl83ijfda/1eELrfyuNxweD9dFb96IOV/73ae53d86f4f6941340d4f1d4a6fbb11/TCA_DietaryPatterns_web.Pdf 2019.
153. Raworth, K. Why It's Time for Doughnut Economics. *IPPR Progressive Review* **2017**, *24*, 216–222, doi:10.1111/newe.12058.
154. Eigenraam, M.; Jekums, A.; Mcleod, R.; Amerikanou, C.; Sharma, K. Applying the TEEBAGriFood Evaluation Framework: Overarching Implementation Guidance.
155. ISO 14040:2006 Environmental Management — Life Cycle Assessment — Principles and Framework.
156. Eigenraam, M.; Obst, C. APPLYING THE TEEBAGRIFOOD EVALUATION FRAMEWORK - Overarching Implementation Guidance. **2020**, doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.18280.70406.
157. Seidel, F.; Oebel, B.; Stein, L.; Michalke, A.; Gaugler, T. The True Price of External Health Effects from Food Consumption. *Nutrients* **2023**, *15*, 3386, doi:10.3390/nu15153386.
158. Springmann, M.; Clark, M.A.; Rayner, M.; Scarborough, P.; Webb, P. The Global and Regional Costs of Healthy and Sustainable Dietary Patterns: A Modelling Study. *The Lancet Planetary Health* **2021**, *5*, e797–e807, doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00251-5.
159. Heller, M.C.; Keoleian, G.A.; Willett, W.C. Toward a Life Cycle-Based, Diet-Level Framework for Food Environmental Impact and Nutritional Quality Assessment: A Critical Review. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2013**, *47*, 12632–12647, doi:10.1021/es4025113.
160. International Labour Office (ILO) Global Estimates of Child Labour: Results and Trends, 2012-2016. ISBN: 978-92-2-130153-0 2017.
161. International Labour Office (ILO) Agriculture: A Hazardous Work. Available Online at: <https://www.ilo.org/resource/agriculture-hazardous-work-0>.
162. de Bruyn, S.; De Vries, J.; Juijn, D.; Bijleveld, M.; van der Giesen, C.; Korteland, M.; van Santen, W.; Pápai, S. Handboek Milieuprijzen 2023 : Methodische Onderbouwing van Kengetallen Gebruikt Voor Waardering van Emissies En Milieu-Impacts (Version 1.0) 2023.
163. Huijbregts, M.A.J.; Steinmann, Z.J.N.; Elshout, P.M.F.; Stam, G.; Verones, F.; Vieira, M.; Zijp, M.; Hollander, A.; Van Zelm, R. ReCiPe2016: A Harmonised Life Cycle Impact Assessment Method at Midpoint and Endpoint Level. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* **2017**, *22*, 138–147, doi:10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y.
164. Scherer, L.; Tomasik, B.; Rueda, O.; Pfister, S. Framework for Integrating Animal Welfare into Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* **2018**, *23*, 1476–1490, doi:10.1007/s11367-017-1420-x.
165. Ecoinvent Database Available Online: <https://ecoinvent.org/the-ecoinvent-database/>.
166. AGRIBALYSE database Available Online: <https://doc.agribalyse.fr/documentation-en/agribalyse-data/data-access>.
167. European Commission. Joint Research Centre. *Understanding Product Environmental Footprint and Organisation Environmental Footprint Methods.*; Publications Office: LU, 2022;
168. FAOSTAT Available Online: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FBS>.
169. IFASTAT Available Online: <https://www.ifastat.org/consumption/fertilizer-use-by-crop>.
170. FAO AQUASTAT Available Online: <https://data.apps.fao.org/aquastat/?lang=en>.
171. Agri-footprint Available Online: <https://blonksustainability.nl/tools-and-databases/agri-footprint>.
172. ESU World Food LCA Database ESU-Services Ltd. – Fair Consulting in Sustainability 2023.
173. *Methods and Options to Monitor the Cost and Affordability of a Healthy Diet Globally*; FAO, 2022; ISBN 978-92-5-136690-5.
174. Capitals Coaliton TEEBAGriFood- Operational Guidelines for Business. <https://capitalscoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/TEEB-for-Agriculture-and-Food-Operational-Guidelines-for-Business.Pdf>.

175. True Price Foundation Monetisation Factors for True Pricing Version 3.0.0. <https://Trueprice.Org/Monetisation-Factors-for-True-Pricing/> 2023.
176. OECD Available Online: [https://Data-Explorer.Oecd.Org/Vis?Df\[Ds\]=DisseminateFinalDMZ&df\[Id\]=DSD_TIME_USE%40DF_TIME_USE&df\[A g\]=OECD.WISE.INE&dq=.._T&to\[TIME\]=false](https://Data-Explorer.Oecd.Org/Vis?Df[Ds]=DisseminateFinalDMZ&df[Id]=DSD_TIME_USE%40DF_TIME_USE&df[A g]=OECD.WISE.INE&dq=.._T&to[TIME]=false).
177. The True Cost Initiative True Cost Accounting Agrifood Handbook. Practical True Cost Accounting Guidelines for the Food and Farming Sector on Impact Measurement, Valuation and Reporting. <https://Tca2f.Org/>.
178. Food Systems Countdown Initiative Data (FSCI). <https://Www.Foodsystemsdashboard.Org/Indicators/Cross-Cutting-Issues/Governance/v-Dem-Accountability-Index/Map>.
179. Transparency International Corruption Perceptions Index. <https://Www.Transparency.Org/En/Cpi/2022>.
180. *Guidance for Implementation of Regulation (EU) No 649/2012 Concerning the Export and Import of Hazardous Chemicals*; European Chemicals Agency, Ed.; ECHA: Helsinki, 2014; ISBN 978-92-9244-893-6.
181. Harrison, M.R.; Palma, G.; Buendia, T.; Bueno-Tarodo, M.; Quell, D.; Hachem, F. A Scoping Review of Indicators for Sustainable Healthy Diets. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2022**, *5*, 822263, doi:10.3389/fsufs.2021.822263.
182. Frehner, A.; Zanten, H.H.E.V.; Schader, C.; Boer, I.J.M.D.; Pestoni, G.; Rohrmann, S.; Muller, A. How Food Choices Link Sociodemographic and Lifestyle Factors with Sustainability Impacts. *Journal of Cleaner Production* **2021**, *300*, 126896, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126896.
183. Turner, C.; Aggarwal, A.; Walls, H.; Herforth, A.; Drewnowski, A.; Coates, J.; Kalamatianou, S.; Kadiyala, S. Concepts and Critical Perspectives for Food Environment Research: A Global Framework with Implications for Action in Low- and Middle-Income Countries. *Global Food Security* **2018**, *18*, 93–101, doi:10.1016/j.gfs.2018.08.003.
184. Anker, R.; Anker, M. *Living Wages Around the World*; Edward Elgar Publishing, 2017; ISBN 978-1-78643-146-2.
185. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020. <https://Www.Lifecycleinitiative.Org/Library/Guidelines-for-Social-Life-Cycle-Assessment-of-Products-and-Organisations-2020/> 2020.
186. Social Hotspot Database Available Online: <http://Www.Socialhotspot.Org/>.
187. Eurostat Mean and Median Income by Household Type – EU-SLIC and ECHP Surveys. Available Online: https://Ec.Europa.Eu/Eurostat/Databrowser/View/Ilc_di04__custom_12943120/Default/Table?Lang=en 2024.
188. Barosh, L.; Friel, S.; Engelhardt, K.; Chan, L. The Cost of a Healthy and Sustainable Diet – Who Can Afford It? *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health* **2014**, *38*, 7–12, doi:10.1111/1753-6405.12158.
189. Hirvonen, K.; Bai, Y.; Headey, D.; Masters, W.A. Affordability of the EAT–Lancet Reference Diet: A Global Analysis. *The Lancet Global Health* **2020**, *8*, e59–e66, doi:10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30447-4.
190. *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2024*; FAO; IFAD; UNICEF; WFP; WHO, 2024; ISBN 978-92-5-138882-2.
191. Maister, K.; Di Noi, C.; Ciroth, A.; Srocka, M. PSILCA - Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment Database. https://Psilca.Net/Wp-Content/Uploads/2020/06/PSILCA_documentation_v3.Pdf.
192. Fitzpatrick, I.; Young, R.; Barbour, R.; Perry, M.; Rose, E.; Marshall, A. The Hidden Cost of UK Food 2019.
193. FreSH True Cost of Food: Unpacking the Value of Food System: FreSH Discussion Paper. <https://Archive.Wbcsd.Org/Programs/Food-and-Nature/Food-Land-Use/FreSH/Resources/Unpacking-the-Value-of-the-Food-System>.
194. Foreman, K.J.; Marquez, N.; Dolgert, A.; Fukutaki, K.; Fullman, N.; McGaughey, M.; Pletcher, M.A.; Smith, A.E.; Tang, K.; Yuan, C.-W.; et al. Forecasting Life Expectancy, Years of Life Lost, and All-Cause and Cause-Specific Mortality for 250 Causes of Death: Reference and Alternative Scenarios for 2016–

- 40 for 195 Countries and Territories. *The Lancet* **2018**, *392*, 2052–2090, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31694-5.
195. Lozano, R.; Naghavi, M.; Foreman, K.; Lim, S.; Shibuya, K.; Aboyans, V.; Abraham, J.; Adair, T.; Aggarwal, R.; Ahn, S.Y.; et al. Global and Regional Mortality from 235 Causes of Death for 20 Age Groups in 1990 and 2010: A Systematic Analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *The Lancet* **2012**, *380*, 2095–2128, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61728-0.
196. Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. GBD Compare. Available Online at: <https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-compare/>.
197. Eurostat Database on Population and Social Condition. Available Online at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>.
198. Wilkins, E., Wilson, L., Wickramasinghe, K., Bhatnagar, P., Leal, J., Luengo-Fernandez, R., Burns, R., Rayner, M., & Townsend, N. European Cardiovascular Disease Statistics 2017. <http://www.ehnheart.org/images/CVD-Statistics-Report-August-2017.pdf>.
199. Stegbauer, C.; Falivena, C.; Moreno, A.; Hentschel, A.; Rosenmöller, M.; Heise, T.; Szecsenyi, J.; Schliess, F. Costs and Its Drivers for Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 Patients in France and Germany: A Systematic Review of Economic Studies. *BMC Health Serv Res* **2020**, *20*, 1043, doi:10.1186/s12913-020-05897-w.
200. Hex, N.; Bartlett, C.; Wright, D.; Taylor, M.; Varley, D. Estimating the Current and Future Costs of Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes in the UK, Including Direct Health Costs and Indirect Societal and Productivity Costs. *Diabetic Medicine* **2012**, *29*, 855–862, doi:10.1111/j.1464-5491.2012.03698.x.
201. Charbonnel, B.; Simon, D.; Dallongeville, J.; Bureau, I.; Dejager, S.; Levy-Bachelot, L.; Gourmelen, J.; Detournay, B. Direct Medical Costs of Type 2 Diabetes in France: An Insurance Claims Database Analysis. *PharmacoEconomics Open* **2018**, *2*, 209–219, doi:10.1007/s41669-017-0050-3.
202. Baudot, F.-O.; Aguadé, A.-S.; Barnay, T.; Gastaldi-Ménager, C.; Fagot-Campagna, A. Impact of Type 2 Diabetes on Health Expenditure: Estimation Based on Individual Administrative Data. *Eur J Health Econ* **2019**, *20*, 657–668, doi:10.1007/s10198-018-1024-9.
203. Ulrich, S.; Holle, R.; Wacker, M.; Stark, R.; Icks, A.; Thorand, B.; Peters, A.; Laxy, M. Cost Burden of Type 2 Diabetes in Germany: Results from the Population-Based KORA Studies. *BMJ Open* **2016**, *6*, e012527, doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-012527.
204. Hofmarcher, T.; Lindgren, P.; Wilking, N.; Jönsson, B. The Cost of Cancer in Europe 2018. *European Journal of Cancer* **2020**, *129*, 41–49, doi:10.1016/j.ejca.2020.01.011.
205. Ecocosts Value Sustainability Impact Metrics. <https://www.ecocostsvalue.com/true-cost-accounting/social-capital-in-agriculture/>.
206. Bünger, B.; Matthey, A. Methodological Convention 3.1 for the Assessment of Environmental Costs - Value Factors Version 12/2020 2020.
207. Klapp, A.-L.; Feil, N.; Risius, A. A Global Analysis of National Dietary Guidelines on Plant-Based Diets and Substitutions for Animal-Based Foods. *Current Developments in Nutrition* **2022**, *6*, nzac144, doi:10.1093/cdn/nzac144.
208. Aune, D.; Giovannucci, E.; Boffetta, P.; Fadnes, L.T.; Keum, N.; Norat, T.; Greenwood, D.C.; Riboli, E.; Vatten, L.J.; Tonstad, S. Fruit and Vegetable Intake and the Risk of Cardiovascular Disease, Total Cancer and All-Cause Mortality—a Systematic Review and Dose-Response Meta-Analysis of Prospective Studies. *International Journal of Epidemiology* **2017**, *46*, 1029–1056, doi:10.1093/ije/dyw319.
209. Amerikanou, C.; Tzavara, C.; Kaliora, A.C. Dietary Patterns and Nutritional Value in Non-Communicable Diseases. *Nutrients* **2023**, *16*, 82, doi:10.3390/nu16010082.
210. Alamnia, T.T.; Sargent, G.M.; Kelly, M. Dietary Patterns and Associations with Metabolic Risk Factors for Non-Communicable Disease. *Sci Rep* **2023**, *13*, 21028, doi:10.1038/s41598-023-47548-0.
211. Kumar, A.; P, N.; Kumar, M.; Jose, A.; Tomer, V.; Oz, E.; Proestos, C.; Zeng, M.; Elobeid, T.; K, S.; et al. Major Phytochemicals: Recent Advances in Health Benefits and Extraction Method. *Molecules* **2023**, *28*, 887, doi:10.3390/molecules28020887.
212. Muscolo, A.; Mariateresa, O.; Giulio, T.; Mariateresa, R. Oxidative Stress: The Role of Antioxidant Phytochemicals in the Prevention and Treatment of Diseases. *IJMS* **2024**, *25*, 3264, doi:10.3390/ijms25063264.

213. Rodriguez-Casado, A. The Health Potential of Fruits and Vegetables Phytochemicals: Notable Examples. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* **2016**, *56*, 1097–1107, doi:10.1080/10408398.2012.755149.
214. WHO Healthy Diet. <https://www.who.int/initiatives/behealthy/healthy-diet>.
215. World Health Organization *Guideline: Sugars Intake for Adults and Children*; World Health Organization: Geneva, 2015; ISBN 978-92-4-154902-8.
216. Richter, C.; Fulgoni, K.; Fulgoni, V.L.; Johnson, B.; Kijek, M.; Mascalco, S.; Psota, T. Assessment of the Unique Nutrient Contribution of White Potatoes in the Diet and the Nutrient Implications of Replacing Refined and Whole Grains with Starchy Vegetables. *Front. Nutr.* **2025**, *12*, 1692564, doi:10.3389/fnut.2025.1692564.
217. Langan, S.; Yadava, P.; Khan, F.N.; Bhardwaj, R.; Tripathi, K.; Bhardwaj, V.; Bhardwaj, R.; Gautam, R.K.; Kumar, A. Nutritional and Food Composition Survey of Major Legumes Toward Healthy, Sustainable, and Biofortified Diets. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2022**, *6*, 878269, doi:10.3389/fsufs.2022.878269.
218. Huang, J.; Liao, L.M.; Weinstein, S.J.; Sinha, R.; Graubard, B.I.; Albanes, D. Association Between Plant and Animal Protein Intake and Overall and Cause-Specific Mortality. *JAMA Intern Med* **2020**, *180*, 1173, doi:10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.2790.
219. Lamberg-Allardt, C.; Bärebring, L.; Arnesen, E.K.; Nwaru, B.I.; Thorisdottir, B.; Ramel, A.; Söderlund, F.; Dierkes, J.; Åkesson, A. Animal versus Plant-Based Protein and Risk of Cardiovascular Disease and Type 2 Diabetes: A Systematic Review of Randomized Controlled Trials and Prospective Cohort Studies. *Food & Nutrition Research* **2023**, *67*, doi:10.29219/fnr.v67.9003.
220. Havemeier, S.; Erickson, J.; Slavin, J. Dietary Guidance for Legumes: The Challenge and Opportunity to Be Part of Both the Vegetable and Protein Food Groups. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* **2017**, *1392*, 58–66, doi:10.1111/nyas.13308.
221. Mariotti, F. Animal and Plant Protein Sources and Cardiometabolic Health. *Advances in Nutrition* **2019**, *10*, S351–S366, doi:10.1093/advances/nmy110.
222. Zheng, J.; Zhu, T.; Yang, G.; Zhao, L.; Li, F.; Park, Y.-M.; Tabung, F.K.; Steck, S.E.; Li, X.; Wang, H. The Isocaloric Substitution of Plant-Based and Animal-Based Protein in Relation to Aging-Related Health Outcomes: A Systematic Review. *Nutrients* **2022**, *14*, 272, doi:10.3390/nu14020272.
223. Agarwal, S.; Fulgoni, V.L. Effect of Adding Legumes to Replace Protein Foods and Refined Grains in Healthy Dietary Patterns. *Nutrients* **2023**, *15*, 4355, doi:10.3390/nu15204355.
224. Mariotti, F.; Gardner, C.D. Dietary Protein and Amino Acids in Vegetarian Diets—A Review. *Nutrients* **2019**, *11*, 2661, doi:10.3390/nu11112661.
225. Semba, R.D.; Ramsing, R.; Rahman, N.; Kraemer, K.; Bloem, M.W. Legumes as a Sustainable Source of Protein in Human Diets. *Global Food Security* **2021**, *28*, 100520, doi:10.1016/j.gfs.2021.100520.
226. Hertzler, S.R.; Lieblein-Boff, J.C.; Weiler, M.; Allgeier, C. Plant Proteins: Assessing Their Nutritional Quality and Effects on Health and Physical Function. *Nutrients* **2020**, *12*, 3704, doi:10.3390/nu12123704.
227. Young, V.; Pellett, P. Plant Proteins in Relation to Human Protein and Amino Acid Nutrition. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **1994**, *59*, 1203S–1212S, doi:10.1093/ajcn/59.5.1203S.
228. Onwezen, M.C.; Bouwman, E.P.; Reinders, M.J.; Dagevos, H. A Systematic Review on Consumer Acceptance of Alternative Proteins: Legumes, Algae, Insects, Plant-Based Meat Alternatives, and Cultured Meat. *Appetite* **2021**, *159*, 105058, doi:10.1016/j.appet.2020.105058.
229. Faber, I.; Henn, K.; Brugarolas, M.; Perez-Cueto, F.J. Relevant Characteristics of Food Products Based on Alternative Proteins According to European Consumers. *J Sci Food Agric* **2022**, *102*, 5034–5043, doi:10.1002/jsfa.11178.
230. gfi Plant-Based Retail Sales Data for Six European Countries: 2021-Early 2024. <https://gfieurope.org/plant-based-sales-data-2023/>.
231. Patrignani, F.; Siroli, L.; Serrazanetti, D.I.; Gardini, F.; Lanciotti, R. Innovative Strategies Based on the Use of Essential Oils and Their Components to Improve Safety, Shelf-Life and Quality of Minimally Processed Fruits and Vegetables. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **2015**, *46*, 311–319, doi:10.1016/j.tifs.2015.03.009.

232. Cellura, M.; Cusenza, M.A.; Longo, S.; Luu, L.Q.; Skurk, T. Life Cycle Environmental Impacts and Health Effects of Protein-Rich Food as Meat Alternatives: A Review. *Sustainability* **2022**, *14*, 979, doi:10.3390/su14020979.
233. Ritchie, H.; Rosado, P.; Roser, M. Environmental Impacts of Food Production. <https://ourworldindata.org/environmental-impacts-of-food>.
234. Gonçalves, B.; Pinto, T.; Aires, A.; Morais, M.C.; Bacelar, E.; Anjos, R.; Ferreira-Cardoso, J.; Oliveira, I.; Vilela, A.; Cosme, F. Composition of Nuts and Their Potential Health Benefits-An Overview. *Foods* **2023**, *12*, 942, doi:10.3390/foods12050942.
235. Walther, B.; Guggisberg, D.; Badertscher, R.; Egger, L.; Portmann, R.; Dubois, S.; Haldimann, M.; Kopf-Bolanz, K.; Rhyn, P.; Zoller, O.; et al. Comparison of Nutritional Composition between Plant-Based Drinks and Cow's Milk. *Front. Nutr.* **2022**, *9*, 988707, doi:10.3389/fnut.2022.988707.
236. Chen, G.-C.; Wang, Y.; Tong, X.; Szeto, I.M.Y.; Smit, G.; Li, Z.-N.; Qin, L.-Q. Cheese Consumption and Risk of Cardiovascular Disease: A Meta-Analysis of Prospective Studies. *Eur J Nutr* **2017**, *56*, 2565–2575, doi:10.1007/s00394-016-1292-z.
237. Sadeghi, M.; Khosravi-Boroujeni, H.; Sarrafzadegan, N.; Asgary, S.; Roohafza, H.; Gharipour, M.; Sajjadi, F.; Khalesi, S.; Rafieian-kopaei, M. Cheese Consumption in Relation to Cardiovascular Risk Factors among Iranian Adults- IHHP Study. *Nutr Res Pract* **2014**, *8*, 336, doi:10.4162/nrp.2014.8.3.336.
238. Zhang, M.; Dong, X.; Huang, Z.; Li, X.; Zhao, Y.; Wang, Y.; Zhu, H.; Fang, A.; Giovannucci, E.L. Cheese Consumption and Multiple Health Outcomes: An Umbrella Review and Updated Meta-Analysis of Prospective Studies. *Advances in Nutrition* **2023**, *14*, 1170–1186, doi:10.1016/j.advnut.2023.06.007.
239. Feeney, E.L.; Lamichhane, P.; Sheehan, J.J. The Cheese Matrix: Understanding the Impact of Cheese Structure on Aspects of Cardiovascular Health – A Food Science and a Human Nutrition Perspective. *Int J of Dairy Tech* **2021**, *74*, 656–670, doi:10.1111/1471-0307.12755.
240. Holden, L.A. Understanding the Environmental Impact of Global Dairy Production. *Journal of Animal Science* **2020**, *98*, skz365, doi:10.1093/jas/skz365.
241. European Union Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on Nutrition and Health Claims Made on Foods.
242. Fardet, A. New Hypotheses for the Health-Protective Mechanisms of Whole-Grain Cereals: What Is beyond Fibre? *Nutr. Res. Rev.* **2010**, *23*, 65–134, doi:10.1017/S0954422410000041.
243. Ndolo, V.U.; Beta, T. Distribution of Carotenoids in Endosperm, Germ, and Aleurone Fractions of Cereal Grain Kernels. *Food Chemistry* **2013**, *139*, 663–671, doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2013.01.014.
244. Chandrasekara, A.; Josheph Kumar, T. Roots and Tuber Crops as Functional Foods: A Review on Phytochemical Constituents and Their Potential Health Benefits. *International Journal of Food Science* **2016**, *2016*, 1–15, doi:10.1155/2016/3631647.
245. Monteiro, C.A.; Levy, R.B.; Claro, R.M.; Castro, I.R.R.D.; Cannon, G. A New Classification of Foods Based on the Extent and Purpose of Their Processing. *Cad. Saúde Pública* **2010**, *26*, 2039–2049, doi:10.1590/S0102-311X2010001100005.
246. Rosqvist, F.; Niinistö, S. Fats and Oils – a Scoping Review for Nordic Nutrition Recommendations 2023. *Food & Nutrition Research* **2024**, *68*, doi:10.29219/fnr.v68.10487.
247. Armstrong, L.E.; Johnson, E.C. Water Intake, Water Balance, and the Elusive Daily Water Requirement. *Nutrients* **2018**, *10*, 1928, doi:10.3390/nu10121928.
248. Riebl, S.K.; Davy, B.M. The Hydration Equation: Update on Water Balance and Cognitive Performance. *ACSM'S Health & Fitness Journal* **2013**, *17*, 21–28, doi:10.1249/FIT.0b013e3182a9570f.
249. Liska, D.; Mah, E.; Brisbois, T.; Barrios, P.L.; Baker, L.B.; Spriet, L.L. Narrative Review of Hydration and Selected Health Outcomes in the General Population. *Nutrients* **2019**, *11*, 70, doi:10.3390/nu11010070.
250. Malik, V.S.; Hu, F.B. The Role of Sugar-Sweetened Beverages in the Global Epidemics of Obesity and Chronic Diseases. *Nat Rev Endocrinol* **2022**, *18*, 205–218, doi:10.1038/s41574-021-00627-6.
251. Anastasiou, K.; Ribeiro De Melo, P.; Slater, S.; Hendrie, G.A.; Hadjidakou, M.; Baker, P.K.; Lawrence, M.A. From Harmful Nutrients to Ultra-Processed Foods: Exploring Shifts in 'Foods to Limit' Terminology Used in National Food-Based Dietary Guidelines. *Public Health Nutr.* **2023**, *26*, 2539–2550, doi:10.1017/S1368980022002580.

252. Koios, D.; Machado, P.; Lacy-Nichols, J. Representations of Ultra-Processed Foods: A Global Analysis of How Dietary Guidelines Refer to Levels of Food Processing. *Int J Health Policy Manag* **2022**, *1*, doi:10.34172/ijhpm.2022.6443.
253. Thapsuwan, S.; Phulkerd, S.; Chamrathirong, A.; Gray, R.S.; Jindaratnaporn, N.; Loyfah, N.; Thongcharoenchupong, N.; Pattaravanich, U. Relationship between Consumption of High Fat, Sugar or Sodium (HFSS) Food and Obesity and Non-Communicable Diseases. *BMJNPH* **2024**, *7*, 78–87, doi:10.1136/bmjnph-2023-000794.
254. Mayer-Davis, E.; Leidy, H.; Mattes, R.; Naimi, T.; Novotny, R.; Schneeman, B.; Kingshipp, B.; Spill, M.; Cole, N.; Bahnfleth, C.; et al. *Beverage Consumption and Growth, Size, Body Composition, and Risk of Overweight and Obesity: A Systematic Review*; U.S. Department of Agriculture, Food and Nutrition Service, Center for Nutrition Policy and Promotion, Nutrition Evidence Systematic Review, 2020;
255. Loyfah, N.; Chamrathirong, A.; Gray, R.S.; Pattaravanich, U.; Jindaratnaporn, N.; Thapsuwan, S.; Thongcharoenchupong, N.; Phulkerd, S. Influence of Multigenerational and Living-Alone Households on High Fat, Sugar or Sodium (HFSS) Food Consumption Pattern in Aging Population. *Appetite* **2025**, *204*, 107731, doi:10.1016/j.appet.2024.107731.
256. Monteiro, C.A.; Cannon, G.; Levy, R.B.; Moubarac, J.-C.; Louzada, M.L.; Rauber, F.; Khandpur, N.; Cediel, G.; Neri, D.; Martinez-Steele, E.; et al. Ultra-Processed Foods: What They Are and How to Identify Them. *Public Health Nutr.* **2019**, *22*, 936–941, doi:10.1017/S1368980018003762.
257. Adams, J.; Hofman, K.; Moubarac, J.-C.; Thow, A.M. Public Health Response to Ultra-Processed Food and Drinks. *BMJ* **2020**, m2391, doi:10.1136/bmj.m2391.
258. Lane, M.M.; Davis, J.A.; Beattie, S.; Gómez-Donoso, C.; Loughman, A.; O’Neil, A.; Jacka, F.; Berk, M.; Page, R.; Marx, W.; et al. Ultraprocessed Food and Chronic Noncommunicable Diseases: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of 43 Observational Studies. *Obesity Reviews* **2021**, *22*, e13146, doi:10.1111/obr.13146.
259. Leech, R.M.; Worsley, A.; Timperio, A.; McNaughton, S.A. Characterizing Eating Patterns: A Comparison of Eating Occasion Definitions. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **2015**, *102*, 1229–1237, doi:10.3945/ajcn.115.114660.
260. World Cancer Research Fund The Facts about Processed Meat. <https://www.wcrf.org/living-well/health-guides-cookbooks/the-facts-about-processed-meat/>.
261. Chung, M.G.; Li, Y.; Liu, J. Global Red and Processed Meat Trade and Non-Communicable Diseases. *BMJ Glob Health* **2021**, *6*, e006394, doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2021-006394.
262. WHO Red and Processed Meat in the Context of Health and the Environment: Many Shades of Red and Green. Information Brief. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240074828>.
263. *IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, Volume 114 ; Red Meat and Processed Meat*; IARC, Ed.; IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans; IARC Press: Lyon, 2018; ISBN 978-92-832-0152-6.
264. DiNicolantonio, J.J.; O’Keefe, J.H. Added Sugars Drive Insulin Resistance, Hyperinsulinemia, Hypertension, Type 2 Diabetes and Coronary Heart Disease. *Mo Med* **2022**, *119*, 519–523.
265. Filippini, T.; Malavolti, M.; Whelton, P.K.; Vinceti, M. Sodium Intake and Risk of Hypertension: A Systematic Review and Dose–Response Meta-Analysis of Observational Cohort Studies. *Curr Hypertens Rep* **2022**, *24*, 133–144, doi:10.1007/s11906-022-01182-9.
266. WHO Global Status Report on Alcohol and Health and Treatment of Substance Use Disorders. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2024. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240096745>.
267. Rehm, J.; Shield, K.D.; Weiderpass, E. Alcohol Consumption. A Leading Risk Factor for Cancer. *Chemico-Biological Interactions* **2020**, *331*, 109280, doi:10.1016/j.cbi.2020.109280.
268. Manthey, J.; Shield, K.; Rehm, J. Alcohol and Health. *The Lancet* **2022**, *400*, 1764–1765, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(22)02123-7.
269. Almiron-Roig, E.; Navas-Carretero, S.; Emery, P.; Martínez, J.A. Research into Food Portion Size: Methodological Aspects and Applications. *Food Funct.* **2018**, *9*, 715–739, doi:10.1039/C7FO01430A.

270. Eldridge, A.L.; Kotzakioulafi, E.; Debras, C.; Tsai, L.-T.; Meijer, G.W.; Salesse, F.; Gibney, E.R. Method to Define Recommended Portion Sizes for Consumer Guidance. *Eur J Nutr* **2025**, *64*, 62, doi:10.1007/s00394-024-03573-x.
271. European Union Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the Provision of Food Information to Consumers, Amending Regulations (EC) No 1924/2006 and (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council, and Repealing Commission Directive 87/250/EEC, Council Directive 90/496/EEC, Commission Directive 1999/10/EC, Directive 2000/13/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, Commission Directives 2002/67/EC and 2008/5/EC and Commission Regulation (EC) No 608/2004 Text with EEA Relevance. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2011/1169/oj>.
272. CREA Tabelle Di Composizione Degli Alimenti. <https://www.alimentinutrizione.it/presentazione-dati>.

Appendices

Appendix A

Decisions taken for mapping products from the EFSA (2011) data to the diets modelled in this study for each product group.

Table 1A. Example of selection of representative product per food category- to be adapted according to national food consumption data classification.

Type	Category	Representative Products	Notes
1. Beverages	1.1 Warm drinks	1.1.1 Tea 1.1.2 Cocoa 1.1.3 Coffee (Arabica)	All products within this category are classifiable as one of these three products.
	1.2 Water	1.2.1 Tap water	
	1.3 Sugary drinks	1.3.1 Soda (cola)	Cola is the most consumed soda in all three Living Lab (LL) countries.
	1.4 Alcoholic drinks	1.4.1 Beer 1.4.2 Wine	Remaining products are matched to representative products based on their main input ingredients (fruit based alcohol, like cider, is sorted into wine; grain-based alcohol, like whiskey, is sorted into beer). If no further information is available (for example "cocktail drink"), the product is classified as the most-consumed representative product in this group, which is beer.
	1.5 Fruit juices	1.5.1 Juice (mixed fruit)	We model the fruit input into this product according to the volume-weighted average of fruits from category 2.4 in each country.
2. Carbohydrate sources	2.1 Cereal products	2.1.1 Wheat 2.1.2 Rice 2.1.3 Oat 2.1.4 Rye	All wheat-based products comprise about 90% of all cereal products. The rest of the cereal-based products differ across the LL countries: in Ireland, oat is most prevalent, whereas in Germany it is rye and in France it is rice. If no information on the main ingredient (e.g. wheat semolina = wheat) of the product is available (for example "buns," the product is classified as the most-consumed representative product in this group, which is wheat.
	2.2 Starchy vegetables	2.2.1 Potatoes	This product category also includes cassava roots and sweet potatoes, but compared to ordinary potatoes the values are negligibly small. Hence, we classify all consumed products as potatoes, since production processes are also similar.
	2.3 Other vegetables and vegetable products	2.3.1 Fruiting vegetables (tomatoes) 2.3.2 Root vegetables (carrot) 2.3.3 Leafy vegetables (salad)	We decided to group this product category according to its botanical properties, as this makes the most difference within the production cycle and hence LCA modelling. For each botanical category, we picked one sensible product that is well-represented in all countries. All remaining

		2.3.4 Collard vegetables (white cabbage)	products are sorted into the representative product according to their botanical properties.
	2.4 Fruit and fruit products	2.4.1 Pomaceous fruit (apple) 2.4.2 Exotic fruit (banana) 2.4.3 Berries (strawberries) 2.4.4 Citrus fruit (oranges) 2.4.5 Stone fruit (peaches)	We grouped this category according to its botanical properties. The representative products within botanical groups are picked according to what is most consumed in all countries. All remaining products are sorted into the representative product that shares their botanical properties.
3. Protein sources	3.1 Beef	3.1.1 Beef	All beef-based meat products are modelled as beef. Under this category, we also included lamb, goat, sheep, and all farmed ruminant products. This is because they are considered red meat (in terms of health implications) and, as ruminants, also have large climate impacts (i.e. environmental implications).
	3.2 Pork	3.2.1 Pork	All pork-based meat products are modelled as pork.
	3.3 Poultry	3.3.1 Poultry	This includes all products derived from farmed poultry breeds, like chicken or goose, and also bred game poultry, like duck or guinea fowl.
	3.4 Meat, other	3.4.1 Venison 3.4.2 Beef and pork 3.4.3 Mixed meat	There is some venison consumed within the LL countries, which is mostly non-bred (like deer or boar) (Wikipedia 2024) and therefore has its own category, as free-roaming animals have very different environmental impacts (e.g. no synthetic fertilizer or farmed feed is necessary) and no social impacts, compared to farmed animals. We give venison the same impacts as poultry, as in Agribalyse it is mostly modelled as avian products (e.g. pheasant). The “beef and pork” or “mixed meat” is used for meat products consisting of two (beef and pork) or more (mixed meat) meat ingredients. Here we average the meat ingredients beef, pork, and poultry for modelling over all sub-categories of 3.4.
	3.5 Eggs	3.5.1 Eggs (chicken)	This encompasses all direct egg derivatives (e.g. hard-boiled egg or fried egg).
	3.6 Fish and Seafood	3.6.1 Marine fish (salmon) 3.6.2 Freshwater fish (trout) 3.6.3 Shellfish (mussels) 3.6.4 Fish mix	We differentiate these products according to their habitat and species. This is due to their production chains and the concomitant quantity of environmental and social impact. All remaining products are sorted into the representative product according to their habitual and species properties. The production difference of “farmed” or “free capture” fish is not given in EFSA data, which is why we use national averages to model this accordingly if possible. The “fish mix” category is used if there are no details given on the specific

			fish used within a product (e.g. “fish (meat)”). Here we average the fish ingredients for modelling over the rest categories of 3.6.
	3.7 Legumes	3.7.1 Peas (garden peas) 3.7.2 Lentils (brown) 3.7.3 Beans (common beans) 3.7.4 Chickpeas (chickpeas)	We differentiate legumes according to their botanical differences and model one representative product for each type of legume. All remaining products are sorted into the representative product according to their botanical properties.
4. Fat sources	4.1 Nuts and oilseeds	4.1.1 Almonds 4.1.2 Peanuts 4.1.3 Sunflower seeds	Peanuts are botanically considered a legume, but are consumed as a seed or nut in European diets. This is why we sorted them into 4.1. Almonds are the most-consumed nut in Europe, followed by walnuts (which botanically speaking are drupes), and hazelnuts, so we chose almonds as the representative nut product. We choose sunflower seeds as representative of oilseeds. Both the nuts and seed consumption shares are not consistent within the LL countries (besides peanuts, which is the most-consumed “nut” in every country), with Germany, for example, consuming more pumpkin seeds. However, these are a by-product of pumpkin production and hence a stringent modelling of sunflower seeds is more sensible. France consumes more chestnuts than almonds, which are not prevalent in any of the other countries. Therefore, we chose to go with overall representative products of nuts and seeds.
	4.2 Dairy products white (i.e. low milk input)	4.2.1 Milk 4.2.2 Yogurt 4.2.3 Processed milk	We disaggregated dairy products with low and high milk input, since the amount of milk used in dairy products is what drives the external costs (cf. Michalke et al. 2024). Within the “milk” category are all products that are direct derivatives of milk, like fermented milk, condensed milk, etc. Yogurt encompasses all minimally processed milk products, like quark or crème fraîche. Processed milk includes all highly processed products like ice cream, puddings, etc.
	4.3 Dairy products yellow (i.e. high milk input)	4.3.1 Hard cheese 4.3.2 Soft cheese	We model two cheeses: soft cheese with low milk input of about 5 l of milk per kg of cheese and hard cheese with high milk input of about 10 l of milk per kg of cheese. Depending on the production practice and quality of the milk (protein and fat content, etc.), this milk input varies even for the same sort of cheese, which is why these two general assumptions suffice for our modelling.
	4.4 Vegetable oils and fats	4.4.1 Olive oil 4.4.2 Sunflower oil 4.4.3 Margarine 4.4.4 Peanut oil	Again, we differentiate vegetable oils according to the botanical properties of their underlying main ingredient. Remaining products are sorted accordingly. Processes of sunflower, olive, and peanut oil rely on the production chain of their main ingredient. Margarine is a blend of different

			plant oils (we assume sunflower, peanut, and olive for it).
	4.5 Animal oils and fats	4.5.1 Butter 4.5.2 Animal fat	Animal fat is a by-product of animal meat production. We used these process chains to model it.
6. Rest	6.1 Sweets	6.1.1 Chocolate 6.1.2 Sugar (beet sugar)	The great majority of sweets are produced with either primarily sugar or chocolate or a mix of both. We sort products into these categories according to their main ingredients.
	6.2 Salt	6.2.1 Salt	All salt products (e.g. sea salt, rock salt) are included in this.
Other	Other	NA.	These are all products which we exclude from our assessment, either because we do not know what ingredients they entail (e.g. ready-to-eat meals for children), or they are not sortable into any of the dietary recommendations (e.g. food colouring). They amount to less than 2% of the overall products consumed and are therefore negligible.

Appendix B

An example of TCA application to dietary guidelines

As part of the Horizon PLAN'EAT project, TMG conducted a study titled "True Costs and Benefits of Three EU Dietary Patterns." This applied the methodology described in this document to evaluate the environmental and health impacts, social risks, and true costs associated with various dietary patterns across three European countries: Germany, Ireland, and France. The research compared the costs of current average diets—known as "Living Lab Diets" (LLDs)—in these countries with their respective National Dietary Recommendations (NRDs), and the Planetary Health Diet (PHD).

The three datasets used to make the comparison correspond to what is reported in the TCA approach description presented in this framework:

- Living Lab Diets correspond to current dietary patterns;
- National Dietary Recommendations correspond to national recommendations in FBDGs; and
- the PHD corresponds to the reference designed for sustainability balancing health and environmental trade-offs.

The results of the dietary assessments conducted for Germany and Ireland using TCA are presented to demonstrate the type of outputs that can be expected when integrating TCA into FBDGs.

The German example highlights the benefits of incorporating sustainability measures into NRDs, demonstrating its better performance compared to the PHD, as backed by TCA results. In contrast, the Irish example illustrates how NRDs can be further improved relative to the PHD by applying insights derived from TCA assessments.

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Figure 1B presents the cumulative environmental and health costs associated with different dietary patterns in Germany. These were calculated using environmental LCA with monetization (via the damage costs approach) and the COI approach for health costs. For the assessment of health costs, the costs associated with the NRDs are taken as the baseline. The deviations in costs for the LLDs and the PHD are then compared against this baseline. The results show that adopting the PHD results in substantial health cost savings. Transforming current consumption towards recommended diets—both NRDs and the PHD—would also result in environmental cost savings. German NRDs show better environmental performance than the PHD, demonstrating the effect of sustainability measures implemented in the NRD. This example is specifically

interesting as it underscores how TCA effectively showcases the benefits of sustainability measures taken within the German NRDs.

Figure 1B. Environmental and health costs per person per day of all three diets in Germany.

Figure 2B presents the actual consumed amounts of food (LLD) and the recommended amounts for NRDs and the PHD, demonstrating the underlying consumption and recommendation data that drive the results. Cost and impact assessments can thereby be based on an understanding of how variations in dietary patterns influence environmental and health outcomes.

Figure 2B. Composition of consumption values (LLD) and recommended intake (NRD, PHD) in Germany per person per day. Some food categories are not recommended within the NRD or PHD and the columns are therefore blank.

Environmental Costs

In addition to presenting the total environmental costs per product, it is also possible to analyze the contribution of different environmental impact categories to the total environmental costs for each food product. This analysis helps identify which environmental impacts contribute most significantly to overall costs, providing insights into the underlying factors driving these costs within product supply chains. This understanding can support improvements to reduce environmental costs.

Figure 3B compares the three diets across all product categories consumed and their respective cost contributions. The comparison highlights that different food categories contribute to environmental costs to varying degrees. While meat consumption is the largest contributor within the LLD, the NRD and PHD show a more balanced distribution of environmental impacts across all food categories. These findings are valuable for identifying products with the highest environmental impacts and refining dietary recommendations to mitigate these impacts.

In addition to presenting the total environmental costs per product, it is also possible to analyze the contribution of different environmental impact categories to the total environmental costs for each food product. This analysis helps identify which environmental impacts contribute most significantly to overall

costs, providing insights into the underlying factors driving these costs within product supply chains. This understanding can support improvements to reduce environmental costs.

Figure 3B. Contribution of the different food categories to the daily per capita environmental costs of the LLD, NRD, and PHD in Germany.

Health Costs

Figure 4B presents the health costs per person per day for the LLD and PHD across all dietary risk factors in Germany. NRD is the healthy benchmark diet and therefore depicted as the zero-line over all dietary risk factors. The results show that, in Germany, meat is the largest cost driver among all dietary-related health risks. An insufficient consumption of legumes in current diets also causes high health costs for Germany. The PHD would offer health benefits in Germany, especially compared to current consumption levels (LLD), due to its higher intake of plant-based food. These results help to understand the underlying causes of current dietary risks and provide a basis for mitigating these risks when developing FBDGs by offering healthier recommendations.

Figure 4B. Health costs per person per day for the LLD and PHD across all dietary risk factors in Germany.

Social Risks

Figure 5B shows the diets in comparison to one another with all product categories and their respective risk contribution to the diets, showing that different product categories contribute in varying degrees to social risks. Shifting from current diets to NRD or PHD would substantially reduce the high-risk contribution of certain product groups. The social risks often diverge from environmental and health impacts, especially when considering plant-based foods. While nuts and beans generally have lower negative health and environmental impacts compared to meat, their social risks depend heavily on the source and supply chain, with higher risks potentially arising from imports from certain regions.

Figure 5B. Contribution to social risks of the LLD, NRD, and PHD per person per day in Germany from different product groups.

Affordability of Germany Dietary Patterns

The cost assessment of diets reveals that the German LLD is the least expensive, with the NRD and the PHD being 57% and 66% more costly, respectively (Table 1B). When these costs are compared to the annual disposable income of the first decile of the German population, all three diets remain within the 20–30% affordability threshold. These findings demonstrate that healthier and more sustainable dietary recommendations, such as the NRD and PHD, are affordable for the German population.

Table 1B. The cost assessment in Germany.

LLD [2021 PPP €/cap/d]	NRD [2021 PPP €/cap/d]	PHD [2021 €/cap/d]
1.4	2.2	2.3

IRELAND

Figure 6B presents the cumulative environmental and health costs associated with different dietary patterns in Ireland. The results show that adopting NRDs toward the PHD results in substantial health costs savings. Similar to Germany, shifting current consumption patterns towards recommended diets—both the NRD and PHD—results in environmental cost savings, with the PHD demonstrating the greatest environmental cost reductions.

Figure 6B. Environmental and health costs per person per day of all three diets in Ireland.

Figure 7B. Composition of consumption values (LLD) and recommended intake (NRD, PHD) in Ireland per person per day. Some food categories are not recommended within the NRD or PHD and the columns are therefore blank.

Figure 7B presents the actual consumed amounts of food (LLD) and the recommended amounts for the NRD and PHD, demonstrating the underlying consumption and recommendation data that drive the results.

Environmental Costs

Figure 8B compares the diets, showing all product categories and their respective cost contributions. It is evident that different categories contribute to environmental costs to varying degrees. In the LLD and NRD, meat consumption is by far the largest cost contributor, while in the PHD, the costs across all product categories appear more balanced. The results suggest that Irish NRDs would benefit from structuring diets to align more closely with the PHD, making it more environmentally sustainable.

Figure 8B. Contribution to environmental costs of the LLD, NRD, and PHD from product categories in Ireland per person per day.

Health Costs

Health costs associated with Irish dietary patterns vary significantly between the PHD recommendations and current consumption levels under the LLD (Figure 9B). In Ireland, the PHD leads to substantial health cost savings compared to both the LLD and NRD, primarily due to a significant reduction in meat consumption.

Figure 9B. Health costs for the LLD and PHD across all dietary risk factors in Ireland per person per day. The NRD is the healthful benchmark diet and therefore depicted as the zero line over all dietary risk factors.

Social Risks

Figure 10B compares the diets, highlighting all product categories and their respective risk contributions. While the LLD carries the highest social risk in Ireland, mainly due to tea and coffee consumption, shifting towards the NRD and PHD can significantly reduce these risks. The NRD presents the lowest risks, although further reductions could be achieved by addressing high-risk categories such as milk and meat.

Figure 10B. Contribution to social risks of the LLD, NRD, and PHD from product groups for Ireland.

Affordability of Irish Dietary Patterns

The cost assessment of diets shows that the Irish LLD is the least expensive, with the costs of the NRD and PHD being very similar (Table 2B). The small difference between the NRD and PHD costs in Ireland suggests that transitioning to a more sustainable diet may not require significant additional financial resources, making both the NRD and PHD viable options for promoting health and sustainability. When these costs are compared to the annual disposable income of the first decile of the Irish population, all three diets remain affordable, with the highest percentage of income spent on the PHD at 3.8%.

Table 2B. The cost assessment in Ireland.

LLD [2021 PPP €/cap/d]	NRD [2021 PPP €/cap/d]	PHD [2021 €/cap/d]
1.34	1.64	1.66